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Open Data in Higher Education

DEFINITIONS, TRENDS, CHALLENGES

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Executive Summary

This report examines the role of open data in higher education, exploring its definitions, sources, applications, and ethical implications. Open data—data that is freely accessible, reusable, and distributed—has gained significance in academia, research, and governance. It plays a critical role in transparency, decision-making, and educational innovation. However, its potential is shaped by the availability, quality, and ethical considerations surrounding data usage.

Through Chapters 1 and 2 the report covers a conceptual approach and introduces trends in the debate about open data generation and usage. Nowadays, higher education institutions generate various forms of open data, including institutional data (HE grey data), data from MOOCs, and open government data (OGD). Studies highlight the increasing reliance on predictive analytics, machine learning, and ontological frameworks to enhance educational governance, student support, and resource allocation. Several initiatives enable institutions to share student data for academic performance analysis and policy planning. However, inconsistencies in data standardization and limited institutional readiness remain challenges to fully utilizing open data for educational transformation.

Chapter 3 delves into case studies from multiple regions, including Europe, North America, Asia and Latin America. This review underscores how open data is leveraged for educational management, student performance prediction, and transparency initiatives. Several universities have implemented data-driven interventions such as predictive models for student success, digital twins for campus management, and ontological approaches for educational data structuring. The MOOC sector, in particular, has been a fertile ground for open data use, with platforms like edX and MiriadaX applying data analytics to track student engagement and dropout rates. The increasing adoption of interoperable formats (e.g., RDF, JSON) and data ethics frameworks suggests a move towards greater accessibility and usability of open education data. However, challenges persist, particularly in data privacy, governance, and ethical considerations regarding student surveillance and institutional autonomy.

Finally, the report proposes a number of recommendations that cover the institutional strategy to use educational data, with a particular focus on data for Teaching, Learning, and Educational Governance. Open data is not only an administrative tool but also a resource for teaching and learning. Several studies emphasize how universities integrate open government data (OGD) into curricula to enhance students' data literacy and critical analysis skills. Examples include projects in political science, business studies, and computer engineering, where students use open data to assess governance practices and develop civic engagement tools. From a governance perspective, machine learning and predictive modeling are increasingly utilized to inform strategic decision-making in education. Universities are leveraging data mining techniques, synthetic data generation, and digital twins to improve student retention, staff recruitment, and campus operations. However, the ethical implications of open data in education remain a critical concern. Issues related to privacy, data ownership, and the commercialization of educational data have sparked debates on data justice and governance frameworks. Researchers advocate for ethical data stewardship, emphasizing stakeholder engagement, synthetic data for privacy protection, and institutional policies for responsible data usage.

The report concludes that while open data holds transformative potential for higher education, its success depends on strategic policies, ethical governance, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Addressing data privacy concerns, enhancing interoperability, and fostering data literacy will be essential to harness the full benefits of open data in academia.

Acronyms

AI,Artificial Intelligence

API,Application Programming Interface

ATLAS,A Large Ion Collider Experiment (Physics Experiment)

EdStats,Education Statistics (World Bank)

FAIR,"Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability"

GDPR,General Data Protection Regulation

HE,Higher Education

HESA,Higher Education Statistics Agency

IITE-UNESCO, Institute for Information Technologies in Education

JSON,JavaScript Object Notation

LOD,Linked Open Data

MOOC-Ed, Massive Open Online Course for Educators

MOOCs,Massive Open Online Courses

ODHE,Open Data for Higher Education

OEA,Open Education Analytics

OECD,Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OGD,Open Government Data

ORD,Open Research Data

PISA,Programme for International Student Assessment

QS,Quacquarelli Symonds (University Rankings)

RDF,Resource Description Framework

SABER,System Approach for Better Education Results

UDHR,Universal Declaration of Human Rights

Introduction

Relevance of the Topic

The concept of Open Data has gained traction in recent years, defined broadly as “data that anyone can access, use, and share” (Open Knowledge International, 2014). At its core, Open Data emphasizes the idea that knowledge, especially that which is publicly funded or generated by government institutions and research organizations, should be freely accessible to promote transparency, innovation, and civic empowerment. Open, public, and accessible knowledge has been a matter of concern for societies since the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) focused the relevant role of knowledge to support social justice and equity. Within the declaration, the need for universal access to information, as a springboard of knowledge building for social, cultural and economic purposes is central. Moreover, the digitalization of information and the broader agenda of public knowledge as a wealth that must be accessible to all fuelled several movements of open knowledge. Some relevant cases are the Open Source (access to code in computer science development), Open Access (access to research publications), and Open Education that have heralded the advancement of the human right to knowledge (OECD, 2007; Scanlon, 2014). Liaising with these aspirations, the movement of Open Science has committed to deliver science for all (Scheliga & Friesike, 2014).

In the last decade, the mentioned movements have embraced the idea of considering data as objects of interest. Digital data, being either captured or produced for several purposes by both the private and the public sector, by the system’s operators and users, became a sort of raw material which elaboration through big data techniques supported relevant developments (Kitchin, 2014). Data usage was received with enthusiasm, encompassing the acceleration of discoveries in the field of research, innovation in digital products and services bridging public-private collaboration, and digital activism (Molloy, 2011; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014). However, data monetization became also problematic and instilled controversies around private interests on public data and/or private data extracted (Gurstein, 2011). The notion of making public data accessible has gained traction in discussions around the restitution of public knowledge to citizens. As purported by Zuiderwijk & Janssen (2014), civic monitoring and appropriation of the results of open data as part of public knowledge is imperative. Open Data assumed several facets and forms of existence with highly specific debates, particularly connecting to the data generated in the public sphere of government, on the one hand, and the science and technology system, on the other. Having in common the public funding which supported their outcomes, these two areas of human activity were claimed to be accountable and transparent. Moreover, they should unleash public knowledge to support civic empowerment and social innovation (Baack, 2015).

Open data narratives retraced the discourse on technology intensification of unrestricted access to human knowledge, highlighting the Internet’s capacity to facilitate this objective. Since Castells

delineated the prevalence of the Internet as a key dimension of cultural transformation in what he termed the network society (Castells, 2011), the knowledge access utopia required deconstruction. The socio-economic and cultural factors hindering individuals from maximising Internet capabilities resulted in what was termed the “digital divide” (Hargittai, 2003). Similarly, digital data perpetually produced by the digital platforms utilised for personal professional transactions daily by connected humans is unevenly accessed and distributed, in what we could consider a *data divide* (Andrejevic, 2014). Moreover, data captured by private, big tech corporations generates extreme inequities, based on unconsented data extraction and monetization with prevalence of North-South economic relationships and domination (Ricaurte, 2019). In this case, the problem is connected with data which access is restricted to those interested in it, and though regulations have advanced in a relevant way in the last decade (Securiti Research Team, 2024; Zaeem & Barber, 2020), the issue is of central importance for the future socio-technical systems. Returning to data that can be open (particularly data generated by actors and institutions from the public sector) the impact will be limited if data are not accessible and used or transformed into knowledge by the society. Despite being considered a driving force for transparency of (e-)government policies, for economic growth and for the effectiveness, productivity, and reproducibility of scientific results, the potential of open data will not be unleashed without a relevant human understanding and engaging with them (Berends, J., Carrara, W., Engbers, W., & Vollers, 2017; Davies et al., 2016; Quarati & Raffaghelli, 2020; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014). Regardless of the enthusiasm surrounding Open Data, challenges persist in realizing its full potential (Santos-Hermosa et al., 2023). Issues related to data quality, metadata standards, and data literacy continue to impede the effective use and reuse of open datasets (Data Quality Campaign, 2024). As several studies suggest (Quarati, 2021; Ruijter et al., 2016; Zuiderwijk et al., 2020), the mere availability of data does not guarantee its impact; rather, structured frameworks, consistent quality standards, and user education are necessary to make Open Data genuinely accessible and usable.

Until here, we made a general presentation of open data as an opportunity and a problem for any human activity. The principles described above apply clearly to the field of education with specificities and concerns that require attention to develop research and practices about the topic of open data. Questions that the reader might anticipate in this regard are: For which purposes open data might be relevant in the field of education? Who produces open data? Where are open educational datasets? Though the topic is not new, and the existing studies emphasise the relevance of open data to advance both educational research and the quality of the educational provision, the topic is covered irregularly and through fragmented perspectives.

The aim of this report is to offer to the reader a picture on open data considering definitions and trends, to hence understand practices through cases. This exploration will let us move further into a number of recommendations for institutional leaders, policy makers and practitioners (particularly professors and teaching staff supporting teaching and learning in higher education).

Open data: from practices to concepts

In this chapter will introduce a conceptual analysis on open data as emerging term.

In fact, Open Data is not monolithic, and though the literature often deals with it as a singular term. The scholarship in the last decade has been delving on definitions and classifications that are mostly related to technical components of an open data record (Enríquez-Reyes et al., 2021); or identifying problems of publication, quality and usage (Quarati, 2021). In the context of this chapter, we will adopt forms of classification which are deemed relevant to address relevant educational practices and impact. We will later demonstrate how educational data encounters all the relevant issues of publication and quality identified in the general literature, hindering usage by practitioners, policymakers, and researchers. Scholars have highlighted the importance of classification as a tool to reduce complexity, enhance accessibility, and promote clarity across various fields, with no pretention of “natural” division of knowledge (Hollinger, 1976).

Classification systems enable a more structured approach to knowledge management, improving the way data is stored, retrieved, and used to solve practical problems (Agrawal & Mukti, 2020). This body of research supports the argument that in any domain, including education, the relevance of classification lies in its ability to organize, streamline, and enhance decision-making processes, making it an indispensable tool for driving effective outcomes. Without clear classifications, the wealth of available data may become overwhelming, leading to inefficient use or misinterpretation

In this context, we will undertake two operations of conceptualisation that will help us classify the types of open data.

Firstly, we will revisit the concept of open data according to the existing but divided traditions around open data, namely, the academia and the public administration. In this regard, we will make the distinction of open data produced by researchers and for scientific purposes, which main users are the same research community; and open data produced by any public institution, which can be enhanced by citizens and other administrations. For example, open data on higher education provision relates to the data delivered by institutions as part of a national education system. But open data analysing the relationship between higher education accessibility and students’ drop-out might be part of a research effort. These two types of open data might be found in different digital infrastructures or portals, and the data editors, curators and users might be diversified. Categorising these two types of open data produced by the digital infrastructures, quality standards and usage, we aim at easily identify relevant data sources and focus their application about open data-driven strategies in educational settings.

Secondly, we will classify open data in education according to the organisational levels within the education system that the open data represent: transnational/national (macro), institutional (meso), educational group/classroom (micro). Providing such a structure, we might help differentiating between open data sources, scope, quality, and applicable contexts. For instance, data related to student performance within a specific project carried out by an educator relate to the micro-level and could be of relevance to support further research on the topic, or reflection on practice, or data modelling for the same context of implementation. Data coming from transnational projects such as OECD PISA can be placed at a macro-level and might be adopted for policymaking. Even though, in both cases data can be adopted interchangeably in different contexts of application at macro, meso or micro level (the first example, as a case study of interest, supporting policymaking; or the transnational open data can address educational interventions). Nonetheless, the schematic categorisation can help open data usage according to the data coverage, the phenomena analysed, the possibility of study replication, etc. This targeted use of data might be a base to discuss data scalability and sustainability for the several purposes

of supporting educational quality, resource allocation, institutional improvements, professional development and so on.

Overall, understanding the different types of data would enable stakeholders to address concerns related to data quality and accessibility. By identifying specific types of open data, educational professionals and researchers can apply appropriate standards of verification, ensuring that the data is reliable and fit for purpose. The categorisation we offer might also allow for a consideration of the limitations and potential biases in different data sets; or to bridge the gap between abstract data availability and tangible educational improvements, leading to a critical approach on the potential of “data-driven” decisions.

Open data: two traditions

Two traditions of open data coexist with their own scholarly work, trends and recommendations. We refer to Open Government Data (OGD) and Open Research Data (ORD), each with unique purposes and implications (Santos-Hermosa et al., 2023). While both share the common goal of accessibility, they serve distinct audiences and functions and encounter specific challenges, particularly in terms of data quality, usability, and data literacy.

Open Government Data (OGD) is data produced and held by public agencies and governments. When made openly accessible, OGD serves as a powerful tool for promoting transparency, accountability, and public engagement in civic processes. According to Dai, Shin, and Smith, developing a culture of OGD within government institutions and the broader OGD ecosystem of users, including researchers, is essential to foster effective civic monitoring and public appropriation of data as part of public knowledge (Dai et al., 2018). Civic engagement with OGD allows citizens to oversee government activities, address public needs, and potentially generate social innovation by repurposing government data for community applications. Zuiderwijk and Janssen argue that OGD's civic potential underscores its role as a resource that supports democratic functions, such as transparency, public participation, and accountability, while also driving economic opportunities through data-driven innovation in the private sector (Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014). For example, platforms like data.gov and city-based portals in the U.S. provide publicly accessible datasets that empower individuals and organizations to monitor and utilize governmental data for various applications, from tracking municipal budgets to analysing public health trends (Barbosa et al., 2014). However, studies reveal that much of this data remains underutilized, with low view and download rates suggesting that simply publishing datasets is insufficient without ensuring that they are accessible, usable, and relevant to potential users (Quarati & Raffaghelli, 2020).

In contrast, Open Research Data (ORD) focuses on data generated through scientific inquiry and held within academic and research institutions. Aligned with the Open Science movement, ORD aims to make research data freely available to enhance transparency, reproducibility, and interdisciplinary collaboration. The European Commission's 2016 Mallorca Declaration emphasized that ORD could facilitate the replication of scientific experiments and thus support Open Science's goals of transparency and public accessibility (European Commission - RISE - Research Innovation and Science Policy Experts, 2016). Scheliga and Friesike (2014) argue that ORD represents a critical aspect of democratizing science by allowing researchers and the public to replicate studies, validate findings, and build upon existing data. The Open Science movement envisions data sharing as a fundamental step toward fostering collaboration and knowledge dissemination across borders and disciplines. As such, ORD benefits not only researchers

seeking to validate or extend prior findings but also industries and policymakers who rely on robust scientific data to inform innovation and decision-making.

The broader societal potential of Open Data lies in its ability to bridge information gaps, promote transparency, and drive innovation across multiple sectors. For instance, in the context of Open Government Data, the release of government-held datasets has shown promise in promoting civic engagement, improving public services, and fostering economic development. Baack (2015) notes that by enabling citizens to monitor government activities and access public information, OGD supports democratic accountability and empowers citizens to participate actively in civic processes. Moreover, the open data movement has spurred collaborations between public and private sectors, facilitating the development of new products and services based on government data. Cruz and Lee argue that OGD initiatives create opportunities for data-driven innovation in the private sector, as businesses can leverage government data to develop insights and solutions that address social challenges (Cruz & Lee, 2015).

Open Research Data, on the other hand, has the potential to transform scientific practices by promoting transparency, reproducibility, and interdisciplinary research. The Open Science movement, which advocates for the public availability and reusability of scientific data, encourages researchers to share data openly, allowing for the replication of studies and the generation of new insights from existing datasets. The European research framework Horizon 2020 and platforms like OpenAire aim to increase the visibility and accessibility of research data, reinforcing the idea that scientific knowledge should be a shared public good (European Commission, 2016). The transparency enabled by ORD aligns with the objectives of the Open Access movement, which seeks to make research outputs freely accessible. Fecher and Friesike (2014) highlight that ORD facilitates the socialization of scientific knowledge, allowing researchers across disciplines to access and build upon each other's work. This collaborative potential is particularly relevant in addressing complex global challenges, such as climate change and public health, which require interdisciplinary approaches and data-sharing practices that transcend traditional academic boundaries.

The practical implementation of Open Data policies, both for OGD and ORD, faces significant challenges. Data quality, accessibility, and user awareness are critical factors that influence the effectiveness of Open Data. One prominent issue across OGD and ORD is the quality of metadata, which is essential for enabling effective data search, retrieval, and understanding. Zuiderwijk et al. (2020) emphasize that metadata quality directly impacts the discoverability and usability of datasets, noting that insufficient metadata can hinder the interpretability and reuse of data, thus limiting its overall impact. Reiche and Höfig (2013) similarly argue that high-quality metadata is vital for dataset discoverability and have recommended creating automated evaluation platforms to assess metadata quality in OGD portals. In response to the widespread quality issues, the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability, Association of European Research Libraries, 2017) principles were developed as a framework to guide the quality standards of open data. The FAIR principles promote robust metadata and data structures, aiming to improve datasets usability, especially for machine processing, which is critical for large-scale data integration in research and industry (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

The benefits of OGD and ORD hinge not only on data availability but also on effective usage, which is closely tied to the quality and accessibility of data. For instance, while OGD has been associated with increased transparency in government operations and the potential for public sector innovation, its impact remains limited if the data is not actively used. Research shows that many OGD datasets are underutilized, with significant barriers to usage stemming from issues such as low data quality, lack of

awareness, and technical accessibility challenges. Barbosa et al.'s study on city-based OGD portals in the U.S. revealed that almost 60% of datasets are viewed fewer than 100 times, and only a small fraction are downloaded more than 100 times, indicating limited engagement (Barbosa et al., 2014). This pattern suggests that making data open does not necessarily lead to meaningful engagement or application; rather, targeted efforts to enhance accessibility and usability are required to maximize OGD's potential. Similarly, ORD faces hurdles that limit its usability and reach. In a study of Open Research Data practices in Educational Technology, Raffaghelli and Manca (2019) found that ORD is often underutilized, with datasets receiving limited views and downloads across platforms like Figshare, Zenodo, and Mendeley Data (Raffaghelli & Manca, 2019). The authors suggest that data quality and metadata standards are inconsistent, which undermines the data's utility for researchers and other users. McKiernan et al. (2016) note that while data sharing in fields such as life sciences and physical sciences has demonstrated benefits—often reflected in higher citation rates and research visibility—ORD practices remain fragmented, and many researchers lack adequate data literacy skills to effectively share and utilize open data. In addition to quality concerns, the effective reuse of ORD also depends on researchers' familiarity with data management practices and FAIR-aligned data standards, further highlighting the need for education and training in data literacy (Raffaghelli & Manca, 2022)

The relevance of data literacy for both traditions

Data literacy is a recurring theme in the discourse on Open Data, as data usage requires both technical and interpretive skills. The FAIR principles provide a foundation for data quality, but data literacy is essential for stakeholders across all levels—researchers, government officials, educators, and the public—to navigate the vast datasets available and derive meaningful insights. For example, the European Commission's Responsible Research and Innovation framework emphasizes data management and visualization as crucial skills for making scientific data accessible and comprehensible for all (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission, 2015). Data literacy is particularly critical in educational contexts where students, educators, and researchers engage with open data in varied ways, from educational data mining to the analysis of learning outcomes. As Zee and Reich (2018) point out, the ethical use of educational data and the interpretation of complex datasets present unique challenges that require careful consideration and data literacy development among both researchers and end-users.

Data literacy is a crucial, yet often overlooked, factor that influences the effectiveness of both OGD and ORD. The ability to access and interpret data is foundational to the Open Data movement, yet stakeholders often lack the necessary skills to work with complex datasets. Data literacy encompasses skills such as understanding data structures, evaluating data quality, and interpreting statistical information—skills that are critical for both government employees managing OGD and researchers handling ORD. For government employees responsible for publishing OGD, data literacy is essential to ensure that datasets are appropriately structured, annotated, and aligned with standards that make them usable by a broad audience. Similarly, end-users of OGD—ranging from civic organizations to individual citizens—require data literacy skills to analyse and make use of government data meaningfully. However, as Dai et al. (2018) argue, fostering a culture of OGD use requires active efforts to develop data literacy among both data producers and consumers. Without these skills, OGD's potential for civic empowerment

and social innovation remains unrealized, as users struggle to interpret and apply the data effectively (Loría-Solano et al., 2021).

In the realm of ORD, data literacy challenges are equally critical, as researchers must not only produce high-quality datasets but also navigate complex data management practices. In many cases, researchers lack training in data management and data-sharing practices, which limits their ability to make data accessible and reusable. As expressed earlier, data management skills among researchers to facilitate Open Science and improve data transparency is key in the EU context (European Commission, 2015). However, in practice, researchers are often inadequately prepared to manage and share data effectively, particularly in fields where data-sharing practices are less established (Koltay, 2017; Raffaghelli & Manca, 2022).

Beyond individual skills, the institutional and infrastructural support for data literacy plays a significant role in shaping Open Data practices. Institutions that emphasize data literacy training and provide resources for data management contribute to a more effective Open Data ecosystem. For example, initiatives like the Open Data Institute (ODI) and FAIR data guidelines are steps toward building a robust framework for data literacy. However, while these initiatives set standards, the practical implementation of data literacy training remains limited across institutions. Studies by Carlson et al. (2011) show that even advanced students and early-career researchers in fields like geoinformatics require structured training programs to develop proficiency in data management and usage, emphasizing that data literacy is a skill that needs to be cultivated systematically rather than assumed. Teal et al. (2015) further argue for the necessity of workshops and hands-on training sessions to improve data literacy, as these formats allow researchers and data users to engage actively with data management practices and develop the skills needed to navigate Open Data platforms. Hernández-Leo et al. (2023) emphasise the relevance of achieving an ethical dimension of data from design, namely, including accurate informed consent and letting participants to understand their rights about data, when they are not directly involved in data collection and interpretation.

The challenges connected to data literacy also intersect with ethical and legal considerations in Open Data use. In education, for example, researchers working with educational data must navigate issues such as student privacy and data protection regulations. Zee and Reich (2018) emphasize that interpreting and using educational data responsibly requires not only technical skills but also ethical awareness, as improper handling of data can lead to privacy breaches and ethical conflicts. The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has introduced stringent guidelines on data privacy, underscoring the need for data literacy that includes an understanding of legal compliance and ethical standards. This need for ethical literacy is particularly relevant in fields where data may contain sensitive information, such as health, education, and social sciences. As data becomes increasingly integral to research and public administration, the importance of data literacy extends beyond technical skills to encompass ethical considerations, further complicating the landscape of Open Data use.

In conclusion, the usage of Open Data, particularly OGD and ORD, is hindered by a combination of quality, accessibility, and data literacy challenges. Data quality, often reflected in metadata standards, plays a crucial role in determining the usability of Open Data, as poor metadata can render datasets difficult to interpret or apply. Additionally, data literacy—spanning technical, interpretive, and ethical skills—emerges as a fundamental requirement for both data producers and users. For OGD, fostering data literacy is necessary to empower citizens and enhance civic engagement, while for ORD, it is essential for promoting scientific transparency and reproducibility. Addressing these challenges requires

a concerted effort from governments, institutions, and researchers to prioritize data literacy training and establish robust standards for data quality and accessibility. Only by overcoming these barriers can Open Data fulfil its promise of driving innovation, transparency, and informed decision-making across sectors.

Understanding Trends

OGD and ORD in education institutions

To delve into the trends of open data in Higher Education, we carried out a review of the literature which is fully illustrated in Annex 1. The results of such analysis are presented in this section, which aim is to illustrate the trends of specific engagement and usage of open data by several actors in Higher Education.

In the landscape of Open Data, education presents a mixed picture regarding data sharing. Education researchers are increasingly encouraged to share data, especially as Open Research Data (ORD) policies and the Open Science movement advocate for transparency and reproducibility. However, studies reveal that actual data sharing practices among education researchers remain limited, often due to lack of data literacy, institutional support, or concerns over data privacy and ethical issues related to student information (Raffaghelli & Manca, 2019). Educational institutions, such as universities, also have varying levels of engagement with Open Data; while some actively contribute to open educational resources and publish research datasets, many institutions still have restrictive practices surrounding data access. Open Government Data (OGD) related to education—such as enrolment statistics, student performance metrics, and funding allocations—holds significant potential for improving educational outcomes, as it enables policymakers, researchers, and educators to analyse trends and make data-informed decisions. Similarly, sharing ORD in education can be transformative for educators and researchers, allowing them to build upon existing findings, enhance professional learning, and adapt instructional strategies based on evidence-based practices. By promoting both OGD and ORD sharing, the educational sector can drive transparency, foster collaboration, and support evidence-based improvements in teaching and learning processes. However, to realize these benefits, education stakeholders must address barriers to data sharing, including data literacy gaps, privacy concerns, and the need for clearer standards and incentives for open data use. Table 1 introduces one example each case (ORD-OGD) in education.

The data derived from educational research and the broader teaching and learning processes present ethical dilemmas and data literacy concerns for both researchers (in terms of rendering the data comprehensible and applicable) and end users (in terms of interpreting and using the data) (Zee & Reich, 2018). In the context of Responsible Research and Innovation framework advocated by the European Commission (2015), educational researchers should be committed to data management and visualisation in diversified ways to engage end users (educators, families, policy makers) with the results of educational research. An understated facet of this situation pertains to the restricted adoption and use of scientific research outputs in the educational domain by prospective users (stakeholders in the education and training system). Particularly, the idea of scientific literacy embedded in RRI has not evolved in the field of educational research as it has done in other fields (linked to several topics of wide interest, such as evolution, climate change, astrophysics, technological development overall). Also, the idea of a more equitable science has been evolving globally for the past decade; however, in the realm of education, challenges in research accessibility may stem from inherent issues within the framework and progress of educational science (Ho et al., 2015).

Table 1– Examples of ORD and OGD

Open Data Type	Example	Description, usage & impact
OPEN RESEARCH DATA	Massively Open Online Course for Educators (MOOC-Ed) network dataset (Kellogg & Edelmann, 2015) Harvard Dataverse	(Excerpt of the Abstract from the Open Data Record) <i>The dataset provides detailed information on the communications taking place between learners in two offerings of the Massively Open Online Course for Educators (MOOC-Eds) titled The Digital Learning Transition in K-12 Schools. (...) The primary use of this dataset is to enable social network analyses (SNAs) of these communications (...) as mechanisms to better understand factors that facilitate or impede the exchange of information among educators (...) (...)</i> The dataset is composed of four files with complete metadata.
	PIAAC – Survey of Adults’ Skills OECD	(citation from the OECD site https://www.oecd.org/en/about/programmes/piaac/piaac-data.html) <i>The PIAAC database contains the full set of responses from youths and adults. These files will be of use to statisticians and professional researchers who would like to undertake their own analysis of the PIAAC data. The files include the Public Use Files (PUF), codebooks, background questionnaires and all materials needed to process the data.</i>
OPEN GOVERNMENT DATA	Gross graduation ratio from higher education Higher Education Data – UNESCO, Institute for Statistics	(Citation from the UIS.Stat website, https://data.uis.unesco.org/) Example of a record extracted on Higher Education. <i>(...)As the official statistical agency of UNESCO, the UIS produces a wide range of state-of-the-art databases to fuel the policies and investments needed to transform lives and propel the world towards its development goals. (...)</i> <i>The data browser tool supports a comprehensive and easy-to-use browser for viewing and downloading the most popular UIS data and indicators in tables. Data are organized in a tree view by topic and presented using a simple three-dimensional format (indicator, country or region, year). Users can build their own customized tables and export data in Excel format.</i>
	Open Data Impact Map – Education Open Data Impact Map initiative	Citation from https://opendataimpactmap.org/education <i>Open data is being used to make educational opportunities accessible in many ways, including by helping parents and students make more informed educational choices and provide technical training. The most used data types include education, demographic and social, and government operations</i> <i>(...) From Kazakhstan to Brazil, open data is being used by developer groups, companies and universities alike to help people develop technical and data literacy skills.</i>

The particular instance of open data, as a pertinent and innovative component of the Open Science framework, warrants discussion as a resource for research in education (Hernández-Leo et al., 2023). There are several challenges in this regard. Firstly, educational sciences are an interdisciplinary field by definition, and while there are areas where the more strict conceptions of data science apply (for example, adopting pre-registration and the concept of replication of studies), there are topics like social justice in education or critical pedagogies that advance through qualitative case studies and action research, in contexts where data usage could be problematic given the sensible topics dealt with, or the unique conditions in which the case studies evolve. Finally, a lot is still to be done to take educational research to become an area of open science (van der Zee & Reich, 2018). In the field of Educational Technology, for instance, researchers tend to have low engagement with data-sharing practices, with many datasets receiving limited views and downloads. This low engagement suggests a need for training and support in researchers' data literacy, as they often lack the skills needed to make their data accessible, let alone reusable by others (Raffaghelli & Manca, 2019).

As for open government data at the crossover with transnational studies which are not academic, a relevant critique in open data usage deals with the misleading and rapid interpretations of statistics, rankings and reports, particularly at the level of policymaking (Biesta, 2015). Public access to educational data triggers policies and institutional practices that are shaped by the desire of "being represented" in a certain way through data (Piattoeva, 2021). Well-known cases are the "Teaching to Test" effect where institutions and educators put all their efforts in improving results through metrics offered by the evaluation system operating as standard (Biesta, 2015). Also present in the literature is the controversial impact of "Students Evaluation of Teaching", which assume that students are clients of a system and need to have their requirements satisfied (Braga et al., 2014). Despite the relevant idea of co-responsibility in building educational quality, and of taking to the forefront the students' voice, the issues spotted with "customer satisfaction approaches" relate to imposing limitations to critical perspectives, non-canonical approaches to teaching, and engagement with socio-cultural and educational transformation (Bertaccini et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the fast development of techniques of educational data mining commonly utilised in e-learning courses, encompassing a range of research methodologies that yield varied data kinds, has put the focus on rapid data collection and big data techniques, which are not necessarily connected with pedagogical values or needs (Williamson, 2016). Data capturing and monetisation by private, big technological corporations generates a grey area where data becomes a gain for few deciding for all. Needless to say, such data and the relating algorithms applied does not become open data, in a conflictive situation where private platforms enter into education as a public interest and service (Kerssens & de Haan, 2022; Rivera-Vargas et al., 2024). Through these lenses, open data can become a problematic field of practice, that requires careful configuration in the future. It is necessary to deal with data justice and educational values before declaring the potential of new technologies supporting rapid approaches to data collection and analysis. In this regard, Christine Borgman was visionary while highlighting the situation in 2018, pointing out that stewardship of data is a great problem, and defining the middle category of "grey data" as particularly applicable to the case of universities. In her words:

Universities are stewards of vast amounts of data. These data provide many new opportunities for research, teaching, administration, partnerships, and strategic planning. Data take many forms, have many origins, and have many uses. Data ownership is rarely clear, especially for research data, and the costs and mechanisms for stewardship are poorly understood. Although data are difficult to manage and

govern in any institution, universities face a particularly complex set of responsibilities and risks (Borgman, 2018, p. 368).

Although we can theoretically describe good stewardship as the dissemination of some data beneficial to institutional objectives or stakeholders, while restricting the release of data that could harm stakeholder interests, the practical application is markedly distinct. Academic freedom from both students and faculty means that anyone can have access to the right or needed data, as far as anyone has the right of data privacy, confidentiality, and security (Borgman, *ibidem*). In concrete terms, while a dataset from teaching and learning could be necessary to conduct rigorous research, the monetization through its transformation in analytics or recommendations systems as commercial products could be problematic. Consequently, the stewardship of data and public trust might be asymmetrical, according to the stakeholders engaged in data usage.

Studies cited up to this point indicate that the quality of open data requires extensive enhancement and the systematic organisation of aggregation methods to improve its usability, which relates to one initial level of socio-technical concern. But also, the tight relationship between the type of open data generated and the educational values promoted through open data usage are a crucial area of reflection to advance the discussion. All in all, we need to remember that while the ORD will aim at advancing the knowledge of educational processes and particularly of teaching and learning, they might not be sufficiently massive or systematic to be adapted to daily decision making by any educational institution or even classroom. Forcefully, OGD can offer relevant data for interventions or strategic planning at national or international level. Nevertheless, they require careful revision from the point of view of quality and conceptualisation, for national standards like the scores for colleges admissions or quality measurements through students' surveys might oversimplify the representation of educational scenarios and their relating possible futures. There is maybe an interesting tension between the two traditions in open data (ORD and OGD) where the former provides advanced or original views on educational phenomena, and the later can scale up usage to inform and support interventions for quality and access to education.

Tellingly, it is key to develop diverse forms of data literacy within the educational sector, encompassing both research and instruction, to approach an ethical and fair dissemination, utilisation, and re-appropriation of generated data. Figure 1 represents this type of relationship, the impact and interests around the two open data traditions. The concepts revised hitherto regarding ORD highlight that despite regulations addressing educational researchers to increase their engagement with public knowledge through open science and hence, quality open data, there is still a long way to go. As for the OGD, openness and transparency are heralded in relevant regulations (see for example GDPR), empowering citizens (and hence learners) to own the data they generate. And yet, the literature highlights the fragmentary vision and approaches from public institutions like the universities to share and re-use open data (Raffaghelli & Sangrà, 2023). There are yet relevant questions requiring exploration: what data can we genuinely disclose? How can the shared data jeopardise students and teachers, and how could they be engaged with the usage of their data for good? What strategies can we employ to enhance awareness among fellow academics on the usability of the data produced in education? And which are the ethical limits of such usability? What methods may be employed to educate teachers and students on utilising open data for their advantage in informal, formal, and non-formal learning contexts?

Figure 1– Open Data in Education: Two traditions, different sources and purposes.

Open education data: macro, meso and micro levels

In social research (where we can place education), the macro, meso, and micro levels provide distinct but interconnected lenses to analyse complex phenomena in social research (Serpa & Ferreira, 2019). The macro level focuses on large-scale structures and systemic factors, such as national education policies, socioeconomic inequalities, cultural and ideological influences on curricula, and global trends driven by international organizations like UNESCO. It explores how these broader forces shape education systems and access on a societal scale. The meso level examines intermediate structures, such as schools, districts, or local communities, that link macro-level policies with micro-level experiences. It investigates how institutions function, how school leadership implements reforms, and how schools collaborate with families or community organizations to influence educational outcomes. The micro level delves into the most granular aspects, focusing on individual and small-group interactions, such as teacher-student relationships, classroom dynamics, and the influence of family background on learning. These levels are deeply interrelated: macro factors shape institutional practices at the meso level and individual experiences at the micro level, while behaviours and trends observed at the micro and meso levels can aggregate to influence systemic change at the macro level. By analysing phenomena across these levels, researchers can capture the complexity of educational processes, uncovering how broad systemic factors interact with local practices and individual experiences to design effective, context-sensitive interventions and policies. Several scholarly works in education examine the macro, meso, and micro levels of analysis. Some have explored the complexity of achieving SDG 4 by analysing its targets through micro (individual), meso (institutional), and macro (systemic) lenses, highlighting the need for cooperation among various

actors to enhance educational quality (Boeren, 2019). There is also research in which higher education trajectories, focusing on how micro-level (individual decision-making), meso-level (institutional characteristics), and macro-level (national education systems) are classified to understand how these level influence students' paths and outcomes Haas and Hadjar (2020). This approach has been followed also to address the complexities of defining and achieving quality in higher education (Krause et al 2011). Coming from the usage of students data some studies explored how various institutional factors at different levels influence the adoption of systems that capture students' data and use them through more or less refined algorithmic techniques to trigger teachers and learners' behaviour according to models of "success" or desired standards (Buckingham Shum & Luckin, 2019; Prinsloo et al., 2018). The authors propose an "institutional cartography" to understand these influences, considering the several impact analytics might have on people (Prinsloo et al, op.cit). At the micro level, the authors place individual stakeholders, such as students and faculty members, and their interactions with learning analytics. Factors at this level include personal attitudes, competencies, and the direct impact of analytics on teaching and learning practices. At the meso level, the organizational units like departments or faculties within an institution are encompassed. At this level, the focus is on how learning analytics are integrated into institutional processes, policies, and the culture of specific units. Finally, at the macro level, the broader systemic and structural elements, including national education policies, regulatory frameworks, and societal expectations that shape the overarching environment in which institutions operate. Having made this classification, the authors emphasize that successful implementation of data-driven systems informing educational interventions and policies in higher education requires navigating the complexities and interactions across these three levels, acknowledging that challenges at one level can significantly impact the others.

Similarly, we can consider that Education Open Data (which is based on all sorts of data produced by educational institutions and the educational system) is collected and impact at different levels, though disentangling neatly the several levels is a schematic action for the sole purpose of understanding complexity. Not embracing the macro, meso, and micro level, but with an approach of classification that retrace these levels, Atenas & Havemann (2019) have carefully informed the state of open data in education. These authors have defined several levels of open data production, connecting them to the types of information the open data can address, and types of usage different stakeholders may carry out. Fig. 2 presents a definition stemming from the several references (macro, meso and micro usage in educational research), the types of data and their scope.

The diagram outlines the role of open data in education across three levels: Education Systems (Macro), Education Institutions (meso), and Education Processes (Micro), highlighting their different data collection purposes and potential open data generation. At the macro level, data is collected transnationally, focusing on national data about Early Childhood Education and Care, Primary, Secondary, Vocational Education, and Higher Education. This data is generally used for evidence-based policymaking and educational planning, aiding in the development of strategies to improve education systems' performance and impact, as exemplified by international programs like the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) by OECD and the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) by IEA. At the meso level, data includes administrative, socio-demographic, and quality metrics about the characteristics of schools, vocational centres, and universities. This data informs educational management, guides families, and supports students in selecting programs and providers, with examples like HESA (Higher Education Statistics Agency, UK), UniversiDATA (Spain), and Scuola in Chiaro (MIUR, Italy). At the micro level, data relates to teaching and learning processes, extracted or generated by

education institutions through reports, studies, and research. It is used as evidence to address the effectiveness of teaching and learning, with examples such as MOOC-Ed network data (Kellogg & Edelmann, 2015). This hierarchical structure demonstrates how open data at various levels supports targeted and comprehensive educational improvements.

Figure 2– Levels of analysis of Open Data

As expressed in the UNESCO IITE policy brief (Duggan, 2020), anticipating the hype of Generative AI, the promise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education lies in its potential to revolutionize teaching and learning by enhancing personalization, improving efficiency, and fostering inclusivity. However, AI is fed by data, that must be curated, organized, labelled to “make sense” of the AI promise. The recent literature on AI is bold in highlighting that it can tailor the delivery, content, and pace of education to individual student needs, enabling personalized learning experiences that support diverse learning styles and abilities. A decade of literature on predictive analytics and machine learning has claimed that through these “intelligent systems” we can analyse vast amounts of data to identify patterns, anticipate challenges, and offer actionable insights, benefiting all stakeholders—from students and teachers to administrators and policymakers. However, if data neglects minority categories, for they are only applicable to an expected “universalized” category, will AI provide the expected response?

AI developers also hold the promise of automating routine tasks, such as grading and administrative work, freeing educators to focus on more meaningful interactions with students. They purport that AI can bridge gaps in accessibility by providing adaptive technologies for learners with disabilities or those in underserved regions. In the same vein, there is a relevant strand of literature attempting to demonstrate that AI-powered systems can offer real-time feedback, adaptive assessments, and dynamic content recommendations, enhancing engagement and outcomes. The key issue here is that the data adopted to develop such services might not be accessible to all, or could be processed efficiently by those that sell

platforms that capture the data over which those AI-powered services are placed (Williamson, 2023). As a result, AI-powered tools create ethical dilemmas about data ownership and sovereignty.

The AI promises must be reconsidered on the light of data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the digital divide, ensuring AI is deployed throughout the lenses of institutional educational vision and mission, which encompasses data collection and access to data. This is a relevant starting point to make data usage for AI purposes ethically and equitable. The AI-powered tools hence lead to another huge debate that falls outside the goals of this report, relating to AI problematic impacts. Nonetheless, the basic material of which AI is built upon, and that allows tailored, local or community developments of technologies draws back to open data (Digital Science, 2023). Was a decade of policies, infrastructure developments and data literacy training a waste of time, in the light of big tech corporations' appropriation of the wealth of public information on the web to develop products with commercial interests? This is a dilemma: there is general agreement that AI could be a driver of human development, access to knowledge and opportunities to live well, but it comes with criticalities that are ineluctable. Therefore, the reflection on open data quality and production by higher education institutions is a compelling discussion.

Four examples of higher education (open) data collection, and usage

Up to here, we have framed open data collection as pivotal in advancing transparency, decision-making, and innovation in the educational sector, we will advance our exploration by considering three examples of open data collection and usage. This review examines four exemplary portals—Jisc's Data Analytics (UK), UniversiDATA (Spain), the European Data Portal (EDP), and Open Education Analytics (OEA)—that demonstrate diverse methodologies and impacts in the realm of educational data management and application. These platforms not only showcase innovative approaches to leveraging data but also highlight the critical role of open access in promoting institutional efficiency, transparency, and societal benefit.

Jisc's Data Analytics portal (UK) provides a comprehensive suite of services tailored to support higher and further education institutions in leveraging data for informed decision-making. One of the key offerings is the Learning Analytics Service, which integrates data from various student systems to deliver actionable insights. This service is instrumental in enhancing student engagement, refining teaching methodologies, and improving the overall student experience. Another flagship service is Heidi Plus, a powerful data visualization and analytics tool. Heidi Plus grants access to up to 15 years of HESA (Higher Education Statistics Agency) data, allowing institutions to create custom visualizations and dashboards. These capabilities enable strategic planning, institutional benchmarking, and a deeper understanding of trends over time. For institutions seeking tailored solutions, Jisc's Data Consultancy offers bespoke analytical support, including customized data visualizations, workshops, and expert guidance to help institutions interpret complex datasets and derive actionable insights. Complementing this is Interactive Insights, a set of co-designed dashboard suites developed with input from higher education professionals. These dashboards are specifically designed to aid universities in institutional research, benchmarking, and strategic planning. Additionally, Jisc offers a hardware-free Attendance Monitoring solution that integrates seamlessly with existing timetabling systems. This tool helps institutions efficiently track student attendance, supporting engagement and retention strategies. Through these innovative tools and services, Jisc empowers educational institutions to gain valuable insights across various operational

areas, from student performance and engagement to financial planning. By providing robust data-driven solutions, the portal facilitates enhanced strategic decision-making and operational efficiency for the education sector.

UniversiDATA (Spain) is a collaborative open data portal specializing in the higher education sector in Spain. Initiated by public Spanish universities, including Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, and Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, in partnership with the company Dimetrical, its primary objective is to promote open data within higher education, facilitating its use and value for both data publishers (universities) and consumers (the public and the infomediary sector). The portal serves as a centralized access point where universities, while maintaining their individual identities and autonomy, share data through standardized criteria. This standardization enhances the analytical capabilities of the published datasets, showcases the collaborative efforts of the institutions, and ensures the project's sustainability and reach. UniversiDATA encompasses various thematic areas, including studies and students, economy and heritage, research activity, human resources, organization and services, and other relevant data. It provides tools like the "Visor de Presupuestos" (Budget Viewer) to facilitate the analysis of university budgets, making complex financial data more accessible to the public. Additionally, UniversiDATA organizes initiatives such as datathons to encourage the reuse of open data and foster innovation. These events provide a platform for participants to showcase projects that process open data to create services, promoting knowledge sharing and collaboration within the community. Through these efforts, UniversiDATA aims to enhance transparency, encourage the reuse of university data, and generate added value for society by providing open access to comprehensive information about the higher education sector in Spain.

The European Data Portal (EDP) serves as a comprehensive repository, offering over 9,000 datasets related to education sourced from various European countries. These datasets encompass a wide range of information, including administrative data, curriculum details, performance metrics, and job opportunities within academia. Such open education data is invaluable to stakeholders like government officials aiming to enhance educational systems, businesses seeking talent, researchers in need of supplementary data, and parents evaluating school options. The EDP also highlights practical applications of open education data through various use cases. For instance, the 'School Information Map' is a free interactive platform in Ireland that enables users to locate schools and explore the facilities they offer, particularly for special educational needs. This tool assists parents in making informed decisions about their children's education. Another example is 'Mime Consulting' in the United Kingdom, which provides insights into education and training options, allowing users to compare career paths and understand the skills in demand for specific jobs. By presenting this information, Mime Consulting guides individuals in selecting appropriate education and training pathways. Additionally, global initiatives like the World Bank's Education Statistics (EdStats) portal publish worldwide education data on topics such as access, policy, learning, and expenditures. Tools like EdStats Planet, a visualisation and mapping tool, allow users to create interactive maps and graphs based on educational statistical data. Another tool, the System Approach for Better Education Results (SABER), evaluates the quality of education policies around the world, enabling countries to benchmark themselves against others to identify opportunities for further development. These examples demonstrate the significant impact of open education data in fostering transparency, supporting informed decision-making, and promoting innovation across the educational landscape in Europe.

The portal Open Education Analytics (OEA) builds over the services provided by Azure data integrated with open-source tools. The webportal (<https://openeducationanalytics.org/get-started/>) is introduced as an open-source community initiative that collaborates with education systems worldwide to develop modern data intelligence capabilities. The website provides a structured approach for educational institutions embarking on data modernization and AI integration. The process begins with defining the problem by engaging key stakeholders—learners, educators, school leaders, and data teams—to ensure that data projects address relevant educational challenges. This collaborative approach helps prevent common pitfalls such as misidentifying issues, misusing data, or making incorrect assumptions. Next, institutions can set up a modern data estate using the OEA reference architecture, which leverages powerful Azure data services and open-source tools. This setup can be accomplished swiftly by following a three-step process outlined in the OEA GitHub repository. Once the data infrastructure is in place, educational data teams can explore and model data using open-source modules available on OEA's GitHub. These resources facilitate the connection and analysis of various datasets, enabling the development of models that address common educational challenges, such as predicting at-risk students or assessing digital equity. Finally, OEA emphasizes the importance of communicating insights through data visualizations and reports, utilizing tools like Power BI. Institutions are encouraged to set up automated actions based on analytics using low-code applications, thereby operationalizing data-driven decisions to enhance learning outcomes. By following this structured approach, educational institutions can effectively harness data and AI to improve decision-making, support learners, and advance educational equity.

Table 2 – Open Data Portals

Portal	Key Features	Good Practice
National data portals		
Jisc's Data Analytics (UK)	Offers comprehensive data-driven solutions like Learning Analytics Service and Heidi Plus for student engagement and strategic planning. Introduces Attendance Monitoring and bespoke Data Consultancy services for tailored analytics.	Interactive Insights dashboards, co-designed with higher education professionals, highlight effective collaboration.
UniversiDATA (Spain)	Centralized open data portal for Spanish universities with standardized data sharing across thematic areas (e.g., finance, research). Tools like Budget Viewer and events like datathons encourage innovation and public engagement.	Standardized criteria for data sharing improve usability and ensure consistent, actionable data.
Transnational Data Portal		
European Data Portal (EDP)	Aggregates over 9,000 datasets from European countries, covering curriculum, performance, and academic opportunities. Demonstrates open data utility through tools like the 'School Information Map' and 'Mime Consulting.'	Interactive tools like EdStats StatPlanet and SABER foster global benchmarking and policy evaluation.
Independent Data Portal (Commercial Platform)		
Open Education Analytics (OEA)	Combines Azure services with open-source tools for modernizing data infrastructure and integrating AI. Provides structured steps for problem definition,	Operationalizing data insights with automated actions and visual reports aligns analytics with outcomes.

Portal	Key Features	Good Practice
	data estate setup, and actionable insights development.	

Each platform demonstrates unique strengths and strategies for maximizing the value of open data in education. From Jisc’s targeted analytics services and UniversiDATA’s collaborative initiatives to the EDP’s comprehensive dataset repository and OEA’s focus on AI integration, these examples highlight the transformative potential of open educational data. Common themes such as stakeholder collaboration, standardized data practices, and the use of cutting-edge technologies underscore the importance of innovation in addressing educational challenges and advancing equity and efficiency in the sector. These good practices serve as a blueprint for institutions seeking to harness the power of open data in education.

Case analysis

Enhanced methodology for open data analysis in Open Universities

In this chapter, we will introduce five cases of open data usage in higher education to illustrate the current trends and activities.

Basing on the IITE relevant work in the field of quality benchmarking applied to open universities (cfr. Annex 1), we will focus on Open Data as element within processes of digital transformation. Key aspects of good practice with Open Data at the crossover with the relevant areas of benchmarking mentioned in IITE documentation (UNESCO-IITE, 2023) has been hence considered to develop the current methodology. Table 2 displays how the open data practices should contribute to the analysis of benchmarking, guiding hence to the analysis of cases to define good and best practice. One final “ethical” dimension is added over the bases of the literature analysis conducted in this report.

The mentioned IITE report guides us to recognise several critical factors in including Open Data as part of a quality culture (Ehlers, 2009) within Open Universities. For example, despite the data collection that occurs due to the fully online studies, there are technological and infrastructure limitations to store, manage and share data in standardized, machine-readable formats. The impact of such limitations relates to the limited capacity to create and maintain Open Data repositories as well as the difficulties in adopting data standards like RDF or JSON that are essential for interoperability and accessibility. Connected to this problem, incomplete, inconsistent, poorly documented datasets are also another frequent problem, as we highlighted in our review of the literature, and it also appears in the report mentioned. Following our integrated perspective on open data as socio-technical systems, we observe that data privacy and security are a challenge due to the appropriate application of the GDPR or other national regulations relating to data sharing if open. As a result, there might be misuse of sensitive data (de-anonymisation risks, identification of discriminatory patterns in the data adopted to represent collectives, etc.), hindering the willingness to collaborate in datasets sharing openly. Particularly, anonymisation for public use is an issue that requires further investigation yet, with implications for clearness in mainstreaming institutional practices. Open data requires strong approaches of stewardship and empirical analysis of educational and social impact, beyond enthusiasm about the technological possibilities to share data. In this regard, institutional resistance could be intended as a regressive approach, but also, it could be part of a proactive action to avoid surveillance or data monetization, as we earlier explained in this report. The lack of agreement at the political level within the OU, which might benefit from networks focused on the topic and promoting transparency and collaboration. In this regard, intellectual property and ownership are issues that require attention. Though Creative Commons practices and Open Institutional repositories are a widespread approach in OU, the material shared could be used in several ways that are problematic, as we explained above.

The whole problem of how and why sharing data across open universities requires attention, as it emerges from the research analysis and from the IITE report based on concrete case studies. The financial and resource constraints need to be explored, for open data and data-driven initiatives require research, development, piloting and discussion at various levels. One peculiarity that necessitates investment is data literacy. The limited understanding among staff and students about the value and principles of Open data might encompass missed opportunities to generate an open data culture.

However, data literacy cannot be indented as an obligation to take part in training activities based on institutional decision-making, but as a participatory approach to learning on open data-driven practices that lead to digital and data sovereignty. This implies technical understanding of the open data and overall digital infrastructure (including software provision), type of data extracted, goals of data extraction and analysis, goals of data visualisation or what is delivered to end users as data-driven interfaces. Such a participatory approach to an institutional data culture is part of an ethical approach which builds over the idea of a situated, community-based idea of education (where open data plays a role in), and not an extractive logic imposed on staff, teachers and students.

Based on the definition of Benchmarking provided in the above report and considering this same report as a linked investigation, we consider the following definitions for the cases analysis.

Benchmarking for Open Universities (p.28, IITE report)

Benchmarking can be internal or external. Internal benchmarking is a process of comparing performance in similar processes between different departments, campuses or sites within a university, and identifying best practice in the institution, without the need to use an external standard to compare the results. Within one organisation, access to sensitive information is easier, standardized data is available and less time and resources are needed. Internal benchmarking can be used to compare similar time periods in the past and future or compare different projects or departments. External benchmarking/best practice benchmarking compares activities across institutions using information about outside organisations that are known to be best in class.

From the three types of benchmarking's definition provided, we will consider the third one, namely, *External trans-institutional benchmarking involves multiple institutions around a common interest to build understanding of the process* (op.cit) in which the open universities are mapped about open data practices and strategies.

As for the focus of benchmarking, we considered "process benchmarking", *which focuses on specific processes and involves comparison of good practices to identify innovative solutions*. This type of benchmarking can be internal or external, therefore, applicable to international collaborative benchmarking.

As for the procedures, we adopted a "desk research" approach (Moore, 2006) basing on a cascade in three steps:

- 1) each case was analysed through the main university websites as starting point.
- 2) Each case was enriched through complementary documentation obtained from connected websites search (including Wikipedia);
- 3) Research literature connected to the case was finally explored, touching upon digital learning strategies, open access and open education, data infrastructures, data ethics, data safety, learning analytics.

Table 3– Approach to the Open Data Analysis

Areas of Benchmarking	Open Data Culture	Activities to map
<p>Open Data sharing to contribute to open knowledge</p> <p>[All levels, OGD/ORD data]</p>	<p>Open Data can provide baseline datasets on learner demographics, academic performance, or resource usage to inform benchmarking metrics. Sharing institutional data through Open Data portals promotes inter-university comparisons and mutual learning.</p>	<p>Existence of guidelines for managing, sharing, and utilizing institutional data in compliance with ethical standards and privacy laws</p>
<p>Fostering HEIs’ open data practises for quality education</p> <p>[All levels, OGD/ORD data]</p>	<p>Making administrative and academic datasets openly accessible enables researchers and policymakers to develop solutions for quality assurance and educational effectiveness. Open Data initiatives can shed light on disparities in access to education, enabling targeted interventions for inclusivity.</p>	<p>Partner with other universities, governments, or organizations (e.g., Open Data portals or research platforms) to co-create and share datasets relevant to education.</p> <p>Application of benchmarking tools to produce specific instruments like an Open Data Maturity Model or the Open Data Pathway to assess and improve how Open Data is managed and utilized in the institution.</p> <p>Highlight the societal benefits of Open Data in education, such as fostering innovation in pedagogy or supporting lifelong learning initiatives</p>
<p>Open Data to enhance teaching and learning</p> <p>[Micro-level, OGD/ORD data]</p>	<p>Open Data in the form of learning analytics or educational resources can empower students to make data-informed decisions about their learning pathways</p>	<p>Open Data usage for student projects, particularly in the form of learning analytics, but also through critical data literacy in specific professional areas or as an overall approach to knowledge.</p>
<p>Ethical concerns</p> <p>[All levels, OGD/ORD data]</p>	<p>Open Data release should consider ethical dimensions as stakeholders’ involvement. Critical data literacy approaches should be considered to understand what it takes to produce and use open data for the institution and for the single user. Data sovereignty should be promoted as part of a situated approach protecting local identities and agency</p>	<p>Open Data generation over the bases of privacy by design, clear practises of informed consent, continuous feedback to data-driven services and products, presence of critical data literacy approaches including data ethics, data justice and data sovereignty integrated to technical understanding of the digital and data-infrastructure adopted in an open university.</p>

Sampling

Continuing with the alignment with the Benchmarking study, we attempted to cover the five major geographic regions globally, selecting one to two cases for each of such regions out from the original list of institutions. The number of cases is connected to the presence of Open Universities in the region and the socio-economic and cultural diversity. The list was converted to a casual sequence of numbers, and eight cases were extracted randomly, stratifying by continent. We also added a university in South America, not present in the IITE report, namely the Open University of Brazil to achieve further global representation. Table 4 introduces the selection of cases and links presenting the institutions via their official webpage.

Table 4 – Sampled cases

Area	Institution	Profile	Link
Asia and the Pacific	Allama Iqbal Open University (Pakistan)	<p>Type: Public Established: 1974 Number of Students: Over 1 mln students Courses Offered: wide range of programs, including matriculation, intermediate, bachelor's, master's, MPhil, and PhD degrees. Teaching Modes: Blended, face-to-face, open, and distance learning. Media-Based Instruction (Radio and TV broadcasts are used for educational programming) is a key strategy of education for all.</p>	https://www.aiou.edu.pk/
	Shanghai Open University (China)	<p>Type: Public Established: 1960 Number of Students: Over 84,000 (97.7% are professionals working). Courses Offered: Associate and bachelor's degree programs, non-degree training, and community education. Teaching Modes: Blended, face-to-face, open, and distance learning</p>	https://global.sou.edu.cn/

Arab States	<p>Arab Open University (Kuwait)</p>	<p>Type: Public-Private Partnership Established: 2002 Number of Students: Over 25000, across eight countries: Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Bahrain, Oman and Sudan. Courses Offered: Business Administration (Accounting, Marketing, Economics); Information Technology and Computing; English Language and Literature; Education (for teacher training); continuing education and short-term training programs Teaching Modes: Blended, distance learning, Face-to-face tutorials (conducted at regional centers to supplement online learning).</p>	<p>https://www.arabou.edu.sa/</p>
	Africa	<p>National Open University of Nigeria</p>	<p>Type: Public Established: 2002 Number of Students: Over 178000, across eight countries: Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Bahrain, Oman and Sudan. Courses Offered: Bachelor's, Master's, and PhD programs; Certificate and Diploma courses; Professional programs in various fields; MOOCs, ODL training, and entrepreneurial courses; Specialized training through the Africa Centre of Excellence on Technology Enhanced Learning (ACETEL) Teaching Modes: E-learning through Moodle LMS, Web-based resources, teleconferencing, video lessons, and MOOCs; Braille and digital materials for inclusivity; Online facilitation and virtual sessions</p>
		<p>Open University of South Africa</p>	<p>Type: Public Number of Students: Over 366,400 students (2022). Established: in 1873. Courses Offered: Undergraduate and postgraduate degrees (Bachelor, Master, and Doctoral). Diplomas, certificates, and short learning programs. Teaching Modes: Open and distance learning using online platforms, printed materials, digital content, and face-to-face tutorials</p>

Europe	Open University (United Kingdom)	<p>Type: Public</p> <p>Number of Students: Over 208,300 students (2021–2022 academic year).</p> <p>Established: in 1969.</p> <p>Courses Offered: Undergraduate and postgraduate degrees; Diplomas, certificates, standalone modules, and microcredentials;</p> <p>Teaching Modes: Supported open and distance learning with a mix of online resources, in-person tutorials, and independent study</p>	https://www.open.ac.uk/
	Hellenic Open University (Greece)	<p>Type: Public</p> <p>Number of Students: Approximately 44,000 active students.</p> <p>Established: in 1992.</p> <p>Courses Offered: Undergraduate and postgraduate degrees. Joint doctoral programs and certifications in training.</p> <p>Teaching Modes: Online and distance learning supported by asynchronous and synchronous teaching technologies</p>	https://www.eap.gr/en/
North America	Athabasca University (Canada)	<p>Type: Public</p> <p>Number of Students: Over 43,000 students from 87 countries.</p> <p>Established: in 1970.</p> <p>Courses Offered: Over 980 courses in 55 programs, including Bachelor's, Master's, Doctoral degrees, and professional development.</p> <p>Teaching Modes: Individualized self-paced study; Online learning, classroom-based group learning, and practicum experiences.</p>	https://www.athabascau.ca/
South America	Open University of Brazil (Brazil)	<p>Type: Public-Private Partnership</p> <p>Established: 2005</p> <p>Number of Students: 126,000 students</p> <p>Courses: Associate and bachelor's degree programs, non-degree training, and community education.</p>	https://uab.capes.gov.br/

Findings

Asia and the Pacific: Allama Iqbal Open University

Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU), based in Islamabad, Pakistan, exemplifies a robust approach to open and distance learning (ODL), blending technological innovation, inclusivity, and social impact. AIOU stands as a vital educational institution in Pakistan, bridging the gap between accessibility and quality in education. With over 1 million students enrolled, its focus on digital transformation, gender equity, and rural inclusion demonstrates its pivotal role in advancing education for all. By leveraging technology and embracing innovation, AIOU continues to set benchmarks in open and distance learning, contributing significantly to Pakistan's educational landscape.

As for the social impact, AIOU focuses on providing education to marginalized communities, with a significant proportion of its students coming from rural and underserved regions (58%). It prioritizes literacy and basic education for the rural population, earning awards like the UNESCO NOMA Prize and the Raja Roy Singh Award for its contributions to community upliftment. About the quality assurance and recognition, the establishment of a Directorate of Quality Enhancement (DQE) ensures high-quality education and services through compliance with national and international quality standards. It develops self-assessment reports, verifies research for PhD awards, and collaborates with QA agencies like the Asia-Pacific Quality Assurance Network (APQN) to maintain academic excellence. Indeed, AIOU's innovative strategies and commitment to inclusiveness and quality have garnered it national and international recognition, reinforcing its status as a leader in ODL. The learning materials and resources support multi-modal education, with the adoption of Self-learning packages, Radio broadcasts, Satellite TV transmissions, Online tutorials and group training workshops.

The technological dotation allows the institution to address the above-mentioned strategies. The AIOU employs a Campus Management System (CMS) for seamless online administration, including admissions, complaints management, library services, and tutor payments. It also operates a Learning Management System (LMS) to facilitate digital instruction, distribute instructional materials, and support online assignment submission. The Directorate of Information and Communication Technology (DICT) enhances the academic environment by managing the university's network, high-speed global connectivity, a Tier III data centre, and in-house software development. DICT ensures secure IT operations and runs a decision support system, contributing to better academic and administrative efficiency. However, the open data portal does not provide direct information on strategies to embrace open data for education. The specific policies on open data sharing and data privacy for the university are not prominently accessible online.

Despite these advanced technologies, survey studies (Noreen & Malik, 2019) have highlighted that portable devices with Wi-Fi and guidance to its use, as well as annual need-assessment systems could improve diverse online learning resources, access, cost and the lack of expertise in dealing with digital learning systems. The university has published about the digital learning strategies (see for example Afzal et al., 2024), but open data and data management are not an explicit approach in connection with education, despite the relevant attention to handle data “in house” through the Data Centre Tier III. The University page does not provide further information about data management as a clear strategy, connecting open data with educational improvement. Learning analytics and data management appear though at a developmental level, with key scholarly work connected to it. For example a recent thesis

dissertation by Hanaan Sadeed Ahmad & Supervised by Moiz-ud-Din Ahmed, (2022) was developed by asking access to the ICT department of the AIOU (p.47-48). This work proposed a machine learning-based model to predict the final exam results of Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) bachelor's students using data from demographics, assignments, midterm marks, and LMS logs. By analysing academic records of over 7,000 students from 2020, the model achieved 75–85% accuracy, demonstrating its potential to identify at-risk students early and inform timely interventions. This work contribute contributes as research to learning analytics in higher education, enabling data-driven decision-making and improving student outcomes, but does not necessarily encompass mainstreamed practise.

Asia and the Pacific: Shangai Open university

Shanghai Open University (SOU) exemplifies a forward-thinking approach to education through its integration of technological innovation, a commitment to inclusivity, and a strong emphasis on lifelong learning. SOU operates over 40 branch schools and numerous community education centers. These institutions emphasize equitable access to education for disadvantaged groups, including prisoners, the elderly, and people with disabilities. In line with this mission, SOU has established specialized institutions like the College for the Disabled and the College for the Elderly, which cater specifically to these demographics. The university actively promotes lifelong learning as part of its mission to transform Shanghai into a learning city. This initiative underscores the importance of continuous education in fostering personal and professional growth. On a global scale, SOU publishes the Global Lifelong Learning journal, which advances research in open and distance learning (ODL) and educational technology. This contribution highlights its leadership in the global educational landscape. SOU upholds rigorous standards through its Teaching Supervision and Quality Assurance Committee and the Quality Monitoring and Evaluation Centre. These bodies oversee the continuous improvement of educational services by conducting graduate and employer satisfaction surveys and implementing feedback-driven enhancements. SOU's innovative efforts have earned it prestigious accolades, including the UNESCO King Hamad Bin Isa Al-Khalifa Prize for the Use of ICT in Education, reflecting its excellence in leveraging technology to enhance learning.

As for the technological asset, SOU has developed a 5G+ holographic learning environment that integrates advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT). This cutting-edge system enhances the learning experience by offering immersive and interactive educational opportunities. Additionally, the university employs a cross-platform Learning Management System (LMS) powered by blockchain. This system collects and analyzes learning behavior, enabling the delivery of tailored support to students, thereby personalizing the learning experience. The university utilizes sophisticated analytics to generate learning profiles, which help in predicting potential challenges that students might face. These insights are used to improve educational outcomes, ensuring that learners receive targeted support to succeed in their studies. SOU hosts a variety of platforms, such as the Shanghai Lifelong Learning Network, which provides access to online courses, digital learning materials, and various educational activities. These resources make learning more accessible and flexible for diverse audiences.

Despite these relevant innovations, the available information from Shanghai Open University's (SOU) official website, there is no explicit mention of open data policies, open data for education, learning analytics strategies, or data-driven governance. The website provides an overview of the university's

programs, history, and recent news but does not detail specific policies or strategies related to data management or analytics. For comprehensive insights into SOU's approaches to these areas, it would be advisable to consult official university publications or contact the university directly. The news' page reports several focuses of interest, like global citizenship education and lifelong learning, as well as the contribution of open universities to global education. The search for specific scholarly work about the SOU yielded items demonstrating an evolving interest in the matter of learning analytics (Hoel & Xiao, 2018). The research introduces the Open Learning Analytics Architecture (OLAA) tailored to the needs of open and distance education, developed by the SOU. This initiative utilizes big data from learning platforms and student interactions to enhance educational outcomes. Key strategies and components include an Open Architecture Design, in which SOU has implemented a modular and interoperable system architecture using the ISO/IEC 20748 learning analytics process model. This architecture supports open standards for data collection, analysis, and feedback loops. Core components include synthetic data generation for privacy protection, open learner models, and predictive engines for tailored interventions. This architecture allows forms of personalisation and feedback. Indeed, the architecture integrates persona modelling and personalized recommendations, enabling adaptive guidance for students based on their unique learning behaviours and needs. A homework warning system, an initial application of this architecture, alerts students through web, text, and chat platforms to ensure timely task completion. The whole system supports the principles of openness, aiming at opening data, algorithms and generating open data visualisations to foster transparency and collaboration. As found in our prior analysis of the literature, synthetic data is used to mitigate privacy risks while enabling robust analytics, including prediction and intervention.

The *dataviz* tools should lead to custom dashboards provide insights for learners, curriculum designers, and educators, ensuring actionable outcomes from the analytics. Also, an iterative design cycle should integrate feedback from international experts and stakeholders, to refine the architecture continuously. The above presented architecture is not an institutional strategy but a research outcome. Therefore, it could be considered a working document that supports potential institutional developments. Indeed, this architecture aligns with global standards for open education and learning analytics, supporting innovation in educational technology. SOU's commitment to leveraging open systems, privacy-conscious practices, and stakeholder engagement sets a benchmark for learning analytics in open and distance education. Probably, networked collaboration with other open universities might support landing and spreading the system development as an actors' practice.

Arab Open University (Kuwait)

The Arab Open University (AOU), headquartered in Kuwait, is a prominent open and distance learning institution operating across the Arab region. AOU emphasizes equal opportunity and respect for diversity through its Equal Opportunity and Respect for Diversity Policy. This includes eliminating discrimination based on race, gender, age, or socioeconomic class. In this regard, the male-to-female student ratio is balanced, and female enrolment often exceeds male enrolment in specific programs. With regards to community engagement, the university is deeply involved in community outreach, collaborating with NGOs and charities. For example: AOU Lebanon works with organizations like the Lebanese Red Cross and T.E.R.R.E Liban on initiatives such as blood donations, health training for refugees, and environmental protection. AOU also Offers education to disadvantaged groups, including Syrian refugees in Lebanon, through tuition discounts and tailored programs. Considering Quality assurance and recognition, the institution under analysis has achieved standards for governance like the Quality assurance is governed

by the Quality Assurance and Accreditation Department (QAAD); the Quality Assurance and Academic; and Institutional Standards Committee at both HQ and branch levels. Also, it operates under a dual awards arrangement with the Open University UK and adheres to the UK Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education's Quality Code. Academic validation is also possible since the university collaborates with the Open University UK, ensuring academic standards meet international benchmarks. As for the resources for learning, with dedicated services such as workshops to train students and tutors on Learning Management Systems (LMS), and bilingual support through English Orientation Programmes and placement tests, AOU effectively addresses the diverse educational needs of Arab societies. Its commitment to innovation and accessibility not only enhances learning experiences but also aligns with sustainable development goals, reinforcing its leadership in the higher education landscape. The Arab Open University is a significant player in open and distance education across the Arab world. Its regional network of branches, focus on equity and inclusion, and integration of technology-enhanced learning position it as a leader in higher education, addressing the diverse needs of Arab societies while contributing to sustainable development goals.

Coming to the technological Innovations, it is worth considering the technology integration for the Learning Platforms adopted. The AOU employs a Student Information System (SIS) integrated with a Moodle-based Learning Management System (LMS). This system supports a wide range of academic and administrative tasks, such as: Recruitment and registration; financial transactions; academic advising; Displaying course content, online assessments, interactive teaching, and videoconferencing.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the LMS incorporated online tutor-student interaction, session recordings, and presentation features to ensure seamless teaching and learning.

Within this digital architecture, we explored open data practices. We observed that the informational about centralized open data portal for the AOU was not readily available. Nonetheless, the university has a Privacy and Usage Policy that outlines data collection, usage, and security measures to protect user privacy. In fact, further exploration of the website policies ¹ display an institutional policy to protect user privacy and ensure the secure handling of personal information. Their Privacy and Usage Policy outline the following key points, connected to Data collection and usage, Security Measure, User Rights, Usage Policy. For the first dimension of data policy, the document highlights relevant practises dealing with the information collected and the purpose of such a collection. Indeed, when users visit the AOU website, certain data is automatically collected, including the time and date of the visit, pages viewed, anonymized IP addresses, and browser information. This information is used to enhance user experience, improve website functionality, and address any errors promptly.

As for the security, the document considers payment transactions, explaining how secure services adhere to respective terms and policies in the Arab countries associated to the AOU. The Data protection is fundamentally supported by security procedures to prevent unauthorized access, loss, or destruction of personal information. Data is stored on secure servers (owned by the institution or as cloud paid by the AOU) with firewall protection, and users are advised to safeguard their passwords and avoid sharing sensitive information through unsecured channels.

User Rights are also present. Users concerned about their data can change their system passwords automatically and may request assistance from technical support if needed. They are also entitled to

¹ <https://www.arabou.edu.sa/about/Documents/Privacy%20and%20Usage%20Policy.pdf>

request corrections to any inaccuracies in their personal data, provided official documents are submitted for verification. Finally for the purposes of data usage policy, the document deals with acceptance of terms while accessing and using the AOU website and electronic services. Users hence agree to comply with the stated terms and conditions. The university reserves the right to modify these terms at any time without prior notice, and continued use of the site constitutes acceptance of any changes.

Scholarly research contributes to the development of learning analytics to inform academic decision making about actions and learning objectives. The chapter titled "A Framework for Harnessing Analytics to Augment the Academic Action Plan" (Hussein & Karam, 2021) presents a structured approach to integrating data analytics into the development of Academic Action Plans (AAPs) in higher education institutions. The key components of the framework are quite evident: a) People, which emphasizes the importance of stakeholders, including academic leaders, faculty, and students, in the data-driven decision-making process; b) Process, that outlines systematic procedures for collecting, analysing, and applying data to inform academic strategies and actions; c) Data, which focuses on the utilization of academic and learning analytics to enhance student experience, progression, retention, and overall success; d) Technology, that highlights the role of advanced analytical tools and platforms in processing large datasets to derive actionable insights. The objectives pursued by the framework application would be: Improving student experience and success as well as enhancing student progression and retention; increasing graduation rates and reducing the time to graduate; optimizing administrative workloads for faculty members; reducing educational costs through efficient resource utilization and finally, establishing a culture of data-informed decision-making.

Finally, the university aligns with Open Access policies globally, offering a Digital library with Open Access texts². Open Research Data are not openly announced in any of the areas of the digital library, nor open data or open knowledge approach are part of the main web portal.

National Open University of Nigeria

The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) is a leading open and distance learning (ODL) institution dedicated to expanding access to quality education across Nigeria. It can be considered a cornerstone of educational equity and innovation in Nigeria. Its commitment to leveraging technology, inclusivity, and lifelong learning ensures it meets the diverse needs of its growing student population. NOUN's focus on cutting-edge research, community engagement, and quality assurance positions it as a vital player in advancing higher education in Nigeria and across Africa. Considering the focus of inclusion, the NOUN plays a crucial role in democratizing higher education in Nigeria, offering flexible learning options to over 178,000 students from various demographics, including rural populations, incarcerated individuals, and persons with disabilities. To provide support to the mentioned divers populations, the university has embraced ICT-driven learning solutions, including e-library services and online portals for seamless administrative support and academic access. Also, NOUN provides materials in both Braille and digital formats to cater to visually impaired students; delivers specialized programs for prisoners, enabling them to pursue higher education while incarcerated, which serves as a model for equity and rehabilitation; and cater to a significant number of female learners, helping bridge gender gaps in education.

² <http://library.aiou.edu.pk/>

Another relevant focus is community engagement, for which NOUN commits by providing education to underserved communities through its vast network of 114 study centres across Nigeria. Their eLearning offer, based on a variety of delivery methods includes printed materials, self-paced digital content, web-based learning platforms, video-tutorials and teleconferencing. The university also provides MOOCs, entrepreneurial courses, and capacity-building programs in addition to its degree and diploma offerings.

However, not only does NOUN commit to social inclusion, but also positions as a leader in technological research, fostering innovation in fields critical to Nigeria's development, from technology applied to food, energy, mining to health care and social development. The NOUN's Africa Centre of Excellence (ACETEL) positions it as a leader in the African context, networking with several other universities across the globe.

As for the quality governance, NOUN operates under the supervision of Nigeria's National Universities Commission (NUC) and adheres to its quality assurance frameworks. It regularly reviews its academic programs and incorporates feedback from stakeholders to maintain and improve standards.

The above introduced institutional structure and strategies in teaching and research are supported by a robust technological infrastructure. NOUN uses Moodle-based Learning Management System (LMS) to provide access to course materials, facilitate online tutorials, and host interactive learning sessions. The platform integrates multimedia elements, including teleconferencing, video lessons, and MOOCs, ensure diverse and inclusive learning experiences. Moreover, the Africa Centre of Excellence on Technology Enhanced Learning (ACETEL) offers specialized digital training and research in cutting-edge technologies like blockchain, cybersecurity, and artificial intelligence.

Upon these bases, the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) has developed a comprehensive framework for implementing learning analytics to enhance teaching, learning, and student support. A published open document addressing the institutional strategy on learning analytics is visible at the secondary menu, yet easily reachable, dated 2023³.

While the university emphasises open education through the publication of Open Educational Resources, through relevant cooperation with other well-known open universities (Agbu et al., 2016), open data practices are not evident. Nonetheless, some scholars do relevant networking through European and international groups, with key publications relating to Open Science as a practice (Stracke et al., 2020). More importantly, by engaging in such networks, the NOUN scholars are contributing to interinstitutional dialogue and development of strategies, through the collaboration with other African Open Universities such as UNISA to implement a learning analytics system⁴.

Key aspects of this framework include guiding principles, value proposition and implementation drivers. This framework is designed to harness learning analytics effectively, focusing on ethical standards to protect student privacy, ensuring transparency in data collection, and recognising the complexity of student learning beyond data points. It emphasizes personalization by tailoring pedagogy, assessment, and support based on data insights, while remaining research-driven through empirical evidence. The value proposition includes utilizing analytics for data-driven decision-making, upgrading digital infrastructure for seamless data integration, and providing professional development to staff for effective

³ http://nou.edu.ng/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Draft-learning-analytics_-National-Open-University-of-Nigeria.pdf

⁴ <https://www.unisa.ac.za/sites/corporate/default/Colleges/Economic-and-Management-Sciences/News-&-events/Articles/Unisa%27s-ODL-expert-garners-global-recognition>

use of analytics tools. By aligning with national educational standards and engaging stakeholders such as students, faculty, and administrators, the framework ensures policy coherence and builds capacity for analytics deployment. Ultimately, it aims to enhance teaching quality, refine services, and improve educational outcomes through a systematic and integrated approach. This strategic approach positions NOUN to effectively harness learning analytics, aiming to improve student retention, success, and the overall quality of its educational offerings.

University of South Africa

The University of South Africa (UNISA) is the largest university in South Africa and one of the world's mega-universities, offering open and distance learning (ODL) to a diverse student body. UNISA's emphasis on inclusivity, cutting-edge technology, and high-quality education makes it a cornerstone of South Africa's higher education landscape. Its commitment to expanding access and lifelong learning aligns with global education goals and positions it as a leader in open and distance learning.

The University of South Africa (UNISA) plays a pivotal role in advancing social impact, equity, and academic quality through its comprehensive educational strategies. By aligning its activities with South Africa's National Development Plan and the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, UNISA actively supports marginalized communities and promotes lifelong learning (LLL). Its commitment to equity is reflected in financial aid and government-funded programs benefiting over 130,000 unemployed students from historically disadvantaged backgrounds. Learning materials, meticulously developed by in-house academic staff in collaboration with the Directorate of Curriculum and Instructional Design, include self-learning packages, supplementary guides, and innovative instructional media to enhance accessibility and learning outcomes. UNISA maintains high academic standards through quality assurance frameworks overseen by the Higher Education Quality Council, with peer reviews and evaluations ensuring relevance and excellence. The university's robust collaborations with organizations such as UNESCO, the Commonwealth of Learning (COL), and African universities further strengthen its academic impact, exemplified by initiatives like the UNESCO Chair on Open Distance Learning. Through these multifaceted efforts, UNISA focuses on fostering educational excellence through the ethics of sustainability and inclusion.

UNISA leverages technological innovations to enhance accessibility and inclusiveness in education, offering robust digital learning support through its virtual learning environment (VLE) on the myUnisa platform. This platform facilitates access to tutorials, peer-group interactions, video conferencing, and satellite broadcasts, while also addressing connectivity challenges by providing offline access to digital materials via memory sticks embedded in wristbands. To support students with disabilities, UNISA ensures that learning materials are available in Braille, large print, and audio formats, alongside electronic formats like DAISY (Digital Accessible Information System), promoting an inclusive and accessible educational experience for all learners. The digital infrastructure allows UNISA to incorporate advanced technological methods like IoT, AI, big data, and cloud computing to support advanced projects including educational research.

It is worth noting that UNISA has renewed scholars contributing to the field of open education (Czerniewicz & Cronin, 2023) and the ethics of learning analytics (Prinsloo, 2019a, 2020, 2022). This key contribution is reflected in the university's policies and procedures, through the digital library offering

open educational resources and open data ⁵ news about students' data ⁶. Through this research work, the scholars are prominently leading the agenda-setting for a Global South Data ethics, in which not only learning analytics are developed, but they also adhere to local values and ethical concerns that are just and relevant to African communities. In fact, navigating UNISA portal easily leads to an Institutional Repository (UnisaIR) that is fed with an open archive of scholarly outputs, including theses, dissertations, research articles, and conference papers. This environment is connected to Open Access and Open Data policies, including Data Sharing Policies. In this regard, UNISA counts over a Research Data Management Policy ensuring that research data is stored, preserved, retained, and made accessible for use and reuse, aligning with legal, ethical, and funding requirements. Also, there is a Policy on Research Involving UNISA Employees, Students, and Data, which governs the conduct of research involving UNISA's community and data, emphasizing ethical standards and data protection

Open University (United Kingdom)

The Open University (OU), based in Milton Keynes, UK, is one of the world's largest providers of open and distance learning. The Open University remains a global leader in education innovation, accessibility, and lifelong technological advancements, diverse offerings, and commitment to social impact align with its mission of inclusivity and educational excellence. The university's program strives to eliminate discrimination and promote opportunities for all, with a historic background aimed at lifelong learning and social inclusion. In 2022, 37078 students declared a disability, making it one of the largest providers for disabled learners. OU is a relevant provider of Lifelong Learning across the globe, pioneering in the field of MOOCs with FutureLearn, and in Open Education, with OpenLearning. Historically, the OU has partnered with the BBC offering quality public resources through several channels, including mass media, supporting social inclusion. These informal learning initiatives attract millions of participants globally. The courses offered are supported by a wealth of open educational resources, like audio materials, software, and digital content accessible through OpenLearn and FutureLearn. Printed books are mostly produced "in house" hence ensuring educational participation.

Quality assurance follows UK standards, ensuring OU degrees hold the same status as those from traditional universities. Also, Eighteen Boards of Studies manage curriculum development, overseen by a Pro-Vice-Chancellor (PVC) for academic quality. The university is also strong in terms of research, particularly in the field of distance and open learning. OU has partnerships with global organizations like UNESCO, Commonwealth universities, and NGOs. Some projects include continuative activity through centres like the Institute of Coding to address digital skills gaps. Also, international degrees and recognitions, like the TESS-India project, enhancing teacher training in India.

As for the technological facilities, the university uses a Moodle-based VLE supplemented with custom plugins to deliver integrated and flexible online learning experiences. Key features include a Student Home Page that centralizes access to resources, assignments, and support services; and Tools for submitting assignments, managing courses, and accessing help and guidance.

⁵ <https://www.unisa.ac.za/sites/corporate/default/Library>

⁶ <https://www.unisa.ac.za/sites/corporate/default/Colleges/Agriculture-&-Environmental-Sciences/News-&-events/Articles/Study-delivers-treasure-trove-of-data-on-international-students-in-Africa>

The OU publishes Open Data, having an owned institutional research data repository that provides access to research data through Open Research Data Online (ORDO). The data sharing policies in place emphasise data management, data ethics and data protection. As for the first policy, it outlines the university's commitment to managing research data according to the UKRI Common Principles on Data Policy and the FAIR Data Principles, promoting open sharing of data where possible. Relating to the data ethics, this policy describes the university's approach to ensuring that data is used ethically, particularly in large-scale data processing intended to inform university actions. Finally, considering data protection, the policy in place underscores the university's commitment to protecting the rights and privacy of individuals, ensuring compliance with data protection laws.

In 2022, the Titan data platform was launched to analyse student engagement and improve learning experiences. In fact, the OU has been pioneering the field of open education data usage, not only through technological developments, but also through relevant international projects discussing the value and the problematic issues emerging while using learning analytics (see for example (Buckingham Shum & Luckin, 2019; Ferguson, 2019; Rienties & Jones, 2019. among others). The scholarly literature connected to case studies of LA development and impact on teaching and learning (Herodotou et al., 2019a; Rienties et al., 2016, 2018), and LA policies (Drachler & Greller, 2016; Tsai & Gašević, 2017a). Furthermore, methodological reflections about data infrastructures where an early matter in the OUUK. For example, adopting a case study methodology, (Kuzilek et al., 2017) found out that open data utilization in higher education supports both institutional transparency and the development of analytics-driven decision-making systems. They examined specific applications such as data repositories and analytics tools to improve student outcomes and institutional processes. The study highlighted the importance of creating linked open datasets that integrate diverse data sources for enhanced academic and administrative functions. Some have contributed further to the publication of open datasets, even creating interactive visualisations for further researchers' to enhance (Jordan, 2015; Russell, 2018).

Relating to educational open data and learning analytics, The Open University (OU) provides two notable resources for open data and learning analytics: the Open University Learning Analytics Dataset (OULAD)⁷ and the Open Knowledge Graphs (OKG)⁸. OULAD is an anonymized dataset encompassing student interactions with the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) across various courses. It includes demographic information, assessment results, and daily summaries of student clicks, facilitating research in learning analytics and student behavior. The dataset is available for download in CSV format and is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, promoting open research and collaboration. The OKG interlinks and exposes data from OU's institutional repositories, covering publications, qualifications, courses, audio/video materials, and associated personnel. It enables users to search via keywords, identifiers, or query through a SPARQL endpoint, supporting data reuse and integration. The data is provided in standard formats (RDF and SPARQL) and is generally available under an open license, facilitating transparency and interoperability.

These resources underscore OU's commitment to openness in education, providing valuable datasets and tools for researchers, educators, and developers to analyze educational processes, develop learning analytics applications, and enhance the overall learning experience. As a result, not only the OU publishes Open Data, but also actively contribute to their interoperability, with a growing reliance on

⁷ https://analyse.kmi.open.ac.uk/open_dataset

⁸ <https://data.open.ac.uk/>

linked open data (LOD) to standardize and interconnect data. Also, a decade of research in the field has led the OD to the implementation of predictive analytics tools to support student success, and increased collaboration across institutions to share data-driven insights and best practices.

Hellenic Open University (Greece)

The Hellenic Open University (HOU), located in Patras, Greece, is a public institution committed to open and distance learning. HOU's blend of technological innovation, commitment to lifelong learning, and focus on equity underscores its role as a significant educational institution in Greece. By aligning its practices with international standards and addressing the needs of diverse learner groups, HOU exemplifies the potential of open and distance education to promote inclusion and sustainability.

The Hellenic Open University (HOU) is committed to social impact through equity, inclusion, and lifelong learning. It provides educational opportunities to diverse groups, including refugees through the Provision of Refugee Education and Support Scheme (PRESS), as well as homeless individuals, drug addicts, prisoners, and people with chronic diseases. HOU develops specialized learning materials for students with disabilities, such as Braille, to ensure inclusivity. In 2021, it established the Centre for Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning to offer non-formal education programs and certifications, emphasizing the importance of lifelong learning. In terms of quality assurance and recognition, HOU operates under the guidelines of the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education, adheres to ISO standards, and regularly evaluates its programs using feedback from internal and external assessments. The university has received accolades such as the European Language Label and the E-xcellence Label by EADTU and is ranked fourth in the Webometrics Rankings for Open Universities. Additionally, HOU has created specialized units, including the Educational Content, Methodology and Technology Laboratory, to enhance teaching methodologies and uphold its high educational standards.

Advanced technological innovations to enhance its educational offerings are clearly in place. HOU operates a robust switched data network with a 1Gbps bandwidth, providing seamless support for both students and staff. This infrastructure includes physical and virtual servers used for storage, computing, and virtual desktops, ensuring reliability and efficiency. HOU's Learning Management System (LMS) is Moodle-based, supporting asynchronous tele-education and complemented by teleconferencing and live streaming tools. To address diverse learning needs, the university offers a combination of printed and digital materials.

Navigation to the HOU website does not yield specific information about an open data portal. Also, detailed policies on open data sharing and data privacy for HOU are not prominently accessible. A page announces the intellectual property right, from where the institution introduces some key aspects of grey data handling. Particularly, HOU collects personal data solely for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes, ensuring that data is processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently (Data Collection and Processing). The university ensures that collected data is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary. Efforts are made to keep data accurate and up to date (Data Minimization and Accuracy). Particularly, HOU retains personal data only for as long as necessary to fulfill the purposes for which it was collected, in accordance with legal and regulatory requirements (Storage Limitation). The university implements appropriate security measures to safeguard personal data against unauthorized access, alteration, disclosure, or destruction (Integrity and Confidentiality). Individuals have rights concerning

their personal data, including access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, data portability, and the right to object, and HOU provides mechanisms to facilitate the exercise of these rights (Data Subject Rights). Additionally, HOU has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) responsible for overseeing data protection strategies and ensuring compliance with GDPR requirements (Data Protection Officer).

Overall, this policy reflects HOU's dedication to maintaining the confidentiality and security of personal data, fostering trust among students, staff, and stakeholders.

Also, from the main page it is possible to discover the digital library⁹ where Open Access materials are announced. The library offers The Hellenic Open University (HOU) Library a range of resources and services that support open access, open science, and open data initiatives. HOU aligns with the Budapest Open Access Initiative, advocating for free availability of peer-reviewed research outputs on the internet. This enables users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts without financial, legal, or technical barriers. Open Access includes Open Data policies, which for the HOU are configured as access to various databases that include open data resources. For instance, the OECD iLibrary provides books, papers, and statistics from the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, serving as a gateway to OECD's analysis and data. The zbMath Open database is a comprehensive resource that includes abstracts and references across the spectrum of mathematical sciences, supporting open data in this field. Furthermore, HOU collaborates with the National Documentation Centre, a Greek public organization that promotes knowledge, research, innovation, and digital transformation. EKT supports open access to publications and data in the academic and research communities. While the library's website does not explicitly mention "open science," its commitment to open access and provision of open data resources align with the principles of open science, promoting transparency and accessibility in research.

Open data could be considered as a relevant element of Open Access in a perspective of Open Science for the HOU. The institution hence supports the broader open science movement and enhances academic experience for its community.

An investigation on scholarly work produced by HOU scholars demonstrates clear understanding and interest in learning analytics. Most cases are works related to the development of LA and emphasise the nature of case studies connected to actual applications, though at small scale. At the Hellenic Open University (HOU), studies have utilized a variety of data mining and analytic techniques, including text mining, sentiment analysis (Kagklis et al., 2016), and Markov Chain Models (Paxinou et al., 2024), to investigate student interactions and behaviors. These analyses reveal patterns in communication, sentiment trends, and transitions between learning states, offering actionable insights for tutors to refine course content and structure (Papadimitriou et al., 2019). For instance, social network analysis and opinion mining on student forum activity have highlighted how collaborative dynamics influence performance and motivation (Kagklis et al., 2016). Similarly, learning analytics applied to Moodle logs have mapped students' self-directed learning paths (Alachiotis et al., 2019), demonstrating correlations between specific actions and academic success.

The use of advanced data visualization tools, such as dashboards (Gkontzidis et al., 2017), supports real-time monitoring and feedback for educators and students. These tools provide a clear view of students'

⁹ <https://lib.eap.gr/?lang=en>

progress, enabling timely interventions and fostering self-reflection among learners. The findings emphasize the value of integrating learning analytics into decision-making processes to improve educational experience and outcomes.

HOU's commitment to open and distance learning has been instrumental in bridging gaps in accessibility to education, offering innovative learning environments and lifelong learning opportunities. This integration of learning analytics and adaptive technologies reflects a broader trend in educational reform, showcasing how data-driven strategies can enhance both teaching efficacy and student autonomy.

Athabasca University (Canada)

Athabasca University (AU), located in Alberta, Canada, is a global leader in open and distance learning, leveraging technology to provide flexible and accessible education. Below is a detailed analysis of its key aspects. Athabasca University exemplifies innovation in open and distance learning, providing inclusive, technology-driven education to a global audience. Its emphasis on lifelong learning, community engagement, and equity reinforces its mission to transform higher education and make it universally accessible.

Athabasca University (AU) demonstrates a strong commitment to equity, inclusion, and academic excellence through its open admissions policy, which ensures accessibility by admitting students aged 16+ who meet basic English proficiency requirements. The university provides tailored accessibility services for students with disabilities, including assistive technologies, alternative formats, and accommodations. AU fosters community engagement by supporting Indigenous students and knowledge through the Centre for World Indigenous Knowledge Nukskahtowin, which promotes traditional knowledge and academic inclusion. Additionally, AU emphasizes lifelong learning through initiatives like PowerED™, offering micro-credentials and digital learning strategies for professional development. The university adheres to stringent quality assurance standards, monitored by the Campus Alberta Quality Council and other national regulatory bodies. Globally, AU collaborates with Canadian and international academic institutions, professional associations, and Indigenous communities, actively participating in organizations such as UNESCO, the International Council for Open and Distance Education (ICDE), and the Commonwealth of Learning (COL), to further its mission of accessible and quality education.

Athabasca University (AU) leverages advanced technological resources to enhance learning experiences and accessibility. The university provides access to e-libraries, e-books, and virtual research platforms, including the IDEA Lab, developed in partnership with AWS (Amazon Web Services)¹⁰. AU employs D2L Brightspace as its cloud-based Learning Management System (LMS), replacing Moodle, where the PowerED initiative is embedded¹¹. The university page claims that this substitution has been made to offer personalised study paths and engaging course delivery. Additionally, within this private platform AI-powered tools and simulations are integrated into undergraduate learning, enabling real-world problem-solving experiences and fostering a dynamic educational environment.

¹⁰ <https://aws.amazon.com/solutions/case-studies/athabasca-university/>

¹¹ <https://www.d2l.com/newsroom/powered-by-athabasca-university-joins-d2l-wave-as-an-education-partner/>

However, learning analytics is not an evident topic within the main page. No policies or developments are available apart from the enunciation of the advanced data-driven tools. As usual, we sought scholarly literature on the topic, produced by scholars at the Athabasca University. Also in this case, relevant and well-known researchers in the international panorama have contributed to initial debates on learning analytics integrated to MOOCs and dashboards (Rahman & Dron, 2012). The university launched the famous conference series “Lak” (Learning Analytics and Knowledge) being the opening Lak’11 in Alberta, coordinated by the AU (Siemens & Gašević, 2012). This opening led to the formation of relevant scholarly investigation in the field, and the collaboration between the AU and the OUUK can be retraceable through joint scholarship. An interesting case is Prof. D. Gašević, currently professor of Learning Analytics at the Faculty of Information Technology at Monash University, but prior Professor in the School of Computing and Information Systems at the UA (2007-2017). He was an active scholar in the field of Learning Analytics and president of the Society for Learning Analytics Research (SoLAR), developing several relevant systems and supporting key scholarly research in the field (see for example Gašević et al., 2014; Yan et al., 2024, which display his anticipation of applied Learning Analytics). Despite this relevant research past, the AU does not display evident implemented policies and developed instruments for their students and teachers.

Open Data is not prominent in information within the university webpage, but it comes while searching through Library Services. Athabasca University provides access to research outputs through its Digital Thesis and Project Room, which houses theses and research projects. The Digital Library offers Scholarly Materials: The library's collection includes journal databases, e-books, print books, maps, and streaming audiovisual materials, all curated to align with AU's curriculum, but there is no evident access to a section on Open Data. The information collected highlights search tools (like the DISCOVER search tool to access a wide range of resources, including subscribed journal databases, open access journals, e-book collections, and media), support services like guides and tutorials, webinars and research assistance. The technical support provided by the library relates with “resolving security certificate warnings that may occur when accessing databases from the homepage”. Within this context, open data is searchable and refers to several open databases as resources for learning¹². The approach promotes open data literacy, being open data clearly explained and introduced with access to several Canadian Open Government Data and Open Research Data. Also platforms to publish Open Data are accessible, aligning with the idea of open data as open educational resources. Nevertheless, there is no information about educational open data.

However, while navigating the main university page, data ethics is a central point to the AU. The information provided is extensive and detailed, presenting an image of strong commitment to ethical research practices, privacy protection, and the secure handling of personal information. Institutional permissions are required for research involving AU's resources, personnel, or pre-collected data, with written consent mandated from AU's executive level. Ethical conduct is governed by AU's Research Ethics Board (REB), ensuring compliance with principles such as respect for persons and justice, while addressing participant recruitment, data access, and resource utilization. Privacy policies align with legislative standards, including Alberta's FOIP (Freedom of Information and Protection Privacy) Act, Canada's PIPEDA (10 fair information principles including Accountability, Identifying Purposes, Consent, Limiting Collection, Use, Disclosure, Retention, Accuracy, Safeguards, Openness, Individual Access,

¹² <https://libguides.athabascau.ca/c.php?g=729954&p=5239196&ss360SearchTerm=open%20data>

Challenging Compliance), and the EU/UK GDPR. Such instruments should ensure transparency, accuracy, and secure handling of personal information. Collected data, such as browsing behaviors, marketing preferences, and login credentials, are used to enhance communication, promote programs, conduct research, and improve user experiences. AU employs cookies and third-party analytics tools to optimize website functionality while offering users control over their preferences. Data is securely stored, often in Canada, with safeguards for international transfers when necessary. Student rights under the FOIP Act allow access, correction, and annotations to personal data, with formal processes for unresolved concerns. Disclosure of information is permissible only under specific conditions, such as student consent, legal obligations, or institutional needs, while sensitive documents like exams must be handled securely to prevent unauthorized access. AU's policies extend to remote activities and portable devices, maintaining rigorous standards for data protection and security in all operational modalities, ensuring compliance and fostering trust among students, staff, and stakeholders.

Also research projects and students' research through thesis writing have a website clearly addressing good practice on data ethics¹³ AU upholds stringent ethical standards for research involving human participants, ensuring compliance with federal regulations and institutional policies. Researchers intending to involve AU staff, students, or utilize university resources must secure specific institutional permissions in addition to obtaining ethics approval.

In a nutshell, AU's adherence to regulations on data integrity and respecting student privacy is connected to a business model based on subcontracts to third parties like AWS or D2L. Therefore, transparency is based on the way this collaboration should work to protect students and staff data. The data produced is not made available nor shared for the purpose of educational development.

South America: Open University of Brazil

The Open University of Brazil (UAB) aims to expand and decentralize higher education through distance learning, focusing on training educators and professionals in various fields. As of 2016, UAB operated over 600 support centers across Brazil, involving more than 100 public higher education institutions¹⁴. By 2024, the system counted more than 120k students across the country. UAB's relevance lies in its contribution to the democratization of education, providing access to higher education in remote and underserved regions, thereby enhancing educational opportunities nationwide.

The UAB publishes their open data on a portal¹⁵. The Universidade Aberta do Brasil (UAB) publishes its open data through a dedicated portal, showcasing a comprehensive and accessible strategy. CAPES (*Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior, National Coordination for Faculty Development*) regularly release datasets related to the UAB program, organized into specific time frames, such as 2013-2016, 2017-2020, 2021-2022, and 2023-2025, enabling longitudinal analysis and tracking of program evolution. The datasets are provided in multiple formats, including CSV, XLSX, PDF, and HTML, ensuring accessibility for various users and technical applications. These datasets contain detailed

¹³<https://www.athabasca.ca/research/ethics/ethics-policies-guidelines-and-permissions.html?ss360SearchTerm=students%20data%20privacy>

¹⁴ <https://www.gov.br/capes/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/sistema-uab-abrange-150-instituicoes-de-ensino-superior>

¹⁵ <https://dadosabertos.capes.gov.br/group/programa-universidade-aberta-do-brasil-uab>

information about public higher education institutions participating in the UAB program, the courses they offer, municipalities they serve, and student numbers categorized by academic trajectory, supporting data-driven decision-making and policy development. CAPES adheres to a structured publication schedule outlined in their Open Data Plan (PDA), ensuring stakeholders receive up-to-date information reflecting the program's dynamic nature. The thematic focus of the open data initiative includes distance public education, teacher training, and higher education courses, aligning with UAB's mission to expand educational opportunities across Brazil.

The apparent UAB's aim with open data is to support a strategy to promote transparency and accountability within the program. CAPES manifests its willingness to enable researchers, policymakers, and the public to analyse and understand the program's reach and effectiveness. This openness should foster trust and encourage collaborative efforts to further enhance the quality and accessibility of higher education in Brazil. The CAPES website requests the availability of such data to support evidence-based decision-making, allowing for the identification of trends, challenges, and opportunities within the UAB program. The claim is that open data should facilitate the monitoring of progress towards educational goals, particularly in expanding access to higher education in underserved regions.

In summary, the Open University of Brazil's open data strategy, as implemented by CAPES, exhibits a commitment to transparency, accessibility, and continuous improvement in higher education. The ultimate goal of such a strategy of publication and accessibility measures is to promote the idea of public knowledge for the democratization of education in Brazil. However, the complex system as a networked university might encompass data loss and inability to integrate data. The CAPES portal of the university does not introduce any visualization strategy for the users to interact with data and promote data-driven practices like a provision of academic or learning analytics.

As in other cases, the idea of using grey data is not developed as an institutional asset, but rather as a research interest that is cultivated by scholars regarding very specific focuses (learning analytics and dashboards development, grey data use for improving teaching). For example, Gonçalves & Nunes (2022), conducted a case study at the distance learning degree in Pedagogy, at a university located in the State of Ceará (Brazil) and participating of the UAB System, with regard to training in school management. The statistical method was adopted, by applying the multinomial logistic regression technique to action categories carried out in Moodle by 274 students in two disciplines in the school management area, distributed in seven centres. The results showed action categories that directly interfere in the student's performance, whether to approve, fail for grade or fail for missing classes, revealing the need for changes in the course design. Takaki et al (2022) developed a framework to evaluate machine learning-based predictive models of academic failure, to facilitate early pedagogical interventions. Focusing on a Brazilian undergraduate course in the distance learning modality as a case study, the authors run seven classification models on normalized datasets, which comprised grades for three weeks of classes for a total of six weeks. Also, the imbalanced-data context served as input to avoid the usage of a single metric to identify the best predictive model of student failure. Authors considered 11 metrics generated by the classifiers run and the application of exclusion and ordering criteria to produce a list of best predictors.

It is interesting to observe that the UAB also produces critical studies like the one carried out by Ferreira et al. (2020), who contended that the spread of data-driven educational technologies in Brazil and specifically at the UAB should not necessarily be considered a good practice. The authors carried out a discourse analysis on conceptual metaphors about data driven practices, considering in that ways in which these specific metaphors may be promoting perspectives that ignore difference and obscure

broader questions concerning education, thus contributing to the reproduction of previously existing problems and supporting new forms of colonisation.

Discussion

The wealth of cases hereby introduced demonstrate the relevant role of Open Universities in the pursue of education for all. Open and distance learning institutions play a crucial role in democratizing education worldwide, each employing tailored strategies to meet regional needs and technological advancements. However, the multi-case benchmarking reveals a diverse landscape institution that vary significantly in their approaches to open education data practices: for contributing to open data literacy and open science, for supporting evidence-based education and quality assurance, for leveraging data-driven technology to support teaching and learning. In this paragraph, we will introduce a synthesis of the findings, emphasizing institutional identities and their connections to open data, data ethics, learning analytics, open education, and open science.

In Asia, Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU), established in 1974, leads with over 1 million learners, utilizing media-based instruction via radio and TV to promote accessibility in rural areas. Similarly, Shanghai Open University (SOU), founded in 1960, serves 84,000 primarily working professionals through blended and distance learning, emphasizing skill development and continuing education. In the Arab States, the Arab Open University (AOU), established in 2002, operates across eight countries, serving over 25,000 students through a public-private partnership model that integrates blended learning strategies and fosters regional educational collaboration. Africa showcases the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), which, since 2002, has educated 178,000 students using advanced e-learning technologies like Moodle and teleconferencing, and the University of South Africa (UNISA), the oldest institution (established in 1873), which supports 366,400 students with printed and digital materials combined with online platforms. In Europe, the Open University (OU) in the United Kingdom, established in 1969, serves over 208,300 students with its flexible open learning model, while the Hellenic Open University (HOU) in Greece, founded in 1992, provides asynchronous and synchronous online learning for 44,000 students. North America's Athabasca University, established in 1970, enrolls 43,000 students from 87 countries, blending self-paced online learning with practicum experiences. In South America, the Open University of Brazil (UAB), established in 2005, has grown rapidly to serve 126,000 students through its public-private partnership model focused on workforce education. Institutions like AIOU and UNISA demonstrate scalability with massive enrolments, while newer entities like UAB and AOU achieve significant regional impacts. Blended and distance learning is a unifying approach, with technology integration ranging from media-based instruction to advanced LMS platforms, ensuring accessibility and innovation in education.

Initial observations across cases relate to the students' enrolments, the universities tradition and the type of learning provision. Institutions like AIOU and UNISA stand out with massive enrolments, indicative of their long-standing infrastructure and commitment to inclusivity. Comparatively, newer institutions like AOU and UAB have significant regional impacts but smaller student bases. Blended and distance learning is the common thread across all institutions, with varying degrees of technology integration, from media-based instruction (AIOU) to advanced LMS platforms (NOUN, AU). It is worth to consider the institution age vs. its scale: Older institutions like UNISA and AIOU demonstrate scalability, whereas relatively younger entities like UAB and AOU focus on specialized regional education initiatives. Though all the universities have a key goal to promote lifelong learning for all, Global North universities are focused on

research-based strategies to use data about and for learning (OU); or to promote a relevant user experience basing on advanced private services (UA).

Coming to the data initiatives, in order of case presentation, the Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) in Pakistan boasts robust technological infrastructure, including a Campus Management System (CMS) and Learning Management System (LMS). Nevertheless, open data and learning analytics remain underdeveloped. Most data initiatives are limited to internal administrative functions, and scholarly research in learning analytics is nascent. As for the Shanghai Open University (SOU), despite high technologies offered for learning to their students, explicit policies on open data and learning analytics are absent from institutional strategies. However, SOU's Open Learning Analytics Architecture (OLAA), developed through research, demonstrates potential for personalised learning and data-driven decision-making. In the Arab States (as mid Asian region) the Arab Open University (AOU), operating in eight countries integrates Moodle-based LMS and Student Information Systems (SIS). While the institution has privacy and data usage policies, no evidence of centralized open data initiatives is present. Research into learning analytics focuses on theoretical frameworks rather than institutional practices.

In Africa, the two cases considered, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) and the University of South Africa (UNISA), are leaders in democratizing higher education. The first university has implemented a comprehensive framework for learning analytics, emphasizing ethical standards and data-driven decision-making, in a research and institutional collaboration with the second university (UNISA). However, open data remains a policy to develop, with existing practices centred on internal data use for administrative and pedagogical purposes, though there are notable scholars committed to Open Science. The UNISA presents policies on open education and data ethics that are to be considered robust, supported by an institutional repository (UnisaIR) that aligns with open data principles within a standard of Open Education and Open Science. UNISA also leads global dialogues on learning analytics and data ethics, emphasizing the importance of African values in data-driven education.

As for the old continent, we should consider that other very relevant Open Universities operate in this geographical space. The selection demonstrates two excellent examples covering the most traditional case (OU), the first open university in Europe; and a successful case (HOU) interpreting South Europe. The first case (OU) in the United Kingdom has established itself as a global leader in open education, with a strong emphasis on lifelong learning and inclusivity. It publishes open data through its Open Research Data Online (ORDO) platform and has pioneered learning analytics with datasets like OULAD. The OU is a research-based model of integrating open data, data ethics, and learning analytics into institutional practices. The second case (HOU) in Greece focuses on inclusivity and lifelong learning through a Moodle-based LMS and robust data protection policies. While open access resources are available through its digital library, explicit open data policies and advanced learning analytics practices are less developed. Research in learning analytics at HOU is primarily exploratory, focusing on small-scale applications.

As for the Americas, Athabasca University (AU) in Canada represents classically the public-private collaboration that characterises North-America. AU emphasizes equity through advanced discourse about diversity. It offers technological innovation by partnering with technological corporations, with a focus on a quality user experience. Its research ethics and privacy policies are comprehensive, aligning with global data protection regulations. Also, aligning with international discourses about open

knowledge, it is the university with the clearest pathway to develop open data literacy for the students and researchers. However, it appears to lack evident institutional policies for the open data produced by the same university (grey data). Learning analytics are announced, but no open data leading to interactive dashboards are presented as an open service. Moreover, despite the history of contributions to learning analytics research, practical applications remain limited to isolated initiatives. In South America, the Brazilian case offers an interesting approach to opening higher education, through a networked institutional approach. The public information by the UAB exemplifies a strong commitment to transparency, offering an open data portal supported by a national structure (CAPES). The portal regularly publishes datasets supporting educational analysis but learning analytics and data visualization tools are not integrated into the mainstreaming of institutional practices. Research efforts focus on modelling students' data, but with applications at local UAB centres and not as an institutional policy.

We will now consider some cross-case elements, considering key topics focused during the analysis transversally.

Open Data sharing for open knowledge

Open data sharing is part of a culture of open knowledge, which also encompasses attention to open education and open science. Open education is a unifying focus for all institutions, with widespread use of open educational resources (OER). However, open science, including open data for educational research, is prominent only at institutions like the OU, UNISA, NOUN and the UAB. It is notable the relevant effort made in this sense by both African institutions, embedding solidarity and community as values for African educational development, including open data and open science. Other institutions, such as HOU and AU, align with open science principles through digital libraries and even commit with open data literacy. However, their discourses do not offer any visibility of HE open data to support educational research or development. The table 4 introduces the synthesis of findings.

Fostering Higher Education Open Data Practises

Open data practices vary widely among the institutions. We might consider that there are leaders in the conceptualisation of Higher Education Open Data usage, like the OU (UK) and UNISA (South Africa). Their approaches blend open science and open education commitment with a focus on research-based technological developments to develop learning analytics and, either way (particularly UNISA) make a sound critique of datafied systems' inconsistencies and ethical problems. The public documentation offered allows any reader to understand their approaches and to reach not only open data, but also open dashboards promoting educational research, data re-use, interaction with pedagogical data to understand relationships between quantified variables out of pedagogical practices (particularly the OU). Another institution pioneering in the field of Open Data is UAB, which demonstrates a strong commitment to transparency but lacks evident integration of data visualization tools to enhance usability and decision-making across the complex network of centres composing the open university model. NOUN can be also placed in this group, with public announced policies for learning analytics that are to be made visible as a service or documented practice. In this scenario, we might consider the institutions that demonstrate strong commitment to data protection, in compliance with regulatory frameworks, with an eye on the user experience. These are the cases of AU and AOU. Nevertheless, it is unclear how do they use the grey data by them produced in further analysis (evidence-based quality) or to support teaching and learning. The

last group is notably composed of AIOU and SOU, which do not display open data policies evidently, though they might have advanced approaches for data protection (like for example owning data servers). Also, they provide limited evidence of their research efforts in adopting data to support teaching and learning.

Open Data to support teaching and learning

This dimension relates to all forms of open data usage but particularly applies to the developments of fair Learning analytics, which remains an area of uneven development. The OU and UNISA have implemented learning analytics systems that inform teaching and learning practices while addressing ethical concerns, becoming best performers and supported by a wealth of research in the field. The difficult element to disentangle here is to which extent an institutional understanding and willingness to implement advanced approaches to learning analytics is hence embedded in research projects or, otherwise, research activity has traction over institutional development. The cases of NOUN, SOU, and HOU demonstrate growing interest in learning analytics, primarily through research initiatives rather than institutional policies. Networking with other open universities provides relevant opportunities for reflection and for potential institutional attention to research, hence becoming part of the institutional offer (see the case of NOUN). AIOU, AOU, and UAB display limited institutional engagement around learning analytics, with research focused on experimental applications rather than systematic adoption. However, UAB announces the relevance of producing this as a result, hence opening to a potential future pathway in the field. UA is the only university displaying a clear strategy of partnering with private institutions (big tech companies) to deliver learning analytics. However, the approach is announced as a private service and not publicly available.

Data Ethics

This dimension refers to an ethical approach to data overall, but that is particularly anchored in higher education open data, from collecting to transforming them into potential services for learners, teachers, staff, researchers, the community, and other institutions. All institutions emphasise data protection and privacy, with policies aligned with global regulations such as GDPR, FOIP, and PIPEDA. UNISA and AU lead in integrating data ethics into institutional policies, emphasizing transparency and ethical use of student data. However, less institutions extend these principles into open data or learning analytics frameworks.

Table 4 – Synthesis of findings

Benchmarking dimension	Universities								
	AIOU	SOU	AOU	UNISA	NOUN	HOU	OUUK	AU	UAB
Open Data Sharing for open knowledge				High	High		High	High	High
Fostering HE open data practices			Low	High	High		High	Low	High
Open data to enhance teaching and learning	Low	Low	Low	High	High		High	Low	Low
Data Ethics			Low	High	High		High	Low	

Note – A color has been used to indicate the type of evidence found in the main institutional page, secondary pages and/or research evidence. The current table **is not an evaluation of levels of development** but a representation of available information to the wider public.

The colors represent the following situations: White for a “not found” dimension; Light yellow for a “Research on the topic found”; gold yellow for a “Institutional policies in place found”; and blue-green for “Institutional policies and instrument in place found”.

Conclusion

From the analysis carried out, it appears that some institutions (AIOU, SOU, AOU) should transition from isolated research projects to institutional strategies to embed open data within a framework of open science, approaching the ideals of open knowledge. Within this context, open grey and research data from Higher Education might support further research and could be the base of institutional strategies for open data as evidence for quality improvement and/or learning analytics development. For other institutions (UAB), enhancing usability by incorporating data visualization tools and aligning datasets with institutional learning goals is not far away, but would require attention, institutional policies and funding.

In this regard, the institutions face ongoing international challenges relating to data ethics. While transparency is a desirable outcome led by the ideals of open knowledge for all, opening students’ data comes with clear conundrums relating to data ownership and privacy, let alone the problem of misrepresentation or discrimination through disclosure of trends and patterns. Also, the problem of commercial interests over data might be framing current data practises. There are cases in which private companies might have interests in keeping data as a restricted access asset (AU), whereas public universities leading public research are committed to the values of open science and generate frameworks to provide informed consent for students and teachers to become a sort of data donors for good (OU, UNISA). It is less clear that this is the approach across all the universities, with open data being in any case a “trending topic” in funded research programmes, particularly after the COVID pandemic (Bozkurt et al., 2020; European Commission - RISE - Research Innovation and Science Policy Experts, 2016). Institutions strive hence to develop data ethics frameworks, with some sticking to the relatively canonical formula of privacy protection and informed consent for use (something that could become a sort of dilemma along educational developments and practises). In any case, all institutions should keep on making efforts to develop both comprehensive policies aligned with international standards but might also find specific approaches to strike a balance between individual privacy rights on data and the relevance of data for transparency and open knowledge development.

In this effort, collaborative frameworks prove to be a strong driver for effective digital transformation. Networking among institutions (e.g., NOUN, UNISA or UA/UK) has fostered shared perspectives on learning analytics frameworks and open data practices tailored to regional and global contexts. Also, the UAB/CAPES collaboration to promote professional development about open data; as well as the UA focus on open data literacy are central to empower staff, faculty and students to approach open data and learning analytics wisely. In this regard, there is no data-driven service that can serve the educational needs without understanding, engagement in decision-making and critical usage.

It is also interesting to consider the lack of clear or consistent relationships between the discourse about openness and the effective presence of open knowledge/open science/open data models. Not all institutions embrace necessarily such strategies in an active way. Moreover, there is an evident gap

between open data as a research-based practise and the practise of re-using open educational data (like grey/administrative data, that could also fall into the category of open government data). Learning analytics hence remain in a foggy area where they might be part of the student's services or teachers' support but not necessarily based on open data. Both research-based or private companies' usage of data to produce learning analytics, can build over restricted access to datasets. While in some cases (like the AU) the privacy policies in place manifest clear data protection measures, in other cases, research-based approaches should be constrained by research ethics committees and overall informed consent measures. In both cases, there is risk of end users' disempowerment and lack of understanding or engagement with learning analytics that are built upon their same data.

The study provides valuable insights into the practices and strategies of Open Universities globally but is not without its limitations. An initial limitation is the underrepresentation in some regions. While the study includes examples from five major geographic regions, it relies heavily on one or two cases per region, which may not capture the full diversity of Open Universities within those regions. For example: Asia includes two universities (AIOU and SOU), Africa also includes two (NOUN and UNISA). However, Latin America is represented solely by the Open University of Brazil (UAB). Europe and North America feature only one case each (HOU and AU, respectively), potentially overlooking other significant institutions, like the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC) and the Open Universiteit Nederland (OUN), also well known for their research-based approaches and the international networks they are part of globally. A selection bias could also be a problem since the Open University of Brazil, which was not part of the original Benchmarking study, was selected to enrich the global perspective but may lead to inconsistencies in methodology for being a networked organisation and not a single university. The strategy to contrast this problem has been considering a multicase study, not a generalisable outcome. Further studies might complete the Benchmarking extending the sampling to all available Open Universities.

Furthermore, this study did not use any standardized metric. While institutional profiles are provided, there is variability in the depth of information reached and adopted for the study. For example, the documentation was easily available for some universities (e.g., UNISA, OU) which provided detailed information on open data and learning analytics strategies, while for other data (AIOU) or policies (SOU) were not equally available. The strategy in this case was complementing the public information with research-based materials. Automated translation of the several texts was provided by Deepl and Quillbot whenever the information was in the original language instead of being in English.

Finally, the study does not analyse socio-economic and political constraints influencing the development of higher education open data, such as the political interest on open science and open data, the relevant organisational and technological ecosystems supporting open data sharing for research or commercial/development purposes. The universities have been characterised by their pedagogical identity, and their technological dimension has been considered in support of further delving on open data practises. Further case studies might compare less cases, with an in-depth analysis of cultural and political or even historical identities. As a strategy, in any case, the study has built over the wealth of findings in prior reporting exercises by the IITE-UNESCO.

The study, in any case, provides a nuanced understanding of the global landscape of Open Universities throughout the specific lenses of open data practices.

Recommendations

Policy Recommendations

The IITE report on Benchmarking highlights that HEIs are already involved in open data initiatives such as open research data and open learning resources HEIs, including OUs, should engage in opening data activities and 'big data' strategy development for the purpose of performance improvement and strategic planning. Benchmarking is often complicated by data reliability and compatibility issues, because of the differences due to varying data collection methods and data sources, which are accessible only to the organizations that conduct benchmarking. The use of comparative data and information is important for benchmarking and vice versa comparative information obtained from benchmarking often provides an impetus for 'breakthrough' improvement or transformational change. This study highlights the state of art and trends of open data usage. Such work addressed a multi-case study through benchmarking methods, identifying four main areas: a) Open Data Sharing for open knowledge; b) Fostering HE open data practises; c) Open data to enhance teaching and learning; d) Approaches to Data Ethics.

In the following, we will offer several recommendations concerning methodological approaches to self-analyse the existence of open data practises and to cultivate a culture of open data.

Open data sharing for open knowledge

It is relevant to take into consideration the wealth of research and policymaking in the area of Open Data, with existing national frameworks to contribute to Open Science as explained at the beginning of this report. Therefore, this is a first level of engagement with open data in Higher Education Institutions. It is relatively straightforward given the existence of instruments and digital infrastructures provided at international level (like open research data repositories that provide solid public infrastructures to publish and share open data). We could observe that some governments are strongly committing to this type of infrastructure, resourcing materials and technical staff to support strategies (see the case of UAB or UNISA). However, throughout the lenses of the multi-case benchmarking conducted here, we also observe that there are several levels of engagement with such recommendations. Research on open data practises as well as data literacy applied to open data might provide lenses to detect emerging activities and to provide appropriate professional development opportunities, as well as curriculum design to deal with open data as part of transparency and open knowledge. In this regard, each university can generate groups or internally funded proposals to contribute to this stage of development. The library institutional systems are already equipped with knowledge on international standards, they have been active in the Open Access movement and can provide excellent support to develop researchers, staff and students' data literacy (case of UA).

In any case, whenever a university desires to proceed with an internal benchmarking with self-diagnosis value, to explore specific Open Data initiatives (connected with research or open education activism) might effectively map the frontiers of institutional development, with a focus on:

- Integration of Open Data as a current practise of research and Open Science,
- Integration of Open Data as open educational resources,
- Integration of Open Data to develop Open Education Science and evidence-based quality standards, and institutional transparency.
- Open Data to support technology-mediated services and research on learning analytics,
- Practical examples of Open Data-enabled innovations, such as linked data platforms, dashboards for student learning analytics, or shared research repositories,
- Challenges such as legal, ethical, and technological barriers, along with strategies adopted to overcome them.

Fostering higher education open data practices

Open Universities (OUs) play a pivotal role in advancing open data practices by leveraging existing research and policy frameworks to align with national and international standards, and their unique possibility to collect data from online learning activities. The international debate on open science and open data for public administration supports the idea that open data integration into institutional strategies not only enhances transparency but also supports institutional planning and evidence-based decision-making. Having said so, for several motivations, students' data entails several challenges and might also be the focus of commercial interests. Should HEIs open data that will be further monetised by a powerful corporation rather than other HEIs or SMEs? The literature reviewed in this report highlights several dilemmas relating the goodness embedded open data in any possible case. However, to foster robust open data practices, HEIs should focus on searching for progressive exploration of strategies and approaches for the appropriate embedding open data into their operational and academic frameworks. This entails ensuring that research outcomes and institutional data are openly available and interoperable whenever relevant institutional actors like students and teachers decide (not as an isolated individual decision on privacy) that there is good in the data shared, not *per se* but for the relationship between open data they contributed to and the ultimate educational benefits that can be achieved. This involves:

- Developing institutional policies that align with open science and open knowledge principles to explore open data sharing across all academic and administrative functions.
- Investing in digital infrastructures, such as open research data repositories and linked data platforms, to search for secure standards in data sharing and to ensure accessibility.
- Promoting interdepartmental collaboration to break down silos and create cross-functional teams that can integrate open data into teaching, research, and administrative processes.
- Building partnerships with government bodies, non-governmental organisations, and other universities to develop shared open data initiatives and frameworks.
- Enhancing institutional capacity by offering professional development for staff, faculty, and students to build competencies in data literacy and open data management. Internal benchmarking and self-assessment can guide institutions in identifying areas of growth, enabling

them to systematically integrate open data into their organizational ecosystem and contribute to broader open science and open education movements.

Open data to enhance teaching and learning

It is said that open data holds transformative potential for teaching and learning by enabling the development of advanced tools and strategies, such as learning analytics and adaptive learning platforms. We observed throughout our multi-case benchmarking that this is not a frequent achievement. In fact, the literature on critical technologies studies analysed in this report purports that the forms into which this message is interpreted lead to problematic practices like commercial dashboards that are of little value for local actors, despite glossy promises. Strong research approaches liaising open data with learning analytics like the one carried out by the OUUK also problematise the adoption of these same developments. They carry out critical exercises, like longitudinal analysis on the actual value of dashboards, or the pedagogical concepts embedded in the data collected. Therefore, beyond saying that HEIs can use open data to support personalised education, improve student retention, and foster active engagement with learning processes, the institutions must create interdisciplinary units or centres advancing discussions that connect the dots relating to digital and data infrastructures, pedagogical concepts, educational goals, and the conceptual artefact that dashboards or learning analytics articulate. To realize this strategy, institutions should:

- Establish institutional frameworks for the collection, analysis, and sharing of educational data to support the development of fair and transparent learning analytics systems.
- Use open data to create dynamic dashboards that provide actionable insights for students, educators, and administrators, allowing for real-time interventions and curriculum adjustments.
- Integrate open data into pedagogy by designing assignments and projects that encourage students to analyse and interpret datasets, fostering critical data literacy (when and why data is trash? Why do we need other sources of information to interpret data?)
- Collaborate with research units within the institution or as providers of the institution, with open models of innovation compliant with companies' social responsibility, rather than huge business models embedded in monopolistic digital platforms, to develop scalable tools that utilise open data for the educational goals the institutions are willing to pursue.
- Leverage open data to explore teachers' reflection and strategies within their classrooms, through democratic and participatory approaches, liaising with institutional development, feeding back into continuous transformational cycles. As part of this process, HEIs must navigate ethical and privacy concerns by ensuring that data usage aligns with legal and ethical standards while prioritising informed consent and transparency in all data-driven initiatives. If these last elements are not in place, it is probably better avoiding data collection.

Approaches to data ethics

Ethical approaches to data (before they become open) are essential for ensuring trust and accountability in higher education, particularly in the context of open data and learning analytics. Institutions must

adopt comprehensive data ethics frameworks that go beyond compliance with legal requirements to foster a culture of ethical responsibility. Key elements of such frameworks include:

- Establishing clear policies that address data ownership, access, usage, and protection, ensuring alignment with international regulations such as GDPR, FOIP, and PIPEDA.
- Developing protocols for informed consent, ensuring that students, staff, and other stakeholders understand how their data is collected, stored, and utilised.
- Implementing rigorous oversight mechanisms, such as data ethics committees or research ethics boards, to review data-driven projects and mitigate potential risks.
- Embedding ethical considerations into curriculum and staff training, raising awareness about issues such as bias in data-driven systems, risks of misrepresentation, and the potential for discriminatory practices.
- Encouraging transparency by publishing reports on institutional data usage and engaging stakeholders in discussions about ethical challenges and solutions.
- Exploring the development of "data for good" initiatives that encourage students and staff to use data ethically for societal benefit, such as addressing inequality or improving sustainability. HEIs should aim to strike a balance between safeguarding individual privacy and maximizing the value of data for institutional and societal benefits. Collaborative efforts with other institutions can further enhance ethical standards and set benchmarks for responsible data usage across the sector.

Methodological enhancement

By elaborating this report, we come across methodological considerations that might well serve further internal benchmarking, or regional benchmarking (between open universities networks).

A Benchmarking Matrix for Open Data Adoption should be developed to evaluate Open Data practices across institutions, focusing on key domains such as Data Governance and Policy, which examines the existence of clear guidelines for Open Data usage, legal compliance, and ethical considerations; Data Infrastructure and Accessibility, which assesses the quality and availability of Open Data portals and adherence to standards like FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable); Impact Assessment, which measures how Open Data improves educational outcomes, research collaboration, and institutional transparency; and Stakeholder Engagement, which evaluates the extent of involvement from internal and external stakeholders in data sharing and reuse.

This matrix should integrate quantitative data (e.g., usage statistics from Open Data portals, number of datasets published, Open Data maturity scores) with qualitative insights from case studies and surveys, employing mixed-methods analysis to identify correlations between robust Open Data practices and institutional performance metrics such as research output, student engagement, or operational transparency. Furthermore, findings from high-performing institutions should be synthesized into a repository of best practices, highlighting innovative uses of Open Data, such as predictive analytics for student success or AI-based tools built on shared datasets. Challenges and opportunities should also be contextualized, particularly focusing on ethical and legal considerations, by building a framework to analyse issues related to data privacy, intellectual property, and inclusivity, and on scalability and adaptation, assessing the scalability of Open Data practices and their adaptability to varying institutional

contexts, especially in resource-constrained environments. Finally, a longitudinal analysis should be incorporated to track changes in Open Data practices over time, including policy updates, technological advancements, and shifts in usage patterns, thereby identifying trends that influence the adoption and success of Open Data in Open Universities. Table 4 introduces a synthesis on the methodological implications.

Table 5– Methodological enhancement’s dimensions

Methodological Dimension	Drivers	Description
Benchmarking Matrix for Open Data Adoption	Data Governance and Policy	Existence of clear guidelines for Open Data usage, legal compliance, and ethical considerations.
	Data Infrastructure and Accessibility	Quality and availability of Open Data portals, adherence to standards like FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
	Impact Assessment	Measurement of how Open Data improves educational outcomes, research collaboration, and institutional transparency.
	Stakeholder Engagement	Extent of involvement from internal and external stakeholders in data sharing and reuse.
Quantitative and Qualitative Integration	Combination of Data	Combine quantitative data (e.g., usage statistics from Open Data portals, number of datasets published, Open Data maturity scores) with qualitative insights from case studies and surveys
	Combination of Methods	Use mixed-methods analysis to identify correlations between robust Open Data practices and institutional performance metrics like research output, student engagement, or operational transparency.
Focus on Best Practices and Innovations	Best practices sharing	Share key findings from high-performing institutions to create a repository of best practices, particularly those that demonstrate creative or impactful uses of Open Data (e.g., collaborative learning platforms, public-facing dashboards).
	Highlights on Success Stories	Highlight uses of Open Data that encompass educational impact throughout success stories, such as predictive analytics or AI-based tools built on shared datasets, that are adopted by end users to transform their teaching or their learning
Contextualizing Challenges and Opportunities	Ethical and Legal Considerations	Adopt existing frameworks to analyse challenges related to data privacy, intellectual property, and inclusivity in HEIs Open Data usage.
	Scalability and Adaptation	Assess the scalability of Open Data practices and their adaptability to varying institutional contexts, particularly in resource-constrained environments.
Incorporating Longitudinal Analysis	Longitudinal perspective	Introduce a longitudinal perspective by tracking changes in Open Data practices over time, including policy updates, technological improvements, and shifts in usage patterns.
	Trends identification	Identify trends that influence the adoption and success of Open Data in Open Universities.

By adopting this enhanced methodology, institutional leaders or units' coordinators can achieve a robust understanding of how the Open University where they operate is leveraging Open Data to enhance transparency, inclusivity, and innovation, while also respecting data privacy and data ethics through appropriate stewardship. This grid attempts to provide a roadmap to detect best practices and strategies for overcoming challenges in Open Data adoption. It also supports the development of institutional strategies to engage researchers and educators in sustainable and impactful Open Data ecosystems in higher education. The ultimate achievement of the conceptual instruments in this report is triggering actors' reflection about overall data practices. Such a reflection should ensure a comprehensive, context-sensitive, and actionable analysis, enabling Open Universities to better align their Open Data practices with global standards and local needs.

In the concluding part of these recommendations, it would be also relevant to consider ongoing debates about the usage for AI development of public goods such as Open Data. Building on the working document "Alignment Assembly on AI and the Commons" (Open Future, 2024), we can consider the relevance of digital activism in considering how technologies should be developed. The principles in this document advocates for transparency in AI systems to ensure accountability and public understanding, inclusivity and ethical considerations, something that is already present in most literature on AI (European Commission, 2020; Nemorin et al., 2023; UNESCO, 2020). Less discussed and as aspect that liaises with the current report is the importance of public infrastructure support, purported by the document, whose authors advocate for funding and developing public digital infrastructures as alternatives to dominant AI systems. The document goes on proposing "Alignment assemblies" that are a collective approach of AI development governance:

"Alignment assemblies are part of a broader trend aimed at increasing deliberation and participatory governance of digital technologies. Citizen panels are a related, more advanced form of deliberative process that is gaining popularity, with citizen panels on AI and data being organized in Belgium and the United Kingdom". (op.cit, p.2)

This approach reverberates in other collectives reflecting on the need of community approaches to technological development. Other works are for example "tequilogias" (Aguilar, 2024) or "compost engineering" (Varon & Egaña, 2024) , who emphasise the relevance of slow reflection and local technological solutions in the respect of cultural values.

Here is where open data and the role of Open Universities achieve centrality. While openness is crucial, the principle of balancing openness with other values acknowledges the need to consider privacy and security in AI regulation. Additionally, the assembly addresses the risks of centralised AI power by advocating for measures to distribute AI benefits more equitably, and underscores the importance of environmental responsibility, emphasizing the need to mitigate the energy consumption and carbon footprint of AI systems.

All in all, the appropriate balance between openness and the individual and collective private or local values is to be considered. And this is the main challenge we must face in a future that overcomes techno-solutionism and embraces human values before any sort of technological development.

Practical recommendations: Working with Educational Data

In this section, we will reflect on the connections between educational data overall (open and public or protected/private) and their usage in Higher Education. We will focus on what we called the “micro-level”, namely, the data that can be extracted from classroom activities.

As data-driven techniques become more popular and some experimental and commercial applications are rolled out, end users like teachers, technical staff supporting online learning, instructional designers, administrative staff, and students need to pay attention to how technologies become part of educational experiences and what values and imaginaries are assigned to data in teaching and learning. The technological advances that lead to the use of data-driven techniques cannot be passively experienced by teachers and students. Rather, they must be continuously active in pushing for the readability of data infrastructures and participating in the negotiation processes related to oversight, transparency, technological robustness, privacy, interests in place, and the overall educational impact.

Nowadays there are instruments that, integrated into learning platforms and apps, allow data collection and visualization that supposedly aim at promoting teachers and students’ reflection on their activity. The type of data collected is based on basic numeric parameters of presence, participation, downloads, etc. Also, data coming from interactions between participants and text like messages, posts, written assignments can generate relevant information. However, it takes complex and interdisciplinary reflection to move from seeing and extracting basic data (clicks, logs or downloads) to produce visual representations of complex educational concepts like “drop out” or “self-regulation”. Furthermore, recommendations and conversational robots or *chatbots*, which introduce interactive features based on the data collected and modelled require pedagogical definition and computational and interface development. Therefore, what we will achieve through this section is several recommendations to collect and share data that might be potentially adopted for self-reflection, teaching developments or institutional policies about educational data collection and usage.

Where is my educational data?

Most data collected in classroom settings come from online learning platforms or apps adopted for several activities. However, to respond to relevant educational problems, universities combine several data sources. Fig. 1 illustrates the different sources of data adopted to inform educational quality.

As a matter of fact, we should consider:

- Learning Management Systems (LMS): Tracks student engagement, assignment submissions, and interactions.
- Presence Records: Attendance logs and participation tracking in digital or physical classrooms.
- Library Data: Information on resource usage, borrowing history, and research habits.
- eBook Platforms: Digital textbook usage, reading habits, and annotations.
- Smart Tutoring Systems: AI-powered platforms that provide adaptive learning and personalized support.
- Informational Administration: Institutional databases storing student profiles, grades, and progress reports.
- Videos: Educational video usage analytics, including time spent watching and engagement levels.

- Other Sources: Additional tools that contribute to the learning ecosystem, such as mobile apps and collaborative platforms.

As we pointed out in the introduction the data gathered is never useful in its “raw” form. Let’s consider an example: if a teacher downloads the logs from her taught course, she might be able to see who has completed a task with delay, or the number of downloads and clicks in a certain section of the LMS that pinpoints interest or concern about the topic presented there. However, without careful learning design, or complementary information about the students’ study habits in the library, logs might reveal very little about students’ difficulties to complete a task in due time, or the lack of interest on a topic. Therefore, meaningful insights come data processing, from basic visualisations to the adoption of algorithms that highlight trends or trigger recommendations.

Figure 3 - Data Systems in Higher Education

Examples of data points that can be integrated include:

- Clicks and Logs: Monitoring student activity, such as login times and resource access.
- Time of Connection: Measuring engagement frequency and consistency.
- Notes and Forum Posts: Evaluating student contributions in discussions.
- Interactions in Forums and Games: Understanding collaborative learning dynamics through sociograms.
- Quantitative Analysis of Discussions: Assessing student discourse and participation patterns.

Therefore, the vast amount of data collected in Higher Education Institutions alone is not enough—it must be transformed into pedagogical concepts to inform decision-making. However, understanding data architectures might help teachers, staff supporting educational development and support like teaching assistants, instructional designer, tutors, to collect and prepare the appropriate data.

To dig deeper into the complex relationship between educational decision making and data supporting such operation, we provide now lists of most data-driven practices and the metrics/data supporting them. In the following, Tables 7 and 8 display such relationship. The first mentioned table provides information about the metrics adopted in relation to data-driven practices in education. The most represented educational dimensions are Learning Design, Teaching Effectiveness, Student Success, Students' self-regulation. Despite there is relevant literature relating specific processes (like collaborative work or problem solving) the above dimensions are general and well represented. From Table 7, we can observe that basic digital interactions (e.g., accesses, clicks, usage time, views, and downloads) are widely used metrics, particularly in evaluating Teaching Effectiveness and the quality of Learning Design. More advanced analytics, such as discourse analysis, planning systems, peer interaction, and competencies tracking, are quite reported but less standardized across research. Self-regulation metrics, including dashboard tracking, motivation, procrastination, and social media use, are underrepresented despite their importance in student-centred learning, and here, we meet the technical difficulties of assembling such data. University-level data (e.g., high school grades, socio-demographics, and institutional engagement) appear mostly in research on Student Success rather than Teaching Effectiveness, highlighting how necessary data-integration is to analyse very relevant educational dimensions. Again, we observe that while digital tools provide valuable data, many complex educational processes remain difficult to quantify, requiring more advanced and contextualized analytics.

Table 8 presents an overview of technologies supporting data collection and analysis, mapping the feasibility and availability of data extraction tools across different learning environments. The table categorizes data collection into LMS-based metrics, university administration systems, and third-party instruments while indicating whether these data points are visible, required, feasible, or inaccessible within existing systems. From Table 8, we can observe that basic user activity data (e.g., accesses, clicks, usage time, and grades) is widely available and visible in common LMS tools such as grade reports, student personal pages, and course settings dashboards. However, more complex interactions (e.g., peer engagement, discussion quality, and academic competencies) are only feasible through advanced developments or custom integrations within commercial tools. University administrative data (e.g., socio-demographic factors, institutional participation, and high school performance) remains largely inaccessible without extensive infrastructure, such as data lakes or institutional repositories. This is partially due to having separate data infrastructures provided by different organizational units with different historic competencies and training. Most importantly, recently the attention has been put on data ethics, with a growing concern on adopting sensible data (like gender, age, address, etc.) with uninformed consent to support institutional processes (Khalil et al., 2018). Also, metrics related to personal student attributes (e.g., motivation, procrastination, social media use) are mostly unavailable or would require external sources beyond LMS and university systems, like teams of experts handling personality inventories and other extremely delicate and sensible information. Educational problems like procrastination and delay in the students' career often require understanding about such variables. Therefore, automated systems, including intelligent tutoring and learning analytics dashboards encounter a dilemma: the relationship between data ethics and accuracy, effectiveness and usability of data to inform daily educational practice (Pardos et al., 2016; Tsai & Gašević, 2017b).

Table 6. Most used metrics according to the educational dimension (mapped in the literature)

METRICS		EDUCATIONAL DIMENSION				
		TEACHING		LEARNING		
		Design	Teaching Effectiveness	Student Success	Self-regulation	
SIMPLE METRICS	Source					
Accesses	Learning Management Systems					
Clicks						
Usage time						
Views						
Download						
Completion						
Final Grade						
Partial Grade						
Correct answer in interaction						
Post						
Sentiment +/-						
Discourse / Narrative Text						
COMPLEX METRICS						
Using auto-complete tools						
Using planning systems (calendar, personalized home page)						
Dashboard view/course progress						
Message to the teacher						
Search for help in forum						
Levels of interaction with peers						
Learning outcomes						
Competencies						
Socio-demographic data	University administration systems					
Parents' educational level						
High School Note						
Type of school						
Extraordinary Institutional Activities						
Group membership						
Using the library						
Item/Subject Difficulty	Specific Apps or Platforms					
Opinion about the course						
Perception of difficulty of the subject						
Personality						
Motivation						
Academic skills						
Procrastination of academic tasks						
Using social media to search for information	Other					
Using social media to seek peer support						
Others...						

Table 7 Technology supporting data collection and analysis

Visible/Required by the system
 Not visible/required but feasible

Not feasible

METRICS		LMS Most Common Instruments									
		Students' Personal Page	Course Settings/Course Parameters	Participants Access	Participant Profiles	Logs	Grade Book and Grader Report	Open Digital Badges	Goals' Achievements / Competencies	Teacher Dashboard	Automated messages / Chatbots
SIMPLE METRICS	Source										
Accesses	LMS										
Clicks											
Usage time											
Vision											
Discharge											
Completion											
Final Note											
Partial Note											
Correct answer in interaction											
Post											
Sentiment +/-											
Discourse / Narrative Text											
COMPLEX METRICS											
Using auto-complete tools											
Using planning systems (calendar, personalized home page)											
Dashboard view/course progress											
Message to the teacher											
Search for help in forum											
Levels of interaction with peers											
Learning outcomes											
Competencies											
Socio-demographic data	University administration systems	Only accessible through development / Data Lakes - Infrastructures									
Parents' educational level											
High School Note											
Type of school											
Extraordinary Institutional Activities											
Group membership											
Using the library											
Item/Subject Difficulty	Instruments development	Only feasible through ad hoc developments OR Integrated as Product / Service within a commercial tool									
Opinion about the course											
Perceived Course Difficulty											
Personality											
Motivation											
Academic skills											
Procrastination of academic tasks											
Using social media to search for information	Other										
Using social media to seek peer support											
Other...											

The type of data extracted can be decided either by the single teacher or at an institutional level. The first case is an expression of teaching autonomy, in which the teacher as professional decides the best approach to teach and to inform teaching through data as just another pedagogical “technique”. For example, a teacher might be interested in understanding the correlation between interest (e.g.: downloads and views on a resource) and success (final grade). The second case displays a situation in which there is an institutional strategy in place, aiming at extracting systematically data to achieve an overall picture of practices. For example, the institution can request teachers to inform the learning goals to be achieved in her lesson plan through a form, and use such information combined with final students’ performance at specific assignments, to generate visualisations connecting the initial planned action with the final learning achievements. It is easy to understand here that any form of data treatment has ethical and political implications (how do we define interest and success in terms of metrics in the first case, and how do we display performance in the second case). The scholarly literature documents this problem very well, offering a well-structured critique (Perrotta & Williamson, 2018; Tsai & Gašević, 2017b), but also several reflections and developments to solve the mentioned tensions (Francis et al., 2023; Pardos et al., 2016; Rienties et al., 2016).

Pedagogical and technological design for educational data enhancement

Let’s explore now how the data collected within a classroom by means of a learning management system (e.g., the popular Moodle, or the commercial platform Blackboard). Fig 2. presents three-level model of data-driven activities in education, visualized as an iceberg. It highlights how data collection, processing, and analysis operate at different levels, revealing the connections between pedagogical and technological design that are often invisible when adopting a data-driven system.

Figure 4 – The “data” iceberg: from the Teaching and Learning Activities and content to data collection

In Fig.4 we see the levels of data extraction, statistical operations, data transformation and algorithmic operations (from visualization to recommendation system) that should serve to support different levels of decision and subsequent human action (e.g. : faced with a certain diagnosis of participation in discussion groups, the teacher can animate, generate subsidiary spaces for support, replace an activity, change the arrangement of collaborative groups). We see precisely the relationship between applied technology and different levels of information and automation supporting decision making.

The first level, as we see in the image, is that of Teaching & Learning. It operates at the surface, visible level and its focus is to provide the necessary interface to support teaching and learning. This is the most visible layer of design aiming at capturing data. Despite it is frequently related to what students see and interact with directly, it requires complex design-thinking from the teacher and other expert staff. It consists of learning materials, online tasks, and participation activities that students engage with throughout their courses. Examples are Files (lecture notes, PDFs, slides, etc.), Media content (videos, podcasts, animations), Quizzes, Assignments, Online forums and other spaces of communication.

At the second level, the focus moves to Feedback & Assessment as part of a monitoring process. This level requires teacher or instructional design attention to support tailored features (from the platforms adopted as Learning Management Systems to apps) like Scales (grading rubrics, evaluation criteria); Grades visualization (progress tracking, grades calculations); Progress bars (visual indicators of course completion). This level hence involves tracking student performance and providing feedback through quantitative measures. It allows students and educators to monitor progress and intervene when necessary. Tools like progress bars help learners self-regulate their studies, while grading tables and learning plans provide structured feedback. The third level is the hidden but relevant in terms of automations available in the system. Data from student interactions, assignments, and progress is extracted and analysed to provide insights (dashboards) and automated recommendations. For example, if data shows a strong relationship between assignment completion and final grades, an early support system can be designed to automatically alert students who are falling behind.

At the third level data extraction, analysis, and automated actions (deep analytics) happen. The data can be manually extracted, for example, downloading Logs (student activity tracking) or grades. However, most LMS systems produce course & student reports which are displayed as cards or web pages aggregating the whole information embedded in the system. If the first and second levels were carefully planned, there are possibilities to see this type of synthesis. However, to produce more refined actions, it is necessary to further transform and elaborate data manually (to see correlations or predictive relationships between variables generated by the data collected). Nowadays many universities include research developments like Early Warning Systems (identifying at-risk students through predictive algorithms using the data from students' performance); Adaptive Content (personalized learning recommendations); Chatbots (AI-powered tutoring and feedback); Automated Actions (e.g., "If a student fails an assignment twice, send a support message."). These types of systems are tailored and tested carefully on contextual data, and it is plausible that respect ethical guidelines to deal with students' data (according to research protocols). Also, commercial platforms (from social media to apps) offer services like the above described. However, such services could be based on prior data extracted from students in social and economic conditions that adopt the freemium models of platforms, hence ceding data with no or little awareness of the process of data monetization (Bennett, 2018; Stewart, 2023). However, some companies engage carefully with the university or other educational organisations to develop tailored products, from co-designing to piloting and collecting feedback on end users' experiences and impact.

This case must be considered positively, if companies are aware of the ethical concerns about surveillance, data monetization and oversimplification. These phenomena are frequent in commercial apps and platforms, often accompanied by bold promises of productivity, performance, achievement that are not supported in literature nor in impact evaluations (Selwyn & Gašević, 2020; Watters, 2021).

All actors involved in the educational activities must recall hence that the “automated” layer does not work in isolation: it requires careful design in connection with the first and second layers. Extracting data, polishing and producing developments that support data visualization, or training AI-powered tools on real data collected from prior cohorts or the same group of students is always complex and problematic.

Overall, we might consider the following steps to extract reusable data at the micro-level:

- Identify the pedagogical processes under analysis
- Establish metrics and data collection through the available technological means.
- Data Extraction and Reading.
- Interpretation.
- Educational decision making.

We will offer now a sequence of steps as a structured approach to designing and implementing data-driven pedagogical interventions to improve teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and learning outcomes. Such an approach outlines a six-step process that integrates pedagogical problem definition, technological design, data collection, analysis, diagnostics, and targeted interventions. The process ultimately supports reflective practices for both teachers and students.

Step 1 - Pedagogical Design

At the foundation of this step lies the educational dimension we want to work with, which focuses on key educational priorities:

- Teaching effectiveness – Ensuring that instructional methods lead to meaningful student learning and engagement.
- Design optimization – Structuring educational activities and tools for efficiency, ease of use, and maximum impact.
- Dropout prevention – Identifying and addressing factors that contribute to student disengagement and attrition.
- Self-regulation – Encouraging students to take ownership of their learning by setting goals, tracking progress, and adjusting strategies.
- Educational goals and related activities – Aligning learning activities with broader educational objectives and competencies.

These issues inform the need for data collection and technological interventions. This is good practice, diverse from an approach where data abundance is believed to be sufficient to get insights into any educational process or phenomenon.

Step 2 - Technological Design

Considering the learning goals, the teaching and learning activities envisaged to pursue such goals, and the connection with an educational priority, it follows a technological design in data collection and classification. This involves defining key data points and metadata related to educational activity, such as:

- Views, downloads, and time spent on materials – Tracking how often students access resources and how much time they invest.
- Forum participation and post counts – Monitoring student contributions to discussions as indicators of engagement.
- Assignment submissions – Measuring student completion rates and submission patterns.
- Quiz attempts and results – Evaluating how often students take quizzes and their performance trends.
- Text-based interactions from forums, diaries, and assignments – Analysing written content for insights into student thinking and engagement.

These data points serve as indicators of student engagement, learning patterns, and potential areas for intervention, provided that there is a careful conceptual definition of the relationship between the pedagogical step and the technology adopted to collect data. For example, considering success as the sole grade achieved at the end of a course is also deemed problematic in the literature (Raffaghelli & Grion, 2023). Other more refined ways of tracking success include collaboration (measured through sociograms or network analysis) or participation (measured through number of replies to post), among others.

Step 3 - Data Collection

This step outlines a systematic data collection process, that can be characterized as follows.

- Participant registration – Gathering basic student demographics and enrolment information.
- Motivation surveys – Understanding students' reasons for engaging in the course and their expectations, mapping their perceived knowledge.
- Progress tracking (topics, activities, assignments) – Monitoring how students advance through the curriculum.
- Results – Recording scores from quizzes, assignments, and other assessments.
- Opinion surveys – Gathering student feedback on course content, teaching methods, and learning experience.

Step 4 - Diagnostics and Predictions

After collecting data, several operations of data polishing, labelling, and re-arranging where necessary are carried out. Whenever the main person responsible for data collection (presumably the teacher) is requested to share datasets, careful operations of data anonymisation must be considered. Data anonymization is a key area of research, including both human-based operations (pseudo-anonymisation, re-labelling, splitting datasets, blending variables, etc.) (Hernández-Leo et al., 2023). Initial analyses are followed by an arrangement of data that informs diagnosis and predictions within the educational process, using both descriptive and advanced analytics:

- Descriptive statistics – Summarizing key trends in student performance and engagement.
- Item difficulty analysis – Assessing the complexity of individual assessment items to refine instructional design.

- Correlation and regression analysis – Identifying relationships between different learning activities and performance outcomes.
- Cluster analysis – Grouping students based on similarities in progress, completion rates, or performance patterns.
- Text mining – Analysing student writing in forums, diaries, or assignments to assess engagement, sentiment, or understanding.
- Machine learning techniques (e.g., neural networks) – Predicting student behaviours, such as dropout risks or potential areas of struggle, to enable proactive interventions.

These insights allow educators to tailor interventions to specific student needs.

Step 5 - Techno-pedagogical Intervention

Based on the analysis, the teaching staff (including interdisciplinary teams supporting the usage of educational technologies) select the type of data usage to inform practice:

- Teacher dashboards – Providing real-time data on student engagement, progress, and learning outcomes.
- Student dashboards – Giving students personalized feedback on their learning progress, strengths, and areas for improvement.
- Automated feedback systems (e.g., chatbots) – Offering students instant feedback and guidance based on their responses.
- Individual feedback from teachers – Providing personalized support to students who need additional guidance based on predictive systems.
- General feedback to the class – Highlighting common strengths and misconceptions to enhance collective learning based on predictive systems.
- Opportunities for peer tutoring and collaborative learning – Encouraging students to learn from and support each other based on data collected.

Step 6 - Teacher and Student Reflection

Having carried the former five steps, our approach emphasises reflection as a crucial component, ensuring that both teachers and students engage with the data in a creative and constructive way. Indeed, certain data usages and representations could trigger competitiveness, metrics' dependence, oversimplification, assuming objectivity, etc. Overall, data-driven systems are not valuable per se. They must produce insights to foster human flourishing.

Figure 5 Moodle data structure – Translated and Adapted from: “Inspire API components ” by David Llaó (2017) - https://docs.moodle.org/dev/File:Inspire_API_components.png GNU Public Licence

Across the 6 steps: Ethical Considerations

Throughout the process, several ethical considerations are acknowledged, including:

- Data definition bias – The way data is labelled and categorized can shape interpretations and decisions.
- Data quality – Ensuring accurate, reliable, and meaningful data collection and analysis.
- Students’ privacy – Protecting personal and learning data from misuse or unauthorized access.
- Algorithmic opacity – Addressing the lack of transparency in how AI-driven decisions are made.
- System glitches – Ensuring reliability and minimizing errors that could affect learning outcomes.
- Techno-political interests – Recognizing how educational technology may be influenced by commercial or policy-driven factors.
- Students’ voice – Involving students in decision-making about their data and learning experiences.
- Ecological impact – Evaluating the environmental footprint of digital education technologies.

This framework of action based on six steps and a cross-component introduces how a data-driven approach could be imagined. Technology or data collection do not come first. Indeed, it is deeply emphasised how pedagogical thinking addresses all the cascade of technological design allowing data collection and usage.

Using data: From data to learning analytics

Up to here, we considered a multiplicity of sources that are integrated into many of the existing developments published in the literature. We will now further into approaches of data usage.

Most frequent uses are connected to support teaching and learning directly and do not necessarily entail opening educational data. Generating open data out of data extracted can be adopted as an approach to support further institutional decision making or educational research. However, adopting data to enhance teaching and learning relates to a different level of discussion connected with the field of *learning analytics*. In the following, we will introduce both approaches.

Educational data extracted from classroom activities could be prepared for being shared as open data. As explained before, the data collected must be prepared carefully to be useful for future educators and researchers. Opening data from educational settings has to do with making accessible each stage of the educational process (techno-pedagogical design, instruments of data collection, analysis, and publication) embracing open approaches to educational science, such as pre-registration, data sharing, transparent analyses, and open access publication (van der Zee & Reich, 2018). A subtle aspect of this situation relates to the poor appropriation and utilization of scientific research products in the pedagogical field by potential users (stakeholders in the education and training system) (Raffaghelli & Manca, 2019). However, we already mentioned the difficulties of collecting relevant data, to which we should add the fact that with no institutional policies in place about open data, teachers might not find any clear motivation to put any effort in working with data.

In the following, some practical indications and illustrations might help how to deal with open education data from classroom settings.

Publishing open datasets

According to our six steps approach, after having selected the key pedagogical concepts, designed the educational activities, adopted the instruments to collect data, and implemented the approaches for data analysis and usage, datasets can be extracted. The teacher might decide to integrate data from other sources, through manual input (working with any spreadsheet software) or through databases integration (also through spreadsheet software or through programming software like R or Python).

We will introduce now the steps to publish data as an open record, enhancing public platforms or the university institutional repositories.

Before starting editing, it is crucial to remember some quality principles relating to build a quality open data record.

For example, the FAIR Data Principles provide guidelines for data management to ensure that digital resources are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Association of European Research Libraries, 2017b). These principles aim to enhance data sharing, reuse, and long-term preservation across scientific and educational domains.

1. Findable (F):

- Data should have unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI).
- Metadata should be richly described and indexed in searchable resources.
- Data should be registered or indexed in a discoverable database.

2. Accessible (A)

- Data should be retrievable using standardized communication protocols.
- Access conditions should be clearly stated (e.g., open access, restricted, or embargoed).
- Even if data is no longer available, metadata should remain accessible.

3. Interoperable (I)

- Data should use standardized formats and vocabularies to allow integration with other datasets.
- It should follow domain-relevant ontologies and metadata standards.
- Data should be linked to other datasets where possible to enhance usability.

4. Reusable (R)

- Data should have clear usage licenses (e.g., Creative Commons).
- Metadata should provide detailed provenance (who created, modified, or used the data).
- Data should follow community standards for quality and documentation.

It is extremely relevant to remember that FAIR principles do not mandate open access but promote transparency and structured data management, ensuring that data remains accessible, interpretable, and reusable across different systems and research communities.

In a small example published at Zenodo (Bozzi et al., 2020) we can find the datasets (spreadsheets in machine-readable version) and code (exported to a text file, usable on R, an open source statistics' programme) adopted to process data. The dataset relates to a study on peer learning as a key component of an active approach to teaching in large size lectures. There is a description of the material available, and the type of analysis performed is explained. The files can be downloadable. The record is referenced with a DOI and can relate to publications, as complementary material. The type of data represents the students' engagement with peer learning (correct responses after time devoted to couples' exchanges on problems) and the final grades got.

Finally, the published material is placed in an open-access research data repository developed by CERN under the European OpenAIRE program (Zenodo)¹⁶. It provides a free and long-term storage platform for researchers, institutions, and projects to share, publish, and preserve research outputs, including datasets, software, reports, and publications. There are multiple open data platforms supporting education researchers to publish their data. For example, Harvard Dataverse is open to any kind of research contribution, and several open datasets connected to the field of education can be found. Harvard Dataverse is an open-source research data repository hosted by Harvard University and managed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS). It provides a secure and scalable platform for researchers, institutions, and projects to store, share, and manage datasets across various disciplines. Relating to data collected from teaching and learning, we can cite the example of the MITx and HarvardX Dataverse¹⁷, which published several datasets on MOOCs which document openly (Open Access, through formats that can be accessed with open-source software). The datasets have been used in several ways

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁷ <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataverse/mxhx>

and are completed with metadata that make them human-readable. Also, DOI (digital object identifier) has been provided. In the image, an open data displaying Socioeconomic Status Indicators (Hansen & Reich, 2016).

Figure 6 – Example of FAIR open education data

Another FAIR approach to data sharing is publishing onto the Institutional Repositories¹⁸. For example, the Open University (UK) has an institutional repository denominated “Open Research Online” (ORO) where several open data records can be found. Fig. 5 introduces a relevant example. The open data record is shortly described. However, the metadata adopted allows the reader to browse other similar works (in this case a dataset with assessment results, logs and interactions with the “Virtual Learning Environment” or LMS).

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Institutional_repository

RESEARCH OA [oa:oro.open.ac.uk:53873](https://doi.org/10.1038/SDATA.2017.171)

Open University Learning Analytics dataset

Jakub Kuzilek · Martin Hlosta · Zdenek Zdrahal · 28 November 2017 · DOI: 10.1038/SDATA.2017.171

Abstract

Learning Analytics focuses on the collection and analysis of learners' data to improve their learning experience by providing informed guidance and to optimise learning materials. To support the research in this area we have developed a dataset, containing data from courses presented at the Open University (OU). What makes the dataset unique is the fact that it contains demographic data together with aggregated clickstream data of students' interactions in the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE). This enables the analysis of student behaviour, represented by their actions. The dataset contains the information about 22 courses, 32,593 students, their assessment results, and logs of their interactions with the VLE represented by daily summaries of student clicks (10,655,280 entries). The dataset is freely available at https://analyse.kmi.open.ac.uk/open_dataset under a CC-BY 4.0 license

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These days, virtual learning environments (VLEs) are essential and widely used worldwide for information exchange. While VLE benefits remote learning, in-person lectures are more challenging to maintain student

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Figure 7 – An open dataset placed in an institutional repository (OUUK)

As can be grasped from the examples shared, educational data relates to educational dynamics and cases, and it is packaged with the intention to support insights or technical developments (like modelling).

Next, we will explore the steps involved in organizing and structuring educational data.

Step 1 – Define a learning ontology

An educational ontology is a structured framework that defines concepts, relationships, and categories within the field of education. It serves as a semantic model that enables data integration, knowledge representation, and interoperability across different educational systems and technologies (Afreen et al., 2024). By formalising the relationships between educational concepts, ontologies facilitate better organization, retrieval, and processing of learning resources, learner data, and pedagogical strategies (Costa Araujo et al., 2020).

Some key features of educational ontologies

- **Standardized Vocabulary** – Provides a common language for educational concepts, making data exchange seamless.
- **Hierarchical Structure** – Organizes concepts into categories and subcategories (e.g., "Assessment" > "Formative Assessment").
- **Interoperability** – Enables different learning management systems (LMS), intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), and adaptive learning platforms to communicate effectively.
- **Semantic Reasoning** – Allows AI-powered tools to interpret and make decisions based on structured knowledge.

The field has developed within the growing sector of online learning. Indeed, with the growing area of pedagogy developing several theories during the XX century, there exist several well-known concepts (e.g., the difference between assessment and evaluation, or the concept of self-regulation or active teaching

methods). However, being education and interdisciplinary field, the terms adopted might differ, particularly in the expanding area of technology-mediated learning. For example, initial educational ontologies were connected to the so called “learning objects” or resources with specific properties that could be shared across digital platforms (LMS). The LOM ontology was such a case, developed by the institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), it classifies the mentioned digital learning objects based on categories such as content type, difficulty level, and intended audience. Nowadays, many Open Educational Resources and MOOCs adopt such standards and can be extracted from one repository to be integrated into another, also using AI techniques to classify and organise them (Barlassina, 2022). A further example is the SIOC (Semantically-Interlinked Online Communities) for Education). The ontology is built upon the SIOC ontology to structure discussions, blogs, and forum interactions in online learning environments. This type of ontology helps analyse student engagement in discussion forums by categorizing interactions based on learning topics. Yet another example is the ontology generated by the Open University (UK) supporting Learning Analytics (Kuzilek et al., 2015). This ontology models student behaviour and learning analytics and has been applied to build dashboards to track student engagement and predict dropout risks.

In conclusion, educational ontologies enhance knowledge representation in digital learning environments, allowing for more effective data integration, personalization, and analytics in education. They are widely used in LMS, adaptive learning platforms, e-learning repositories, and AI-driven educational technologies.

Step 2 - Define the title of the educational open dataset

The title should relate to a key term possibly existing on a selected educational ontology. If there are no ontologies available, the definition of key terms must come from pedagogical theory or a well-established term in the educational literature. Also, the title can refer to the type of data to be shared. For example, this case is connected to the research published: “Understanding collective behaviour of learning design communities” (Hernández-Leo & Michos, 2018) relates to the first type of approach. Instead, this case refers to the type of data shared “Socioeconomic Status Indicators of HarvardX and MITx Participants” (Hansen & Reich, 2015).

The title is relevant: it is the first visible element and addresses database searches. Titles like “revised.csv” do not help both human and machine readability.

Step 3 - Define the right Key Words

In this phase it is crucial to select keywords that relate to an educational dynamic or topic. In this regard, we must consider the relevance of educational ontologies applied to learners’ data. Labelling data has been a key problem (as we explained earlier in this section) to represent educational phenomena. Keywords can highlight the education area (STEM, Humanities...), teaching method (problem-based learning), the type of data (social interactions), among others.

Step 4 - Write a significant summary/abstract

The abstract must contain key information addressing the reader or the algorithm scrapping data to grasp the purpose and the type of data collected. There is information more useful to a human reader, and

metadata allowing machine-reading¹⁹. Both cases must be considered. A suggestion to structure a summary is to include:

- Research Context
- Research Question/Hypothesis
- Methodological Approach
- Data collection procedures (Survey, Data extracted, Assessment, LMS, etc.).
- Software used.
- Data cleaning and anonymisation procedures (if significant)
- Data descriptions and type of analysis
- Number of files
- Type of files

To conclude, comments on the data re-usability (critical issues, proposals for data sharing and interest of the authors in keep tracking over the reusability) can be added.

Step 5 - Prepare your dataset

The type of files that can be included as datasets are many, however, often educational datasets are configured as a dataset (from spreadsheets to text without format or lightweight data formats like JSON, to other basic files like images or multimedia files). Also, the code adopted to analyse data and/or source/link to externally placed code source (e.g. GitHub) is good practice. The Statistical Report can be shared if it's not possible to provide a script. Data can also be corpora or results of learners' works in the case the approach also processes text as data.

It is also extremely helpful to include a Codebook or "Readme" file that supports the reader to browse the database, understanding the purpose of including specific columns or rows.

Whenever the dataset relates to a publication, it is also advisable to include the reference or the full text.

Step 6 - Publish and Share

Before publishing, the record can be shared for quality review and versioning in the case that several participants collaborated to data collection and publication.

After finishing the dataset preparation, it can be shared by using the appropriate data platforms (e.g., open data portals or institutional repositories). In this phase is crucial to understand the difference between such data infrastructures and social media. Despite circulating materials on academic social networks like ResearchGate, Academia.edu or Mendeley Data, can be relevant for a social engagement and dissemination of the educational data published, these are private funded platforms. They might use the published data for business (monetizing the results of public-funded research), for example in AI developments.

Moving forward, we will explore the current developments of learning analytics as a case of data usage.

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Machine-readable_medium_and_data

Implementing Learning Analytics

It was in 2011 when the interest on data collected in educational settings was finally considered an object of study. It was initially connected to educational data mining, but it was soon coined an emerging definition: “learning analytics”. Initial research focused on the digital data generated from learning management systems in fully or blended learning courses. However, the idea of systematically collecting and analysing data was particularly embraced during the MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) spread, between 2012 and 2015. Learning analytics was defined as:

“... the measurement, collection, analysis, and reporting of data about students and their contexts, in order to understand and optimize learning and the environments in which it occurs” (Siemens & Gašević , 2012, p. 1)

Following this trend, the Open University of the UK, a large, fully online university, produced the first experiments, generated a working group that led the development of the field and later also produced a critique (Herodotou et al., 2019; Knight et al., 2014; Rienties et al., 2016) . Rebecca Ferguson, from the same group, generated a vision on the complexity of the field where data collection was combined with a complex vision of the possibilities of pedagogical research on the same data (Ferguson, 2012) . This group of authors also emphasised that data mapping must go far beyond eLearning platforms to encompass interoperability with other systems and give a solid foundation to the pedagogical constructs adopted (Herodotou et al., 2019; Knight et al., 2014) . Already indicated in the seminal work of Long and Siemens (2011) based on the evolution of the topics within the LAK conference (Baker et al., 2021), the areas of research in higher education were also divided, related to:

- System effectiveness (dropout prevention)
- Support for teaching decisions (preventing failure, focusing attention, guiding in-depth study, etc.)
- Support for study autonomy or “self-regulation”.

There are several classifications, but a well-known framework is based on LA approach to data analysis and usage.

Figure 8 - Typologies of analytics according to the levels of automation-human intervention interaction. Diagram adapted from Raffaghelli et al. (2021) .

Fig. 8 represents a data-driven decision-making framework in learning analytics, integrating different data processing approaches with four key types of analytics: Descriptive, Diagnostic, Predictive, and Prescriptive Analytics. These analytics enable educators to move from understanding past learning behaviours to making data-informed interventions for improving student outcomes. Table 9 introduce the functions that Learning Analytics can carry out. The reader can observe that there are different approaches to data processing that lead to characterise the learning analytics and their functions.

Table 8 Integration of Data Processing Approaches and Analytics

Data Processing Approach	Type of Analytics	Function in Learning Analytics
Recording present events, ex-post analysis	Descriptive Analytics	Answers "What happened?" through data visualization , providing insights into student engagement, participation, and performance trends.
Recording present events, ex-ante analysis	Diagnostic Analytics	Answers "What caused it?" by identifying patterns and relationships in student behaviors that influence learning outcomes.
Recording past events, subsequent probability	Predictive Analytics	Answers "What will happen?" by using historical data to predict future learning trends , such as identifying students at risk of failure.
Recording past events, modeling and recommending	Prescriptive Analytics	Answers "What should we do?" by generating automated interventions and personalized recommendations , such as adaptive content suggestions or early warning notifications.

After processing data through analytics, educators must interpret insights and implement actions to enhance student learning.

Example Decisions:

- “This specific student needs my support as a teacher.”
- “This active student requires acknowledgment and can support others.”

Example Actions:

- Offering personalized feedback for students struggling with assignments.
- Assigning peer mentors to promote collaboration.
- Implementing adaptive learning pathways based on individual performance.

Figures 9 and 10 outline a learning analytics dashboard, based on examples taken from online course management platforms (such as Moodle or Blackboard) or experimental projects ²⁰.

Figure 9 – Example of a teacher-side analytics dashboard for an international online course

²⁰For permission reasons we do not reproduce real images in this paragraph. However, the examples on which it is based are from https://docs.moodle.org/400/en/Analytics_plugins

Figure 10 – Examples of teacher-side and student-side analytics dashboards in a hybrid course. The graphical representation captures online activities and activities developed in class or in face-to-face groups, delivered on the online learning platform (e.g. Moodle).

Crucially, data processing and analytics work together to move from observing student performance to predicting and guiding learning experiences. However, teachers always play a crucial role in transforming data insights into meaningful interventions. Interest in learning analytics has grown steadily since its inception a decade ago. On the one hand, this is due to the interest of the interdisciplinary research community between education and computational science. The growth was driven by its diverse applications, which were not exempt of commercial interests. For instance, many learning platforms today claim that they can introduce advanced analytics features—such as access panels, data visualization, and student participation tracking—as their most innovative aspects. At the same time, this evolution has been closely linked to Moodle, arguably the most widely used learning platform in universities worldwide. This last is an open-source platform that is adopted by researchers and developers with open innovations schemes.

In the following, we introduce a working approach to consider the use of Moodle instruments. Following the “data pyramid” scheme and the steps of techno-pedagogical design for data enhancement early introduced in this section, we refer to a) the educational dynamics we want to analyse and promote; b) the type of data collected; c) the methods of data collection and visualisation; d) the type of analysis that can be carried out to cover the specific educational dynamics (supporting reflection). As for the last

column (c) the type of techno-pedagogical goal is also highlighted in terms of Observation (the aim is to observe an existing dynamic), Experimentation (the aim is to establish causal connections, or relationships between an element in the pedagogical design and its impact on learners' activities, achievements, opinions) or Development (developing a techno-pedagogical tool to support any chosen educational dimension)

Table 9 – Working approach to integrate Moodle data and analytics

Data Collection	Methods of Collection, Analysis and Visualization (ex-ante)	Integration of Analysis (ex-post)
<p>PEDAGOGICAL DESIGN Pedagogical question: Can the overall course architecture influence student learning and perceptions?</p>		
Total and Percentages of Access to Resources or Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Logs, Course Participation • Manual Descriptive Statistics • Associated descriptive dynamic panels 	<p>OBSERVATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Series • Correlation between access levels of an activity or set of activities and the grade obtained. • Multiple or Logistic Regression (access levels to various resources and activities, positive reaction to messages, completion of activities, opinion about the course, difficulty of questions – consider normalizing the variables on the final grade of the course). <p>EXPERIMENTATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inferential statistics (considering simple models such as the t-test or very complex ones such as a general linear model) comparing scores obtained in an evaluation of a previous group and a participating group to innovations introduced by the Design. <p>DEVELOPMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictive models of student satisfaction based on quality surveys. • Topic Extraction (topic modelling based on open messages from students)
Completion percentages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Activity Completion • Manual Descriptive Statistics • Associated descriptive dynamic panels 	
Totals and percentages of reaction to a teaching instruction (automatic message)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Message history • Moodle Reports: Course Participation, Activity Completion • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
Grades	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report of the Course Grader • Added display panels for the class • Item Analysis / Descriptive Statistics 	
Opinion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forum Questionnaire/Opinion Results • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	

TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS Pedagogical question: Can (a certain) teaching method influence (positively) students' learning and opinions?		
Total and Percentage of Accesses to Specific Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Logs, Course Participation (Focus Activity) • Display panels available • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	OBSERVATION <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Series • Correlation between access levels of the experimental activity and grade obtained. • Correlation between the grade obtained in the experimental activity and the final grade obtained. EXPERIMENTATION <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inferential statistics (analysis of variance) comparing levels of participation in the specific activity and final grades obtained; or the views of the activity that entails the application of the method; or the time elapsed; or the opinion on the activity as a moderator. DEVELOPMENT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictive models based on student clusters and response to method. • Communication models based on Natural Language Processing systems; or collaboration networks; or epistemic networks.
Specific activity completion percentages Participation in forums	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Activity Completion • Display panels available • Manual Descriptive Statistics (including sociograms of communication between participants in a forum) 	
Totals and percentages of reaction to a teaching indication (message) on a specific activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Message history • Moodle Reports: Course Participation, Activity Completion • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
Partial and total grades	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report of the Qualifier • Display panels available • Item Analysis / Descriptive Statistics 	
Opinion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forum Activity/Opinion Questionnaire Results • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
DROP OUT PREVENTION Pedagogical question: How can we prevent drop out? Which method will better address the problem of drop out?		
Total and Percentage of Access to specific activity during initial and subsequent period of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Logs, Course Participation (Focus Activity) • Instructor Dashboard • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	OBSERVATION <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Series Analysis: Identification of at-risk student groups based on access levels, completion rates, partial grades (percentages, averages, and student group clustering). • Logistic Regression: Analysis of dropout likelihood (yes/no) in relation to access levels, partial grades, and responses to teaching interventions (e.g., message-based support). EXPERIMENTATION
Completion percentages of the specific activity in the initial and subsequent periods of the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Activity Completion • Display panels available • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
Totals and percentages of reaction to a teaching instruction (message) in relation to a specific activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Message history • Moodle Reports: Course Participation, Activity Completion • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	

Partial and total grades	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report of the Qualifier • Display panels • Item Analysis / Descriptive Statistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inferential Statistics (e.g., multiple analysis of variance) to compare response levels to teaching interventions—including teaching/automated messages plus complementary support activities—and their impact on final grades obtained.
Opinion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity/Opinion Results in Private Message • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	

DEVELOPMENT

- Application of neural network models for the early identification of at-risk students.

STRENGTHENING SELF-REGULATION

Pedagogical question: How can we support students' self-regulation skills?

Total and Percentage of Access to activities that support self-regulation (e.g. calendars, planning forums, reflective journal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Logs, Course Participation (Focus Activity) • Display panels available • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	<p>OBSERVATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Correlation between access levels to self-regulation support activities and grades obtained. • Correlation between self-regulation scale results and final grades obtained.
Completion percentages of activities supporting self-regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moodle Reports: Activity Completion • Display panels available • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
Totals and percentages of reactions to system instructions addressing organisation, monitoring and assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Message history • Moodle Reports: Course Participation, Activity Completion • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	
Scales or surveys identifying self-regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grader report • Available progress bar and reports • Manual Descriptive Statistics 	

EXPERIMENTATION

- Inferential statistics (e.g., analysis of variance and covariance) to compare self-regulation scale levels and final grades, considering activity views, elapsed time, or opinions on self-regulation support activities as covariates.

DEVELOPMENT

- Application of neural network models to identify self-regulated behaviours, followed by personalized recognition or motivational messages.

In a study conducted by the University of Barcelona (Raffaghelli, 2023) a group of 23 professors was invited to explore Moodle data applications to assess the feasibility of implementing a learning analytics system. Over a period of four months, participants engaged in reflective work, instrument exploration, and collaborative discussions through weekly videoconference meetings. In the final phase, six teachers presented their approaches to working with data, showcasing diverse strategies:

- Integrating multiple data sources to assess the effectiveness of a problem-based learning strategy.
- Designing adaptive messaging systems, where messages were tailored to different student groupings based on their risk level identified in previous cohorts.
- Implementing automated question selection, ensuring progression based on student performance levels.
- Personalizing motivational messages, automatically adapting them to students' self-regulation strategies.

While some participants focused on practical applications, others concentrated on understanding the pedagogical challenges associated with learning analytics. A shared observation was that pre-configured analytics tools often simplify classroom complexity, requiring careful interpretation alongside teaching experience. Additionally, while privacy considerations were discussed early on, addressing them within a structured framework remained a challenge.

Despite these concerns, there was a collective willingness to integrate data-informed insights into teaching and learning practices. However, key questions emerged: Who else has access to this data? How aware are students of their digital footprint? How can institutions balance data collection without overwhelming learners with excessive interactions? The participants highlighted the importance of responsible and transparent data to enhance, rather than replace, the human-centered nature of education.

Following this case, we will observe another approach to the classification of analytics. Knight and colleagues (2014) worked on a distinction between the types of analytics not according to the types of possible operations, but rather based on pedagogical approaches. They thus determined six approaches, that can again address the relationship between educational data collection and usage.

The first approach is the “Transactional or instructional” in which learning is based on the transfer of knowledge from the knower (teacher) to the learner (student). Such an approach is characterized by an assessment perspective in which success is assessable by the degree of correspondence between the statements made by the students and the content they have been taught. This is the approach traditionally adopted in universities, and the technological ease with which they can be automatically assessed is the basis of their current predominance. The design of analytics tends to focus on simple metrics, such as exam scores, and does not require a deeper analysis of more complex artifacts, or of the processes by which they were obtained. The case study for preventing dropouts that we have introduced before could fit into this framework.

We follow with the “Constructivist approach”, focusing on the forms of learning that occur in the student’s guided exploration towards experimentation with the world. These models usually measure success based on the quality of the construction process or artifacts generated by the students. The design of the analytics will focus on progress, by monitoring and evaluating modifications made to a set of materials, resources or tools selected and organized by the educator. An example of analytics in this tradition would be the monitoring of the evolution of digital artifacts within the Scratch visual programming environment and community (Maloney et al., 2010) or the work of progress analysis in collaborative discussions developed by Cerro Martínez and collaborators (Cerro Martínez et al., 2020) . We observed that in these cases, the focus is on classifying behaviours that indicate progress in a process (building objects with Scratch, elements that indicate collaboration in a debate) and in any case they require prior labelling to then produce visualizations that “show” students and teachers the success of the construction process.

According to the Cerro-Martínez study, teachers were not aware or needed hard work of reading and annotating to be able to distinguish whether the collaborative process in a forum was effective. Through a visualization system based on the construction of a sociogram and the automatic identification of key elements of the debate, graphs and word clouds were generated, as well as statistics on levels of individual and group participation. The teachers who were able to experience this system found it effective in transmitting to them the effectiveness of the collaborative process, helping when it came to systematically intervening in the groups with the most problems.

We move now to the subjectivist approach, which focuses emotional and affective support in the pedagogical relationship. According to this approach, the abundance of information prevents participants of a learning process to select the best solution. Therefore, responding to a challenge is already a relevant focus to promote significant learning. Besides, individual or group reflections along activities, especially considering transformation processes improve skills like team working or entrepreneurship. The design of analytics will focus, in these cases, on providing feedback that motivates students to continue working; to understand whether someone is getting involved in a reflective process; or whether they are working in depth on self-assessment or peer assessment. Examples of this type of approach are the semantic marking of emotional processes, the so-called *sentiment analysis* together with textual analysis approaches that trigger actions or work suggestions for students. For example, Saucerman and colleagues generated a scheme to automate the detection of reflective processes led to “expert” actions to then apply it to problem solving with university students (Saucerman et al., 2017) . Or also Crossley and colleagues developed a model based on natural language processing to understand the subjective approach to mathematics or “mathematical identity” that predisposes to good or bad learning of it (Crossley et al., 2020) .

Born in the 90s, the community of practice approach spread to online learning activities particularly in the case of professional learning. From this perspective, success consists of “being part of” a certain group, moving from the peripheral area of a community (participants that are novice in the type of knowledge cultivated by the community) to the centre (participants that are experts). The analytics hence focus on the classification of expert and novice users, and on the transition from novice’s position to that of expert. Analytics are based on exploring behavioural markers, signalling expertise. The work of identifying learning variables in gaming environments has been an important first step (since the objective is, within the same gaming environment, to move from being novice to become expert). In that sense it is possible to mark, quantify and represent (even with badges) the degree to which participants demonstrate behaviours valued in a gaming community. Going one step further, epistemic network analysis has made contributions to understanding the connections between cognition, social aspects of behaviour and interaction in gaming environments and then transferring this approach to learning environments (Shaffer et al., 2016) .

Following with the fifth approach, we consider now Connectivism. From this perspective, learning involves understanding how to connect ideas effectively and knowing where to find the necessary information to do so. The act of knowing is the ability to activate and interlink networks of knowledge, whether these networks consist of information objects or people. Connectivist approaches leverage social network analysis to examine the structure and flow of information among individuals, focusing on how learners build and maintain connections. Learning analytics, in this context, can assess the size, quality, and evolution of knowledge networks over time, providing insights into effective learning processes. Additionally, analytics can help identify key sources for strengthening these networks, whether

human or posthuman, fostering deeper engagement and knowledge integration.. (Markauskaite et al., 2022; Nijland et al., 2018) .

Finally, we can consider the pragmatic and sociocultural approach. Building on Dewey's perspective, knowledge is understood as being inherently linked to its practical application. From this viewpoint, the effectiveness of a pedagogical process depends on how useful and applicable the information provided in a course is for students. This process is mediated by cultural and contextual factors, shaping how learners engage with knowledge. Sociocultural approaches emphasize the role of reflection in learning, encouraging students to analyse their own interactions and information-processing strategies in relation to their personal and academic contexts. Learning analytics within this framework support the mutual exchange of perspectives, particularly in collaborative learning and discourse analysis. For instance, as highlighted in Cerro-Martínez's work, analytics can facilitate collaborative information-seeking tasks and enhance student empowerment in group settings. An example of this is the BLINC tool (Worsley et al., 2021) , which identifies seven key dimensions that influence students' experiences in teamwork: a) The work environment; b) Compatibility among peers; c) The effectiveness of communication; d) The emergence of conflicts; e) The pressure from work contexts; f) The levels of individual contribution; g) The constructiveness of the overall process.

Analytics within this approach extend beyond digital learning environments, incorporating multimodal data sources that capture real-world group interactions. These may include biometric data, facial and eye-tracking technologies, and in-class behavioural analytics, providing a more comprehensive view of how students engage, collaborate, and develop their skills in diverse learning contexts.

In the following paragraph, we will move beyond the mere description of classifications. By introducing some scenario-cases of LA usage in order to support design-thinking.

Scenarios: imagining Learning Analytics in action

Scenario I - Improving Course Design

Scenario. There are challenges related to student motivation for deep and critical learning. Many students submit low-quality or unoriginal final assignments just to pass the course. The class size is very large (about 150 students per semester), making direct student-teacher interaction difficult. The goal is to redesign an exam and final assignment to better assess learning depth and prevent plagiarism.

Context. Pedro is an informatics professor. His students have an average academic maturity, and he works with a well-established teaching team that agrees on implementing a design that includes peer-learning approach with a final written exam.

Proposed Strategies

- Implement sequences of joint collaboration to solve problems including progressive tests with automated feedback.
- Use badges to highlight top-quality work and showcase anonymized exemplary assignments by couples of peer-learners.
- Track students' progressive grades and group them based on positive peer' interactions.

- Analyse participation levels in a gamified system, considering the badges earned, the levels of positive engagement in peer-learning and the relationship with the final achievements at the final written exam. in relation to progress and the final assignment.
- Consider whether the peer-learning has supported students' achievements.

Scenario II - Analysing Teaching Effectiveness

Scenario. The goal is to better understand the effectiveness of a digital cataloguing system used for instructional purposes.

Context. Elsa is a digital humanities professor working with a small, advanced group of final-year undergraduate students. She collaborates with two colleagues to implement a new system for cataloguing digital objects using a 3D repository accessible via virtual reality. Students are highly motivated and eager to engage with this innovative approach. However, by mid-course, Elsa is unsure whether students are fully engaging with the 3D system, as complaints have arisen, and mid-term exam results have been unsatisfactory.

Proposed Strategies:

- Use views, participation and completion to understand students' engagement with the cataloguing system.
- Implement structured surveys to evaluate students' experiences with the 3D cataloguing tool.
- Discuss results with students to adjust the approach as needed.

Scenario III - Preventing Dropout

Scenario. The instructor is seeking to reduce dropout rates, especially after students take their first partial exam.

Context. Meritxell is a Physics professor teaching first-year engineering students. Many of her students are new to university learning, and she works with four teaching assistants to deliver the course to approximately 600 students per semester. Historically, 50% of students disengage after the first exam, prompting the need for an early intervention strategy.

Proposed Strategies:

- Use students' response systems to learn where epistemic errors appear and to explore the students' intuitive understanding of physic phenomena.
- Complement classroom activities with active video lessons divided into four phases, each with accompanying questions.
- Review these questions in class, facilitating group discussions before instructor explanations.
- Send automated messages to students who do not complete the video lessons and exercises.
- Encourage peer emotional support, allowing partners to flag issues in joint work when one student fails to engage.
- Evaluate jointly with the students the factors that influence their learning success or failure, jointly analysing errors, difficult items and key success stories in groups.

Scenario IV - Enhancing Student Autonomy

Scenario. The course aims to develop students' self-regulation skills to prepare them for professional practice.

Context. Josep is a Social Education professor, teaching students at the midpoint of their degree. His students have some established academic habits and behaviours influenced by faculty norms and past experiences. As students approach practical training, they experience high stress and feelings of being overwhelmed by the combination of academic tasks and apprenticeship. The goal is to help them discover their creative strengths and develop an identity as professionals through self-regulation skills.

Proposed Strategies:

- Use student satisfaction surveys to assess progress.
- Encourage manual completion of activities to promote self-discipline.
- Implement a scoring system that tracks the acquisition of transversal skills through partial group projects and collaborative tasks.
- Encourage students to compare their progress using Student Dashboards and Instructor Dashboards to reflect on their learning journey.

Cases of usage

Open University of UK

The Open University UK has extensively explored data-driven practices through a strong research-based approach, leveraging its fully online structure to assess the feasibility of data extraction and analysis in higher education.

The institution adopts both data to enhance student learning experiences and the promotion of open access to educational resources.

As for the open data initiatives, the Open University Learning Analytics Dataset (OULAD) demonstrates commitment to open data. The repository includes anonymized data from 22 courses and over 32,000 students. This dataset encompasses demographic information, assessment results, and logs of interactions with the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), supporting research in educational data mining and learning analytics. The open dataset is being currently used in settings like teaching and modelling data.

As for the Learning Analytics Initiatives²¹, the OU implements data-driven student support. Specifically, learning analytics to monitor student engagement and performance are integrated into the Virtual Learning Environment. By analysing data such as assignment submissions and online activity, the university aims at proactively offer personalized support to students, aiming to improve retention and success rates. Also, the students' point of view is considered to evaluate the quality of teaching. The university clearly states their policies for the ethical use of students' data.

Educational data is adopted as said for research and development: The OU's Institute of Educational Technology²² leads research in learning analytics and learning design. This program investigates how data can inform course design and teaching practices, ultimately enhancing student outcomes.

²¹ <https://help.open.ac.uk/learning-analytics>

²² <https://iet.open.ac.uk/research/programmes/learning-analytics-and-learning-design>

Trends

Figure 11 Teacher dashboard at the Open University of UK (Herodotou et al., 2019)

Some interesting, mapped projects can exemplify the approach to open data.

Open Dashboard on MOOCs data. Led by K. Jordan (2015), the research collected and aggregated open data from 221 courses, from which the author created an interactive data visualisation (<http://www.katyjordan.com/MOOCproject.html>) which combines completion rates (%) with assessment type. The user can respond to several questions (How big is a MOOC? How many students complete a MOOC? Which is the relationship between completion rates and the assessment type?)

Therefore, the open data has been transformed to yield a visualisation that the users can engage with. The data has not been updated since June 2015, however, it is a relevant example of large datasets aggregation and sharing that allow the user to understand the nature of a MOOC.

Open Essayist, developed by the Open University UK (OOUK), is an automated writing analysis tool that provides real-time reflective feedback on students' draft assignments (Whitelock et al., 2015). It leverages text-mining and quantitative text analysis to evaluate the structure, coherence, and semantic density of academic writing. Through automated responses, students receive insights that guide them in refining their vocabulary, argumentation, and organization of ideas. The tool also includes interactive dashboards,

allowing students to visualize patterns in their writing, track improvements, and self-regulate their learning process. The pedagogical hypothesis behind Open Essayist is that academic writing is an iterative and reflective process, where feedback fosters vocabulary enrichment and stronger argumentative skills.

Longitudinal study on learning analytics impact. Similarly, the learning analytics have been studied for its impact on teaching practices and student engagement. A three-year mixed-methods study involving 59 educators (Herodotou et al., 2019b) explored how teachers perceive learning analytics tools and their effect on at-risk students' behaviour. Findings suggest that positive teacher perceptions about learning analytics contribute to better student engagement and reduced dropout risks. These insights highlight the importance of teacher adoption and belief in learning analytics, reinforcing the potential of tools like Open Essayist to improve student success. The fig. 9 displays the LA interface adopted in Herodotou et al. study (2019).

Universitat Oberta de Catalunya

This fully online university has built several projects over their owned data lakes or the “Datamart”²³. The projects include strategic reports that display learners’ competences, supports learners self-paced learning and address the dialogue with companies and external institutions about professional development. We will mention here PINBALL, an intelligent learning analytics tool that provides automatic alerts based on a predictive system. The tool helps students reorganize their study strategies by offering personalized feedback derived from student data, including enrolment in assignments, study trajectory, participation speed, resource usage, and performance in initial assessments. Using an algorithm specifically designed by UOC, PINBALL identifies potential learning challenges early and provides real-time guidance to encourage self-regulated learning. Additionally, students have access to tutorials and dashboards, allowing them to visualize their progress, interact with their results, and engage with instructors for further support. The pedagogical hypothesis behind PINBALL is that self-regulation improves when students receive timely insights into their learning difficulties, enabling proactive adjustments (Bañeres Besora et al., 2021)

²³ <https://www.uoc.edu/portal/en/elearning-innovation-center/learning-analytics/index.html>

Students of the classroom													
User	Name	Last login	Consent signed	CAA1		FP1		FP2		CAA2		PF3	
				Prediction	Grade								
Uso de bases de datos aula 1													
		08/06/2020	Yes - 08/03/2020	Yellow	Z B	Yellow	Z Cm	Red	Z Cn	Black	Z N	Red	B Cn
		25/05/2020	No	Yellow	N B	Green	N A	Green	N B	Green	N A	Green	N N
		08/06/2020	No	Yellow	N A	Green	N N						
		03/06/2020	Yes - 28/02/2020	Yellow	N A	Green	N A						
		21/04/2020	Yes - 03/03/2020	Black	A N	Black	Z N	Black	A N	Black	A N	Black	B N
		04/04/2020	Yes - 29/02/2020	Yellow	N B	White	N						
		07/06/2020	No	Yellow	N B	Green	N A						
		28/05/2020	Yes - 28/02/2020	Yellow	Cm Cm	Red	Cm D	Black	Cm N	Black	B N	Black	Cm N
		23/05/2020	No	Yellow	D Cm	Green	D B	Green	N Cm	Green	N B	Green	N N

Figure 12 The PINBALL learners' dashboard (Bañeres Besora et al., 2021)

The University of Florence

The University of Florence, a traditional university using blended learning approaches, conducted a research study to explore diagnostic analytics in an online self-study teacher development program for e-learning. The primary objective was to examine how well the program's design objectives aligned with users' preferences and engagement patterns (Ranieri et al., 2018)

The research applied ad hoc diagnostic analytics, leveraging data extraction from Moodle through an interoperable database (RDBMS MySQL). The study variables were structured as follows:

1. X0: Course Design Levels

- Categorized based on the complexity of Moodle resources and modules used by participants.
- Ranged from "Null" (no course opened) to "Highly Advanced" (comprehensive use of Moodle tools, including badges, assessment modules, and restricted access settings).

2. X1: Course Module Types

Classified into five categories that displayed the users' preferences for the Module types. The modules introduced the theory of eLearning:

- Enter (basic access resources)
- Cont_Supp (content support)
- Wrap-Around (integrated resources)
- Collaborative (interactive learning)
- Equal_Pref (balanced use of all module types)

3. X2: Learning Units (LUs) Categorization

Based on Bloom's taxonomy, this variable explored the types of learning goals covered by the teachers in their Moodle courses:

- Know (basic knowledge acquisition)
- Understand (conceptual understanding)
- Apply (practical application)
- Experiment (exploratory learning)
- Equal-Pref (balanced learning approach)
- Data Extraction and Analysis

Therefore, the study analysed participant engagement through:

- Platform Logs & User Participation – Tracking course access, module interactions, and learning unit preferences.
- Module & Learning Unit Completion Rates – Measuring total engagement and completion per category.
- User Activity Coding & Summary Tables – Identifying patterns in user interaction and module selection.

The study revealed that usage patterns varied significantly based on participants' experience levels and motivation. More experienced and motivated users engaged with a wider range of course modules and learning units, opting for collaborative and experimental approaches. Instead, less experienced users preferred basic course designs, focusing on content support and structured resources. The self-paced, process-based learning design approach was confirmed as effective, supporting a diverse range of user preferences and teaching strategies.

To wrap up, the study highlighted the possibilities of analysis led by the university's Moodle platform databases queried through a system internally developed. By integrating learning analytics, the institution analysed the whole engagement with eLearning in all its possibilities (as a more traditional content-based delivery, or through more complex collaborative approaches). Through these means, the university was able of adapting online programs to better align with teachers' skills, preferences, and engagement levels, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of faculty development programs.

In the following we will also introduce cases based on commercial platforms, aiming at displaying different settings and approaches to data extraction and usage.

Moodle IntelliBoard

The IntelliBoard™ Dashboard²⁴ is a learning analytics tool designed for Moodle, offering distinct visualizations for administrators, teachers, and students. It provides data-driven insights to identify at-risk students, monitor their success and progress, and track key performance indicators such as student status summaries, assignment completion rates, and course averages. For students, IntelliBoard™ promotes self-management by enabling them to compare course progress, track assignment completion, monitor activity participation, and analyse final grades in relation to engagement levels. With these

²⁴ https://moodle.org/plugins/local_intelliboard

features, the tool facilitates data-informed decision-making, improving teaching strategies, student support, and institutional oversight.

Some cases of usage are:

Rhodes University. Located in South Africa, Rhodes University faced challenges transitioning to online learning during the pandemic. By integrating IntelliBoard with their Moodle LMS, they could efficiently track student engagement through user status and access reports. This data allowed them to analyse student behaviour and engagement metrics, informing their pedagogical strategies.

Loyola University Maryland. Loyola University aimed to increase participation among instructors and learners and to supplement strategic decision-making. Utilizing IntelliBoard, deans and department chairs could correlate engagement levels with course delivery methods. This insight enabled them to determine which delivery methods—such as hybrid, online, synchronous, or asynchronous—yielded the best results for student success.

Haywood Community College. Haywood Community College in North Carolina needed a more efficient method for compiling crucial census data. By adopting IntelliBoard Pro, they streamlined the process of building customized reports, significantly reducing the administrative burden on instructors and allowing the registrar's office to pull data on demand.

These cases illustrate how IntelliBoard's learning analytics platform was applied to student engagement, inform strategic decisions, and streamline administrative processes in higher education institutions.

APEREO

The Apereo Learning Analytics Initiative (LAI) is a collaborative effort within the Apereo Foundation that focuses on developing scalable, open-source learning analytics tools for educational institutions. The initiative aims to create a suite of tested tools that can be adopted and adapted across various educational contexts, particularly in the UK and USA. A key component of this initiative is Shuhari²⁵, a set of software components designed to help institutions embark on their learning analytics journey with a solid foundation and minimal investment. Shuhari includes tools like OpenLRW, a standards-based learning record warehouse, and OpenDashboard, which provides data visualizations to support teaching and learning.

The pedagogical hypothesis underpinning the LAI is that positive results and best practices identified within one institution can serve as a foundation for broader adoption and scalability across the educational system. By involving educators who have tested these tools and activities, the initiative seeks to foster a community of practice that shares insights and strategies for effective implementation.

Through this collaborative approach, the Apereo LAI aims to enhance the educational experience by providing institutions with the tools and knowledge necessary to implement effective learning analytics solutions.

²⁵ <https://github.com/apereo-learning-analytics-initiative>

A notable case is the Marist College in Poughkeepsie, New York. This institution has collaborated with the Apereo Foundation to develop an open-source learning analytics platform aimed at improving student retention and success. The initiative focused on creating scalable analytics tools that could be adapted across various educational contexts. Apereo's learning analytics components, including the Open Learning Record Warehouse (OpenLRW) and OpenDashboard were integrated into the college's existing systems. These tools allowed for the collection, storage, and analysis of student data from multiple sources, providing educators with actionable insights.

By utilizing these analytics tools, Marist College was able to identify at-risk students early and implement targeted interventions. The data-driven approach facilitated timely support, contributing to improved student outcomes and retention rates.

Knewton “Alta” (in partnership with Pearson)²⁶

Knewton Alta, developed in partnership with Pearson, is an adaptive learning platform designed for secondary and university-level education. It leverages advanced algorithms to analyse student behaviours and learning outcomes, providing personalised guidance throughout the learning process.

At its core, Knewton Alta captures student interactions with educational content, assessing their performance on specific topics. Based on real-time data, the platform generates automatic feedback and tailors activity recommendations to enhance learning. These recommendations may include participating in discussion forums, earning rewards through gamified structures, or engaging in targeted exercises to strengthen weaker areas.

The pedagogical hypothesis behind Knewton Alta is that students adjust their learning objectives based on micro-actions that reflect their performance levels. By providing continuous, data-driven feedback, the platform encourages self-regulated learning, helping students identify gaps, set personalized goals, and optimize their study strategies.

A case of use is the Calculus I course at the University of Texas Rio Grande Valley (UTRGV). The course is delivered at the UTRGV multi-campus of the public university with over 25,000 undergraduate students, 89% of whom are Hispanic, and 58% are first-generation college students. The institution aimed to improve student success rates in Calculus I, a prerequisite for degrees in engineering, computer science, and physics. Prior to course revisions, Hispanic students had a 57% pass rate (grade C or better) in this course. To enhance learning outcomes, UTRGV's School of Mathematical and Statistical Sciences undertook several initiatives:

- **Course Coordination:** Established a community of practice among instructors to standardize assessments and align learning objectives across multiple sections.
- **Evidence-Based Instructional Practices:** Introduced collaborative problem-solving sessions, tutoring led by learning assistants, and developed an interactive calculus webpage.
- **Adaptive Learning Technology:** Integrated Knewton Alta, an adaptive courseware, to provide personalized learning experiences tailored to individual student needs.

²⁶ <https://www.knewton.com/>

Within three years of implementing these changes, the success rate for Hispanic students in Calculus I increased to 74%. The adaptive features of Knewton Alta played a significant role in this improvement by offering customized learning paths and immediate feedback, thereby enhancing student engagement and understanding.

Recommendations for Teaching Practice

In the following, we will introduce potential activities to be implemented by practitioners, from early stages of data usage to more advanced approaches to data.

Designing a Data-Informed Learning Activity Using Moodle Analytics

Description

The goal of this activity is to leverage learning analytics from the widespread open-source Moodle to enhance instructional design and improve teaching and learning outcomes. By utilising data traces available in Moodle, educators can gain insights into teaching and learning challenges, instructional effectiveness, student performance, and self-regulation strategies.

The activity follows a data-driven instructional design cycle, using student-generated data from Moodle to inform pedagogical decisions. The activity can be carried out in five steps.

Step 1: Identify a Teaching or Learning Problem. Choose a recurring challenge observed in the learning process (e.g., low student engagement, poor quiz performance, or inconsistent participation in forums). Define hence a research question based on the problem. Example:

“How does forum participation correlate with quiz performance in an online course?”

Step 2: Select Data from Moodle Analytics. Use at least one data generation criterion from Moodle, such as:

- Forum interactions (number of posts, replies, discussion engagement).
- Assignment submissions (timeliness, completeness).
- Quiz attempts and scores (initial attempts vs. final results).
- Time spent on learning resources (video views, document downloads).

Step 3: Design and Implement the Activity. Develop an interactive task in Moodle that requires active engagement, such as:

- A forum discussion where students must respond to peers before completing a related quiz.
- A self-paced learning module with progress tracking and self-reflection prompts.
- A gamified assignment where students earn digital badges based on task completion.

Step 4: Monitor and Analyze the Data. Use Moodle analytics tools to track student behaviors:

- Completion tracking to observe participation rates.
- Progress bars to assess learning engagement.
- Correlation analysis between forum activity and quiz scores.
- Self-assessment surveys to measure students' perception of their learning.

Step 5: Reflect on the Impact and Make Adjustments

- For teachers: Identify how analytics data informs teaching effectiveness and helps refine instructional design.
- For students: Evaluate how analytics influence self-regulation and performance improvement.
- For institutional learning: Consider how this activity could be scaled or adapted for broader application.

Resources

- Institutional Learning Analytics Tools (Moodle Dashboard, IntelliBoard, Open Analytics Tools)²⁷.
- SOLAR. Society for Learning analytics research²⁸
- Nguyen, Rienties & Toetenel (2017): *Mixing and Matching Learning Design and Learning Analytics*. Springer.

Reflection Question for educators

What data from digital learning environments can be effectively, ethically, and economically used to support teaching decisions?

Data to Promote Learning to Learn

Description

The primary aim of this initiative is formative—to enhance students' pedagogical data literacy and empower them to engage in self-regulated and self-directed learning. By integrating learning analytics, students can gain insights into their learning patterns, track their progress, and make informed decisions to optimize their educational experiences.

To achieve this objective, several activities are suggested.

Introduction to Learning Tools. At the beginning of a learning cycle, students should be introduced to digital tools such as dashboards, system alerts, or tracking mechanisms that help them understand their own learning behaviours. These tools can provide students with data on their engagement levels, progress, and areas needing improvement.

²⁷ <https://moodle.com/functionality-with-moodle/learning-analytics-for-moodle/>

²⁸ <https://www.solaresearch.org/>

Monitoring Learning Behaviour. A key step is generating monitoring events that capture student interactions with the learning tools. These events help analyze how frequently students engage with the tools and how effectively they use them for self-regulated learning.

Reflective Discussion and Feedback. Students should share their experiences using these tools in a structured discussion. Teachers can document key insights and provide corrective instructions to help students refine their learning strategies.

Comparative Analysis of Student Performance. By comparing scores and behavioural patterns between a previous group and a current group of students, educators can assess the effectiveness of interventions and identify best practices for improving learning outcomes.

Resources

To support the implementation of learning analytics in self-regulated learning, two key academic resources are recommended:

- Winne (2018): Learning Analytics for Self-Regulated Learning – This study explores the role of learning analytics in helping students develop autonomy in their learning processes. (DOI: 10.18608/hla17.021)
- Groba et al. (2014): Using a Learning Analytics Tool for Evaluation in Self-Regulated Learning – This research examines how data-driven tools can be used to assess and enhance self-regulation in learning. (DOI: 10.1109/FIE.2014.7044400)

Reflection Questions for educators

A crucial question to address in designing such an approach is:

"What aspects of learning data manipulation might be relevant for my students?"

This encourages educators to critically evaluate how data is collected, interpreted, and used to inform teaching and learning strategies.

Data to support Reflection on the Quality of Learning

Description

This initiative seeks to promote critical awareness in students regarding the data generated throughout their teaching and learning experiences. The goal is to help students analyse the quality of education they receive by engaging them in discussions about learning analytics, instructional design, and assessment metrics.

To foster this awareness, several activities are proposed:

Explaining Learning Dashboards. Firstly, introduce students to learning dashboards, explaining how they function and how they provide insights into learning behaviours. Hence, highlight the key metrics displayed and how they can be interpreted to reflect educational progress.

Presenting Analytical Instruments. Showcase the available data collection tools and explain how teachers use them to monitor learning progress. Open to a debate on the purpose and limitations of these instruments in educational evaluation.

Reflecting on Instructional Design and Metrics. Engage students in discussions about instructional design and assessment metrics, including what is measured and what aspects of learning might be left unmeasured but still valuable. Through this activity, promote students' critical thinking about the incompleteness and biases of educational data. Include discussions about the ethical implications and privacy concerns of sharing learning data.

Adjusting Design Based on Student Feedback. Whenever possible, adapt learning analytics tools and instructional approaches based on student input. Foster a participatory culture where students contribute to refining the evaluation process.

Analysing Learning Experiences Over Time. At the end of a learning period, guide students in analysing their own data to identify patterns, strengths, and areas for improvement. It is also important to encourage students to share their experiences using learning analytics tools and how they influenced their learning.

Collecting Opinions on Student Evaluation of Teaching. Finally, gather feedback from students on the effectiveness and relevance of analytics-based evaluation tools.

Resources

For deeper engagement with the ethics and practical applications of learning analytics, the following resources are recommended:

- Slade, S. & Tait, A. (2019). Global guidelines: Ethics in Learning Analytics. International Council for Open and Distance Education
- Whitelock-Wainwright, A., Gašević, D., & Tejeiro, R. (2017, March). What do students want? Towards an instrument for students' evaluation of quality of learning analytics services. Published in the Proceedings of the Seventh International Learning Analytics & Knowledge Conference, LAK '17, pp. 368-372. DOI: 10.1145/3027385.3027419.

Reflection Question for educators

An essential question to consider is:

"What data and analytics systems could be shared and discussed with students to analyse the quality of the educational process?"

This encourages educators to reflect on how to make learning analytics transparent, participatory, and beneficial for students.

Conclusions

In general, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have focused on developments such as those we have mentioned, considering that at the university level, students are connected in a massive and continuous way, much more intensively than at any other level or learning situation, both through LMS (*Learning management system*) adopted as a basis for the virtual campus, such as the use of digital repositories of text and video, as well as personal data collected around the student's career for administrative purposes. However, and as has emerged from the cases presented here, the current state of development shows little progress in the adoption of analytics, raising concerns about the authentic validation and scalability of technologies such as predictive learning analytics and learning dashboards (Tsai and Gašević, 2017; Viberg et al., 2018). Furthermore, ethical issues of data use are not sufficiently considered to build institutional policies that integrate learning analytics as part of quality education model (Guitert Catasús et al., 2024).

In literature, the theoretical and empirical reliability of various technologies remains a persistent issue. While the lack of authentic validation contexts raises concerns about empirical consistency, perhaps more alarming are the theoretical, political, and ethical challenges surrounding data aggregation, modeling, and visualization. Additionally, data collection often occurs in contexts where students are unaware of the nature and extent of the data being collected, raising ethical concerns about surveillance practices and the trade-offs between personal privacy, individual approaches to quantification, and institutional uses of Big Data (Khalil et al., 2018; Pargman & McGrath, 2021).

All indications suggest that the widespread adoption of analytics has yet to move beyond the development niche. Innovation appears stagnant in the developmental phase, preventing it from becoming a widely used service in higher education institutions (HEIs). Consequently, large-scale evaluations of its effectiveness do not abound (Herodotou et al., 2020). Even less can we expect to find high-quality approaches that incorporate principles of equity and social justice (Pargman & McGrath, 2021). Not only is the technology underdeveloped, limiting its practical application in daily teaching, but numerous ethical, social, and political questions remain unresolved, keeping analytics in an uncertain and ambiguous state.

Early in 2013 Siemens, Dawson, and Lynch (Siemens et al., 2013) had imagined the integration of learning analytics within a quality framework. Figure 13 presents their vision, outlining a five-phase institutional journey: first, awareness of learning analytics tools, followed by experimentation, professional development for teachers and students, institutional transformation (through the development of an information system for institutional practices), and finally, the transformation of research and academic management based on data. According to the authors, this structured progression enables a reflection on quality, though understood primarily from a linear and productivity-focused perspective. After a decade, we cannot say higher education institutions have reached the highest levels in the process.

However, some more important advances are going to be made from two perspectives.

The first is related to technological development itself, which requires greater experimental activity *in situ* to verify the effectiveness and impact of the instruments made available to users.

Institutional development strategies based in AA

Figure 13 – Higher Education Quality through the implementation of data-driven practices and learning analytics. From Siemens et al., 2013

The second, and more disruptive, is through the strong criticism promoted by social science scholars. Based on these studies, it seems necessary to shape a research and *policy agenda*. *making* about learning analytics from a practical, contextualized and critical perspective (Prinsloo , 2019) . It is also extremely important to give students a voice in participatory designs that take into account decisions about privacy and the usefulness of instruments that are based on the continuous tracing of data (Broughan and Prinsloo , 2020) .

Although the focus of these two strands is not linked to the discussion of quality, it is presented as a debate in an embryonic state on what may later become instruments and strategies for educational quality in higher education.

In fact, according to Broughan and Prinsloo (2020, p. 618)

“Central to much of the research on student success and retention in higher education is a normative acceptance that student attrition and failure are related to deficits in educational background, student attitude, engagement, and ability (...) As higher education institutions increasingly process student data in learning analytics, these learning deficit approaches have the potential to determine not only what data matters and is collected, but also how it is used (...) As always, the methods deployed and the ontological stance adopted will inevitably shape the evidence produced.”

Also, Selwyn (2019) noted some of the key issues that could arise from the misuse of learning analytics and overall students’ data. These revisit and broaden the points discussed above.

The consequences of misusing analytics could include:

- A reduced understanding of education. The phenomena measured by the data collected in the analytics necessarily minimize the complexity of the learning process.
- Ignoring the broader contexts of education. Learning analytics suffers from a lack of understanding of the social dynamics that can make an educational issue important, while detecting and guiding irrelevant micro-behaviour.
- Reducing students' and teachers' capacity for informed decision-making. Systems that provide diagnoses and recommendations run the risk of diminishing users' ability to understand their own cognitive processes and interactions.
- A means of surveillance rather than support. When analytics are used to observe if users' behaviours align with the interests of the business.
- A source of performativity. When measuring systems are invented, users learn to act in ways that "please" the indicators, i.e. they perform for the system.
- Disadvantaging those excluded from the system. When an assessment and recommendation model is based on behaviours seen as desirable for the elite group responsible for programming the system, there is a risk of excluding minorities who do not fit this pattern.
- Serving institutional (rather than individual) interests. When an institution collects mass volumes of data using systems it has developed itself, it has unlimited scope for acting in its own interests following its own models of ethics and professional duty.

Selwyn's proposals to remedy these issues include:

- Giving users the right to inspect. The design of analytics applications that are more open and accessible, giving users genuine control and supervision, better reflecting their real lives.
- Giving users more control over their data. Designing learning analytics systems to inform users of how their data are being used in research and in institutional business models linked to education.
- Rethinking the governance and economy of the learning analytics industry. All the services for visualizing data and recommendation systems linked to learning platforms have the potential for monetizing students' data to produce new dashboards and recommendation services.

This criticism of the principles underlying products based on harvesting students' data brings into question the very existence of the products (such as learning analytics) that they generate. These products are themselves constructed on a failed premise, that of appropriation and commercialization, so it is pointless to debate whether data have been collected with or without consent or participation, if they are later transformed for the benefit of a few. And it must be remembered that all ethical approaches can be criticized as having a fatal flaw: they encourage "whitewashing" practices by businesses, who use recommendations, declarations of adherence to international standards, lists and guidelines to paint a superficial portrait of ethical behaviour (Green, 2021).

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Annex – Literature Review

Understanding Trends about Open Data in Higher Education: A narrative review of the literature.

Method

To delve into the current trends in Open Data in Higher Education as specific topic of interest, studies and research related to the issues of developing a critical communicative approach, we reviewed several studies. Starting from the narrative review of the literature, conducted according to a snowball sampling criterion (Wohlin, 2014), the conceptual nodes will be identified and a reflection on the central thesis of this work will be proposed, namely the relevance of the production and use of open data in the context of higher education.

The narrative review of the literature, considering the keywords related to the definition of open data and the need to investigate into the context of implementation/adoption of open data, namely, higher education. As previously mentioned, the technique adopted is the snowball sampling technique (Figure 2), a non-probabilistic sampling technique typical of qualitative research and, more precisely, the "forward snowballing" approach (Wohlin, 2014, p. 3): Selected the texts, the bibliographic lists were then considered, and the approach was repeated until the same concepts were read in the texts, that is, until the so-called theoretical saturation was reached, a criterion still much debated for its implications in the interruption of data collection and analysis. (Saunders et al., 2018). In the context of narrative research, in fact, it can be considered in terms of a reflection on the "completeness" of a bibliographic account (Saunders et al., 2018).

The databases were queried adopting the following script:

("Open Educational Data" OR "OED" OR "open data") AND ("usage" OR "utilization" OR "use") AND ("Higher Education" OR "universities" OR "colleges" OR "postsecondary education")

Figure 3 reports the workflow.

The exploration of Open Data usage in Higher Education is hence grounded in a comprehensive screening process across major scientific databases, including SCOPUS (389 items), EBSCO-host (40 items), WOS (100 items), and DOAJ (no items), using a search string focused on terms like "Open Educational Data," "usage," "utilization," and "Higher Education." Screening over this initial search 22 papers were selected on SCOPUS and 12 from WOS, forming a foundational group for analysis. Further refinement employed snowball sampling by reading the selected texts (28 items) and analysing relevant references, 11 relevant reports were identified. Also, four (4) relevant websites were analysed and four (4) international reports (grey literature) were considered. The Table A.1 displays the final selection (by database query and by snowballing). To ensure a robust framework, the process reached saturation through categorizing the literature, identifying trends, and reconceptualizing elements for Open Data usage in Higher Education. Key areas explored include framing the concept in context, identifying trends, assessing potential for educational practice and research, and addressing challenges such as data quality, policies, data literacy, privacy, and ethics. This systematic approach underscores the multifaceted nature of Open Data in higher

education, providing insights into its transformative potential and the critical issues that must be addressed to maximize its impact. In the remainder of this section, the trends of Open Data usage in Higher education according to the papers selected will be presented and discussed.

Figure A.1 – Workflow adopted to carry out the narrative review of the literature

Findings

The key findings are listed according to the themes found throughout the classification of articles. Table 1 reports the list of articles analysed and the method adopted for the selection.

Table A.1 - List of Publications Analysed

(full citations and analysis integrated as Open Data in this report, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18608623)

Authors	Year	Selected
Behrang, F; Orso, A	2018	DB-query
Bir, DD; Ahn, B	2019	DB-query
Bradberry, C; Pittges, J	2020	DB-query
Butuner, R; Calp, MH	2022	DB-query
Cantador I.; Criado J.I.; Muñoz L.A.; Cortés-Cediel M.E.; Liarte I.	2023	DB-query
Chockkalingam, S; Yu, R; Pardos, ZA	2021	DB-query
Dorodchi M.; Al-Hossami E.; Benedict A.; Demeter E.	2019	DB-query
Feng J.; Zhao Y.	2021	DB-query

Guo J.	2021	DB-query
Hadavand, A; Muschelli, J; Leek, J	2019	DB-query
Howard, E; Cronin, A	2022	DB-query
Krumova M.	2017	DB-query
Kumar, G; Singh, A; Sharma, A	2023	DB-query
Lohse, JJ; McManus, CA; Joyner, DA	2019	DB-query
Mareca, P; Bordel, B	2019	DB-query
Osorio-Sanabria M.A.; Amaya-Fernández F.; González-Zabala M.P.	2020	DB-query
Panagiotakopoulos, T; Kotsiantis, S; Kostopoulos, G; Iatrellis, O; Kameas, A	2021	DB-query
Paneque M.; Roldán-García M.D.M.; García-Nieto J.	2023	DB-query
Perez-Vergara, K; Li, KC	2018	DB-query
Pukach P.; Liubinskyi B.; Hladun V.; Holdovanskyi V.	2024	DB-query
Roda-Sanchez L.; Cirillo F.; Solmaz G.; Jacobs T.; Garrido-Hidalgo C.; Olivares T.; Kovacs E.	2024	DB-query
Silva C.; Belo O.	2018	DB-query
Taganov A.I.; Kolesenkov A.N.; Perepelkin D.A.; Zhuravlev D.S.	2017	DB-query
Umer R.; Khan S.; Ren J.; Umer S.; Shaukat A.	2022	DB-query
Victorino M.; Magalhaes H.; Cardoso L.; Holanda M.; Ishikawa E.	2017	DB-query
Wang, YQ	2018	DB-query
Si L.; Liu X.	2024	DB-query
Toffolin L.	2024	DB-query
Dai, W., Zhou, Y., Zhang, C., Zhang, H.	2024	Snowballing
Dermentzi, E., Zotou, M., Tambouris, E., Tarabanis, K.	2022	snowballing
Dorodchi, M.; Al-Hossami, E.; Benedict, A.; Demeter, E.	2019	Snowballing
Dymora, P.; Mazurek, M.; Kowal, B.	2018	Snowballing
Evans, M.O.	2021	Snowballing
González, Y.M., Rodríguez, C.T., Pascua, J.C.T., Rodríguez, A.I., Martín, A.H.	2023	Snowballing
Kijanovic, S.; Komosar, A.	2023	Snowballing
Kuzilek, J., Hlosta, M., Zdrahal, Z.	2017	Snowballing
Li, A.W., Sinnamon, L.S., Kopak, R.	2022	Snowballing
McNicol, T.; Carthouser, B.; Bongiovanni, I.; Abeysooriya, S.	2024	Snowballing
Rivas-Rebaque, B., Gêrtrudix-Barrio, F., De Britto, J.C.D.C.	2019	Snowballing
Rodrigues, D., Regio, M.S., Musse, S.R., Manssour, I.H.	2021	Snowballing
Rodriguez-F, I. E.; Arcos-Medina, G.; Pástor, D.; Oñate, A.; Gómez, O. S.	2021	Snowballing
Šalamon, D., Blašković, L., Džidić, A., Varga, F., Seljan, S., Bosnić, I.	2024	Snowballing
Szász, B., Fleiner, R., Micsik, A.	2017	Snowballing
Valluru, S.L., Srivastava, B., Paladi, S.T., Yan, S., Natarajan, S.	2024	Snowballing
Zhu, Y. J.; Freund, L.	2020	Snowballing

Reports

European Schoolnet (Editors: Andronikidis, K.; Wastiau, P.)	2023	Snowballing
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Robert, J.	2024	Snowballing
Knyazeva, S., Pushkareva, E.	2023	Snowballing
Knyazeva, S., Jumani N.B, Kapelyushnik, D., Pushkareva, E.	2022	Snowballing

Portals
https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis
https://www.universidata.es/
https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/datastories/open-education-data-european-data-portal
https://data.europa.eu/en/news-events/news/fostering-fair-education-open-data
https://openeducationanalytics.org/get-started/

Total DB-Query	36
Total Snowballing	17
Total Reports	4
Total Portals	4

In the following, the publications are aggregated under relevant themes.

Data sources for open data

In the final selection of 28 articles, we observe that a diverse range of data sources is used in the selected studies, with the most prominent being HE grey data, accounting for 25% of articles, followed by MOOCs data at 16.67% and Grey ODHE data at 11.11%. Smaller contributions include categories like OGD/ORD and public information, each representing 5.56% or less. A closer look at examples highlights the focus of these studies. For instance, an article titled “*e-LION: Data integration semantic model to enhance HE data usability*” explores how learning management systems and semantic models can improve the accessibility and usability of higher education data. Similarly, another study, “*Prediction of students’ failure using VLE and data mining*,” examines the application of predictive models to identify at-risk students, leveraging data from virtual learning environments. In the category of Grey ODHE data, an article titled “*Using Synthetic Data Generators to Promote Open Education*” delves into how synthetic data can be employed to protect privacy while enhancing the usability of data in open educational platforms. These examples illustrate the varied ways data sources are utilized to address critical challenges in education, from improving data accessibility and usability to developing predictive analytics and safeguarding privacy in data sharing.

Zhu & Freund (2020) explored cases of Open Data in Higher education, through a semi-structured environmental scan seeking information on university data sharing practices and open data initiatives. The sample was made of 36 units from major research universities in Canada, and major universities in the US, UK and Australia based on their rankings in the 2018 QS rankings. Authors point out that open data initiatives are driven mainly in the context of open science and open government, but integrate specifically the idea of open university concepts, with the adoption of models, frameworks, methods and standards. Particularly, the authors emphasise the relevance of “grey data” as defined by Borgman (2018, op.cit). This research work acknowledges practices of data sharing as Linked Open Data (LOD) such as the Join

Information Systems Council in the UK (p.705). US universities participate in joint initiatives in which they share a standard set of students' data with publisher to support consistent reporting. In other cases, some adopt APIs registered to GitHub and datasets with Creative Commons Attribute 4.0 licences to analyse specific trends in teaching, learning, participation and drop-out). In other cases, like the Harvard University, mixed formats of dataset are supported from Open-Source owned platforms like Dataverse, where datasets are published for the wider access, with no further elaboration. Authors conclude that "there appears to be little order or consistency in the data offered" (p.708), being the concept of open data initiatives in higher education new.

Case studies about data usage

Open data case studies can be relevant to understand best practises and solutions found in specific context. We identified 9 (32.14%) out of 28 articles explicitly marked as national or institutional cases. The HE grey data category is the most represented, accounting for 33.33% of the case studies. This data type typically includes institutional and administrative data related to higher education, often used for integrating and improving education systems and analytics, though not necessarily made open. HE grey data finds applications in studies such as the University College Dublin's Mathematics Support Centre, where predictive modelling based on six years of student and tutor activity data optimizes resource allocation, reducing queue times and extending service hours. Another study leveraging HE grey data uses semantic web technologies, like the e-LION model, to integrate and analyse heterogeneous learning management system data for predictive modelling and student performance forecasting.

Grey Open Data generated by universities and MOOCs data each constitute 22.22% of the case studies. The former emphasizes transparency and the reuse of education-related datasets, while the latter focuses on online learning environments, exploring issues such as student behaviour and dropout rates. For example, Grey Open Data is used in a study examining the readiness of Colombian higher education institutions for open data, emphasizing transparency and conceptual evaluation models. Similarly, a Brazilian case highlights the development of ontologies for organizing and sharing data in higher education, creating foundational frameworks for stakeholders. This convergence in the Latin American region reflects growing interest in how open government data from universities can be reused to improve higher education provision and promote administrative transparency. MOOCs data is showcased in a study focusing on edX, a platform jointly developed by Harvard and MIT, which applies data analysis methods to examine learner types and behaviours, offering insights into online learning dynamics. Another case study addresses the 70% dropout rate in MOOCs, proposing a systematic analysis of student profiles and course management strategies using the MiriadaX platform to improve outcomes.

Smaller contributions come from OGD HE data (Open Government Data for Higher Education) and ORD (Open Research Data, typically generated by researchers within universities), each representing 11.11% of the case studies. OGD HE data is employed for analysing government-provided datasets to enhance transparency and decision-making in education, while ORD supports open science practices and collaboration for teaching and learning (though research collaboration is excluded as the focus of this analysis, it is worth noting that a significant body of literature emphasizes ORD re-use for open science).

Overall, these data sources exemplify the integration of diverse datasets to address educational challenges such as resource optimization, predictive analytics, and improving learning outcomes. These case studies highlight the transformative potential of open and grey data in fostering innovation and equity in education systems worldwide.

Open data characteristics: accessibility, interoperability, stewardship

Access to data is still a concern. For example, Dymora et al. (2018) highlighted that there is a continuous growth in the number of open data portals globally, with the increasing adoption of interoperable formats like RDF Turtle for linking data, and the establishment of centralized data hubs like the European Union Open Data Portal. Through their review of the literature, the authors consider that there is a shift towards greater transparency, accessibility, and integration of public data to drive societal and economic benefits, but there are still critical principles of open data, including free access, availability in modifiable formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, RDF), and allowance for reuse and redistribution. Open Government Data (OGD), a subset of open data, plays a significant role in enhancing public understanding of government operations and improving decision-making processes.

Digging into educational data through our snowball technique, Kijanovic & Kmosar (2023) aimed at discussing the need for accessible and transparent open data in education. Their case stemmed from a country (Serbia)'s efforts to digitize public administration in contrast with another country (Estonia "Educational Eye"). Also, PISA studies were considered to display the positive impacts of sharing open data. In this context, legal frameworks, technical requirements, and ethical considerations, including data privacy and accessibility, were also analysed. The study considered that Open data fosters transparency, equity, and innovation in education by enabling informed policymaking, enhancing institutional performance, and supporting global collaboration among researchers. The transnational examples (Serbia, Estonia, US) illustrate how open data facilitates stakeholder engagement, data-driven decision-making, and the creation of interactive platforms for evaluating educational systems. However, gaps in data availability, especially in the Serbian case, and insufficient attention to educational datasets in that country underscore the need for targeted investment and strategic development, which might mitigate regional disparities, the authors pose. This study consolidates the trends analysed in the background of this report and it is useful in reporting transnational differences, Nonetheless, practices in Higher Education are mixed with public education systems.

A systematic literature review methodology by Rodriguez-F et al. (2021) considered that there is an increased adoption of Linked Open Data (LOD) principles to improve data interoperability, the widespread use of RDF standards and RESTful APIs for data publishing and linking, and a significant concentration of open data initiatives in European HEIs, which account for the majority of documented efforts.

The transformative potential of data in solving administrative and governance issues in education is exemplified through various studies, constituting 79% of the total articles (22 out of 28). Most articles dealt with the meso-level, proposing solutions to deal with institutional data to address issues such as students' recruitment, students' profiling, students' drop out, students' success, students effective testing, tutoring, staff recruitment. Dorodchi et al. (2019) propose the use of synthetic data generators, addressing data usability concerns in higher education learning analytics by enabling researchers to optimize algorithms while maintaining compliance with privacy laws. Feng and Zhao (2021) explore the application of data analysis in MOOCs using edX data, focusing on learner behaviour and characteristics, thereby enhancing online education systems. Guo emphasizes the use of data mining to optimize information access in distance education platforms, demonstrating its significance in improving digital education services.

Osorio-Sanabria et al. (2018) contribute to data governance, by designing a model to evaluate the readiness of Colombian higher education institutions for open data practices, promoting transparency and efficiency. Paneque et al. (2023) propose the e-LION ontology model for managing large volumes of heterogeneous data in Learning Management Systems, advancing predictive modelling and strategic decision-making. Pukach et al. (2024) utilise machine learning methods for student classification and recruitment, refining strategies to enhance academic placement.

Roda-Sanchez et al. (2024), representing adopt the Digital Twin approach, integrating sensor and open data for efficient campus management, emphasizing privacy and open data stewardship. Taganov et al. (2017) present a geoinformation-based model to measure and mitigate educational risks, providing comprehensive insights into institutional performance. Umer et al. (2022) analyse virtual learning environment data to predict students' academic performance, demonstrating the importance of demographic data in improving learning outcomes.

Victorino et al. (2017) develop a decision support system for Brazilian higher education data governance, offering strategic resources for institutional analysis. Perez-Vergara and Li (2018) representing, design a decision model for equitable faculty staffing using human resources and enrolment data, addressing staffing challenges. Finally, Howard and Cronin (2022), also comprising optimize tutoring services at University College Dublin using predictive modelling, showcasing how data analysis enhances resource allocation and service efficiency.

The studies reveal several emerging trends in access, usage and interoperability. Firstly, the problem of integration of data analytics, with several studies focusing on integrating advanced data analytics techniques, such as machine learning and predictive modelling, into governance and educational processes to enhance decision-making and optimize outcomes. Concerning technological innovation and campus management, the adoption of Digital Twin technology (Roda-Sanchez et al.) and geoinformation systems (Taganov et al., op.cit) reflects a shift toward smart and efficient educational infrastructure management. Furthermore, there is a concern on the personalisation of educational services. Studies by Umer et al. and Pukach et al. (op.cit) highlight the use of demographic and learning data to personalize academic services, from student recruitment to predictive academic support. Also, the problem of transparency and governance, represented for example by the research of Osorio-Sanabria et al. and Victorino et al., which demonstrates the growing emphasis on transparency through open data practices and structured governance models. To this regard, cross-disciplinary approaches based on multiple studies in this sample such as those by Dorodchi et al. (op.cit) and Paneque et al. (op.cit), underscore the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in addressing complex data challenges. Finally, MOOC data is a recurring focus, as shown by Feng and Zhao (2021), Mareca and Bordel (2019), and others, addressing challenges like dropout rates and learner diversity, but also, demonstrating the opportunistic approach in the development of all educational data mining and data-driven approaches in education.

These trends collectively highlight how data-driven approaches are reshaping educational governance, resource management, and student support, fostering more transparent, efficient, and inclusive systems. The collaboration among authors across various institutions underscores the global and interdisciplinary nature of this effort.

Data for teaching and learning

The use of open data for teaching and learning (micro-level) is illustrated through four studies and practices drawn from the abstracts. One example is an interdisciplinary teaching project that integrates open government data into higher education curricula across fields such as political science, economics, and computer engineering. This project focuses on equipping students with professional and technological skills to understand, access, analyse, and utilize open data. The initiative evaluates its effectiveness through student feedback via questionnaires, providing valuable insights into how open data can enhance teaching and learning. Another example emphasises the use of web 2.0 tools in higher education to foster co-creation practices. This study develops a conceptual framework for university openness and co-creation performance, leveraging open data as a core element to enhance collaboration and innovation in the educational context. The ATLAS Open Data project demonstrates the role of open-access data from high-energy physics experiments for educational outreach and research purposes. These resources have been widely utilized in universities and schools globally, showcasing the integration of simulations and data sets to make complex scientific concepts accessible and engaging for students. Lastly, GUI Test Migrator, a novel tool for online education, addresses scalability challenges in assessing student coding assignments. The tool automates the migration of test cases for Android apps, significantly reducing instructors' workload while ensuring the accuracy of evaluations. This approach exemplifies the potential of data-driven technologies in managing large-scale educational platforms.

These practices highlight the versatility of open data and digital tools in transforming teaching methodologies and enriching learning experiences across disciplines.

It is worth noting that some studies are moving beyond the Open Data usage as Open Educational Resource but are trying to determine a new methodological approach. Cantador et al. (2023) introduced a novel educational initiative designed to explore the application of open government data in higher education. The authors purport, after referring to other three studies of open data for teaching and learning in the fields of Statistics, technology and education, that there is need of a multidisciplinary approach to investigate the value of open government data in education. By implementing and assessing various learning activities across degree programs in diverse fields—political science, economics and finance, and computer engineering—aiming to cultivate professional and technological competencies for comprehending, accessing, analysing, and utilising open data. The authors conducted several open data learning activities of different nature (i.e., writing reports, oral presentations, practical assignments, and final degree work) and methodologies (i.e., teacher-centred, student-centred, and project-based). For example, in Public Administration and Political Science, they were guided to appraise governance, transparency and accountability by analysing the information on data portals. Students from Business Studies explored the differences between open data platforms and explore real cases considering the quality of shared open data and the potential adopting by the private sector. Also, students from Computer Engineering implemented and evaluated recommender systems that exploited OGD to address participatory citizenship. The results of this recent research demonstrated the relevance to cultivate or enhance competencies in data processing and analysis, as well as to encourage the utilisation of open government data in everyday tasks, such as verifying the accuracy of information disseminated in news and social media and conducting research projects. Also, this investigation consolidated the value of OGD for learning, but don't encompass necessarily the usage of "grey" educational data.

Methods to improve open data usage

Overall, all the studies analysed reveal a strong concern on the methodology to publish, label, collect, analyse and model, to adopt Open Data through significant approaches for the improvement of different areas of the Higher Education provision. Twenty-five (25) studies out of the 28 (90%) selected deal with methodological approaches to deal with Open Data as an aim of the research beyond the study conducted.

The studies reviewed reveal a strong emphasis on leveraging advanced methodologies to address challenges in education governance, teaching innovation, and operational efficiency. A significant number of studies demonstrate a focus on data modelling, which has emerged as a critical approach for analysing and predicting key outcomes. For instance, Paneque et al. developed the e-LION ontology model to integrate and analyse multi-source e-learning data, showcasing its applicability in predictive modelling and student behaviour classification. Similarly, Butuner and Calp employed machine learning algorithms, such as Random Forest and Deep Learning, to predict academic success in distance education, while Howard and Cronin optimized tutoring center staffing by applying predictive modelling to student visit data. Chockkalingam et al. introduced a novel approach for predicting course workloads using institutional data, and Panagiotakopoulos et al. utilized machine learning to forecast MOOC dropout rates with high accuracy. These studies underscore the expanding role of predictive analytics in education.

Data mining also stands out as a prominent methodology, particularly in studies like Guo's, which applied mining techniques to optimize data collection and enhance access to distance education resources. Similarly, Butuner and Calp integrated data mining with machine learning to extract insights into academic performance.

Another notable trend is the adoption of ontological mediation for knowledge integration. Paneque et al. and Silva and Belo demonstrated how ontologies could structure and organize knowledge, facilitating semantic querying and enabling stakeholders to better manage and reuse data. For instance, Silva and Belo developed an ontology specifically tailored to Brazil's National Higher Education Assessment System.

The focus on policy and governance analysis reflects an increasing need to structure and regulate educational data systems. Osorio-Sanabria et al. proposed a conceptual framework for assessing open data readiness in Colombian higher education institutions, emphasizing governance as a tool for transparency and efficiency. Similarly, Si and Liu explored data ethics governance frameworks, highlighting the central role of research institutions in managing data ethics and policy. Bradberry and Pittges addressed theoretical aspects of governance, while Perez-Vergara and Li developed decision models for equitable faculty staffing based on institutional data.

Synthetic data generation emerges as a solution to ethical and privacy challenges, with Dorodchi et al. proposing synthetic datasets to maintain compliance with privacy laws while enabling reproducible research in learning analytics. This aligns with the broader trend toward balancing open data initiatives with privacy and ethical considerations, as discussed by Si and Liu.

Teaching innovation is another area of focus, particularly in studies like Cantador et al.'s, which explored multidisciplinary approaches to teaching with open government data, aiming to equip students with professional and technological skills. Toffolin's work on the ATLAS Open Data project similarly

emphasizes the educational potential of open-access data resources in high-energy physics and computer sciences.

The global focus on open data is exemplified by initiatives like Brazil's National Higher Education Assessment System (Silva and Belo) and CERN's ATLAS Open Data project (Toffolin), which highlight the potential for open data to enhance education and public policy. Moreover, studies like Lohse et al.'s emphasize the challenges in ensuring the quality and accessibility of educational open data, advocating for standardized frameworks and policies to bridge existing gaps.

Finally, research on MOOCs and online education reveals a growing interest in addressing the scalability challenges and high dropout rates associated with these platforms. Feng and Zhao analyzed learner behavior in MOOCs, while Kumar et al. and Panagiotakopoulos et al. employed advanced machine learning techniques to predict and mitigate dropout rates, demonstrating the potential for data-driven interventions to improve student retention.

In conclusion, the reviewed studies highlight a robust shift toward data-driven methodologies in education, with a focus on predictive modelling, governance frameworks, ethical data sharing, and innovative teaching strategies. These efforts illustrate the potential of integrating advanced data technologies to foster inclusivity, transparency, and efficiency in educational systems worldwide. The findings underscore the growing collaboration between educational institutions, technology, and policy, paving the way for a more informed and equitable future in education.

Data ethics

The articles addressing data ethics in educational contexts reflect a rich exploration of the challenges and opportunities associated with the growing use of data in education. They highlight the need to balance innovation with ethical responsibility, particularly in areas like privacy, governance, and data accessibility.

Dorodchi et al. delve into the ethical implications of creating and sharing datasets, particularly for learning analytics in higher education. They propose the use of synthetic data generators to address privacy concerns, enabling researchers to reproduce and scale their work without compromising sensitive student information. This approach underscores the need for ethical safeguards in leveraging open data for academic purposes, ensuring compliance with privacy laws while advancing research reproducibility.

Roda-Sanchez et al. focus on the development of Digital Twin frameworks, an innovative approach that combines sensor data with external open datasets to create digital replicas of physical environments. While this strategy has the potential to revolutionize campus management and operational efficiency, it introduces critical ethical challenges, especially around data stewardship. The integration of semantic knowledge graphs within these frameworks adds complexity, demanding accountability and transparency in managing public and private data sources.

Si and Liu bring a governance perspective to the discussion, offering a comprehensive framework for data ethics governance. By employing grounded theory and social network analysis, they analyse 78 policies from UK institutions, illustrating how collaborative networks can optimize governance practices. Their findings emphasize the importance of a lifecycle approach, addressing ethical issues from data collection to utilization and beyond. This framework identifies governance initiatives, guidance, and context descriptions as essential components of effective data ethics policies, while underscoring the central role of research institutions in driving ethical practices.

Lohse et al. address the challenges of sharing anonymized datasets in the context of MOOCs. Their study reveals a significant gap in the availability of de-identified, open data for research, which hampers reproducibility and innovation. They stress the ethical difficulties of making student performance data accessible while maintaining adequate privacy protections. This lack of standardization in data sharing policies and tools poses a barrier to advancing research in online education.

Across these studies, certain trends emerge that reveal the evolving priorities in educational data ethics. One prominent theme is the ongoing effort to balance transparency and privacy. Synthetic data generation and anonymization techniques are central to achieving this balance, allowing researchers to utilize data without compromising individual privacy. Another key trend is the lifecycle approach to ethical governance, as articulated by Si and Liu, which integrates ethical considerations at every stage of data management, from collection to disposal. The importance of collaboration also features prominently, with robust policy frameworks and stakeholder involvement seen as essential for effective governance. Furthermore, technological innovation, exemplified by Digital Twins and semantic knowledge graphs, offers new opportunities for data integration and analysis but demands advanced governance mechanisms to address ethical concerns. Finally, the barriers to open data sharing, as highlighted in Lohse et al.'s work, reflect broader challenges in making data usable for research while safeguarding privacy.

From the papers further collected through snowballing, it is worth to comment the study of McNicol et al., who found out that engaging stakeholders directly in the design of ethical frameworks for corporate data governance can significantly enhance transparency and stakeholder-centricity. They used revised canonical action research methodology, which led them to the development of the Enhanced Enterprise Data Ethics Framework (EEDEF). The framework emphasises stakeholder involvement, the ethical treatment of corporate data, and the importance of transparency in data usage within higher education institutions. Findings also highlighted the dominance of transparency as a core ethical principle among all stakeholder groups.

In conclusion, these studies collectively underscore the critical role of ethical governance in managing educational data systems. As data becomes more integral to educational processes, navigating the tension between innovation and ethical responsibility will require thoughtful strategies. The focus on synthetic data, collaborative governance frameworks, and policy-driven practices illustrates a maturing approach to managing these complexities. Looking forward, there is a clear need to standardize ethical practices across institutions, enhance transparency, and leverage technology to safeguard privacy while maximizing the potential of data to advance education.

We have two areas of intervention: firstly, a social and regulatory area that claims for increasing adoption of stakeholder-centred approaches to data governance with frameworks to navigate regulatory complexities, and the growing institutional emphasis on balancing ethical data practices with organizational and technological advancements. From a technical perspective, synthetic data might play crucial role in advancing transparency and collaboration, and an increasing reliance on technology to safeguard privacy in the development of data-driven educational tools.

To wrap up, the several studies considered bring to the fore that open data in higher education encompasses various types of data and offers several benefits but also presents challenges and ethical considerations.

Discussion

The analysis of articles led to the discovery of key topics insisting on the problem of open data formats and meta-data to improve their interoperability and accessibility, with several cases introducing relevant interventions to solve the problem and enhance open data. Data stewardship, in connection with data ethics, was a challenge clearly emerging in connection with the efforts to improve open data infrastructures. Nonetheless, there is a parallel growing interest in teaching with and for the usage of data, improving data literacy in a world where professionalism will be surely connected to understanding and operating critically within datafied systems.

In this paragraph, we will delve into international reports that, while dealing with digital transformation, place data-driven practises and open data within the topics under analysis. Reports are also relevant given the recommendations that are a more readable outcome for policy makers and practitioners than the “raw” academic scholarship. Therefore, reports’ impact is allegedly more important. We will adopt reports’ analysis to wrap up our exploration and configure categories and methodologies of analysis of our next part: the Open University case studies. We will consider four relevant reports of international circulation, covering the US, Europe, Asia and the global perspectives (UNESCO).

The *2024 EDUCAUSE Horizon Action Plan: Unified Data Models* (EDUCAUSE, 2024) outlines a vision for the next decade in higher education, focusing on the implementation of unified data models to enhance learning analytics and the holistic student experience.

The methodology employed involved contributions from a panel of nine experts in higher education, facilitated by EDUCAUSE through foresight methodologies adapted from the Institute for the Future. Panellists reviewed emerging trends and technologies from the 2023 EDUCAUSE Horizon Report: Holistic Student Experience Edition, envisioned a preferred future for unified data models, and analysed potential threats and opportunities. Remote discussions held on November 16, 2023, provided the foundation for the action plan. Key areas of focus include future goals and actionable steps. Among the future goals are fostering ethical, equitable, and inclusive data governance that emphasizes student privacy, security, and autonomy; promoting digital literacy among students, faculty, and staff to enhance informed use and governance of data; implementing data mesh architecture to enable unified data access and interoperability across institutions; and advancing comprehensive learning records (CLR 2.0) to integrate data from K–12 to postsecondary education and workforce credentials. Actions are proposed at various levels: individuals are encouraged to engage in lifelong learning for data literacy, practice ethical data stewardship, and actively involve students in data-related activities. Departments and institutions are tasked with redesigning workflows to incorporate data responsibilities, adopting scalable infrastructure, and fostering collaboration across departments. At the multi-institutional level, the action plan advocates for creating industry-wide standards for data interoperability and transparency while negotiating fair pricing with third-party partners. The results envisioned include enhanced student engagement and retention, increased institutional efficiency, and the democratization of data usage. A cornerstone of this vision is the evolution of CLR 2.0, which aims to provide actionable insights that inform both individual learning journeys and institutional strategy. This comprehensive vision emphasizes the importance of collaboration, governance, and the transformative power of data, reimagining the future of higher education to be more inclusive, data-driven, and impactful.

This are resounding notes for the work of Rodriguez et al. (2021), whose review of the literature found out that the main applications of open data in higher education institutions include fostering research through

Open Science initiatives and enhanced research dissemination, improving teaching by creating educational resources and developing curricula, enhancing institutional management in areas such as human resources, quality assurance, and resource planning, and advancing social responsibility by driving innovation and strengthening university-community partnerships. Yet the challenges are significant and multifaceted. These include intellectual property issues, where the misuse of research data and exposure of sensitive information pose risks; lack of standardization, with inconsistent data governance frameworks and metadata standards across institutions; legal and ethical barriers, such as jurisprudence and privacy concerns limiting the openness of certain datasets; and operational issues, such as insufficient infrastructure for data storage and dissemination, as well as inadequate training and awareness among faculty and staff regarding the potential of open data.

To consider another geopolitical region and a complementary focus of debate, the EU report from the Schoolnet network focused on data ethics (European Schoolnet, 2023). The trends in Europe are marked by a growing adoption of open data initiatives, with European higher education institutions leading efforts to promote transparency and accountability. This includes the development of comprehensive open data portals by universities like the Open University (UK), University of Alicante (Spain), and ITMO University (Russia). Moreover, there is an increasing emphasis on Linked Open Data (LOD), aimed at interlinking and reusing datasets to facilitate interoperability across systems, reflecting a broader move towards innovative and collaborative data practices across the region. However, the Schoolnet report spots another relevant concern. It is a product of the *Data4Learning Webinar Series*, and it delves into the complexities of ethically managing educational data while prioritizing student and teacher rights. Experts such as Duuk Baten, Wayne Holmes, and Sonia Livingstone explore themes like trust, safety, data ownership, usability, equity, and systemic governance. The concept of "ethical data" is reframed to emphasize human agency over technological determinism. Holmes suggests that ethical educational data practices should protect dignity, autonomy, and safety while ensuring informed consent. Livingstone adds a layer of urgency by aligning data practices with the *United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child*, highlighting the importance of safeguarding children from potential long-term consequences. Governance emerged as a pivotal topic, with Baten advocating for "justified choice" frameworks that consider the intent behind data collection and its systemic application. Both public and private sectors are scrutinised for their roles in data stewardship, with calls for stronger public sector accountability to prevent over-reliance on commercial interests. Through these lenses, we might say that overall education systems (and HEIs specifically) face a paradox: while data fosters personalised learning and resource optimization, it also risks over-surveillance and commercial exploitation. In this regard, Holmes critiques the efficacy of learning analytics, arguing for robust evidence before adopting new technologies in classrooms. The report underscores the need for nuanced consent processes, minimum standards for educational technology, and enhanced digital literacy. In conclusion, this report advocates for a data ecosystem that prioritizes human-centric values, fosters collaboration, and upholds ethical standards, aiming for a transformative yet just use of data in education.

To accomplish this view on digital transformation that involves open data production and adoption, the *insight report on ICT in higher education and TVET in Pakistan* (UNESCO-IITE, 2022) outlines a comprehensive roadmap for leveraging technology to enhance education and align it with national development goals. The findings are grounded in a dual-method approach: an extensive desk review of policies, frameworks, and global data sources, coupled with a detailed case study crafted through structured surveys and expert feedback. This meticulous process highlights both the opportunities and challenges within Pakistan's educational landscape. ICT integration has emerged as a cornerstone of

Pakistan's higher education strategy, particularly in response to the disruptions caused by COVID-19. Institutions have increasingly adopted hybrid learning models, learning management systems (LMS), and digital platforms to ensure continuity in education. The Higher Education Commission (HEC) has positioned ICT at the centre of its strategic vision, aiming to equip both educators and students with essential digital skills. TVET institutions play a pivotal role, emphasizing ICT training to align workforce capabilities with evolving labour market demands.

However, the report underscores significant challenges that need immediate attention. The shortage of skilled teaching staff, inadequate digital infrastructure in rural areas, and persistent gender disparities in ICT education are barriers to realizing the full potential of digital transformation. Moreover, high dropout rates in secondary and higher education further compound these challenges, threatening the inclusivity and effectiveness of education reforms. To address these issues, the report presents a forward-looking agenda for action. Strengthening public-private collaboration is paramount; partnerships between industries, higher education institutions, and TVET can align curricula with market needs and bridge the skills gap. Inclusivity must also be a priority, with targeted initiatives to expand ICT education for women and underserved communities, ensuring equitable access to opportunities. Capacity building is another critical area of focus: The report advocates for robust teacher training programs to enhance digital teaching capabilities and the establishment of dedicated e-learning units within institutions to manage and produce digital content. Additionally, modernising TVET systems to incorporate lifelong learning pathways will allow learners to advance from vocational training to higher education, fostering a culture of continuous skill development. Digital infrastructure and curriculum innovation are highlighted as essential for the future. Investments in modern ICT infrastructure can support online learning and administration, while curricula should be diversified to include advanced fields like artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and big data. To complement these efforts, the report stresses the importance of ethical frameworks for data usage, ensuring privacy, security, and trust in educational systems. In summary, the report envisions a digitally empowered education system in Pakistan and places a key role in data usage to transform such a system.

If the former report emphasises how digital transformation requires as key action to consider data ecosystems and infrastructures, the *Benchmarking for Open Universities* report (UNESCO-IITE, 2023), serving as a comprehensive guide to improving the quality and performance of open and distance learning (ODL) universities, provides a framework to reflect on the role of open data and data-driven practises across such institutions. This report emphasizes benchmarking as a critical tool for evaluating and enhancing the efficiency, inclusivity, and sustainability of open universities (OUs). It identifies the unique challenges and opportunities faced by these institutions, including the integration of digital technologies, promoting inclusivity, and maintaining quality standards amid increasing competition. The report underscores five relevant areas of attention: a) Quality Assurance and Benchmarking; b) Digital Transformation; c) Inclusivity and Lifelong Learning; d) Global Best Practices and Case Studies; e) Challenges. For the first area, Benchmarking serves as a systematic approach for assessing institutional performance, enabling Open Universities (OUs) to compare their practices and outcomes with peers to identify areas for improvement. This process emphasizes the importance of implementing quality assurance mechanisms that are specifically tailored to the unique operational models of OUs, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness. As OUs transition from traditional correspondence-based education to more dynamic, technology-enhanced learning systems, such as online platforms and massive open online courses (MOOCs), the adoption of digital tools for teaching, learner support, and administrative functions becomes critical. Leveraging these technologies is not only essential for enhancing educational

delivery but also for maintaining competitiveness in an increasingly digital and globalized higher education landscape. For the second area, it is worth to consider that Open universities are undergoing a pivotal transition from traditional correspondence-based education to flexible, technology-enhanced systems. This shift includes the adoption of online platforms, massive open online courses (MOOCs), and digital tools for teaching, learner support, and administration. Such innovations are deemed essential for sustaining competitiveness in an increasingly digitalized higher education landscape. In the third area, we must consider that Open Universities (OUs) place a strong emphasis on inclusivity, striving to make education accessible to underrepresented groups such as rural learners, women, and differently abled individuals. This commitment to inclusivity is complemented by a dedicated focus on lifelong learning, aligning with the global Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims to ensure equitable and quality education for all. Through these efforts, OUs address educational disparities while fostering opportunities for continuous learning and development across diverse communities. For the fourth area, the report synthesizes international experiences from 21 open universities across diverse regions, offering a matrix of benchmarking domains and indicators. In this regard, governance, IT infrastructure, staff development, curriculum design, and learner support are analysed through shared best practices. Finally, the challenges (fifth area) relate to resource limitations, staff capacity, retention rates, and technology adoption remain barriers to maximizing the potential of OUs. Though open data and data are just a piece of the puzzle, the benchmarking approach supports the methodological reflection on the role of datafied processes within open universities.

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